

ROYAL VETERINARY COLLEGE, UNIVERSITY OF LONDON

**A ONE HEALTH APPROACH TO TACKLE SCHISTOSOMIASIS IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA:
Transmission, control and population genetics of schistosomes from African livestock of the
Senegal River Basin**

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ABSTRACT

Schistosomiasis, a neglected tropical disease also known as Bilharzia or snail fever caused by *Schistosoma* trematodes, is reported in 78 tropical and subtropical countries across five of the seven continents. However, most of the global burden of this water-borne disease is predominantly found in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), a region where the need for a One Health approach with anew focus on relevant animal reservoirs has recently been recognised.

The existence of ecological settings with a multi-host, multi-parasite biological system is further emphasized by the increasing recovery of hybrids between livestock-specific (such as *S. bovis*) and human-specific schistosomes (with *S. haematobium*) from people across SSA. Amongst such settings is the Senegal River Basin (SRB), a schistosomiasis endemic area with year-round and seasonal transmission locations where both humans and their livestock—in particular domestic ruminants that can act as schistosome reservoirs—are affected. While a lack of structured control programs targeting animals remains in SSA, attempts by SRB farmers to decrease the disease impact on livestock productivity have been reported, albeit using inappropriate praziquantel (PZQ) dosages.

This doctoral thesis explored a potential transmission control strategy for livestock schistosomiasis by focusing on domestic ruminants of the SRB. Three interconnected lines of enquiry were investigated. Firstly, an illustrative herd-level mathematical model of transmission and control based on baseline 2017 prevalence estimates from 200 sympatric bovines, found that the impact of a test-and-treat intervention targeted at SRB cattle is likely to be significant. Secondly, statistical analyses of 2018 data from a small PZQ drug efficacy trial (59 bovines, 22 goats and 22 sheep, naturally infected by schistosomes) used to derive preliminary drug efficacy estimates for a single 25 mg/kg PZQ dose, highlighted variation in treatment response by animal species and village. Thirdly, optimisation of microsatellite molecular markers to evaluate miracidia recovered from bovines with population genetics methods (175 pre- and 25 post-PZQ miracidia genotyped), uncovered a greater level of differentiation between pre- and post-PZQ samples than between villages during the 2018 trial. Interestingly, genetic signatures of parasite inbreeding were found in the village in which treatment was particularly ineffective. The optimal livestock schistosomiasis PZQ dosage and treatment regimen for SSA domestic ruminants are yet to be determined.

This thesis underscores the need for structured control interventions targeted at ruminants within the transmission hotspot of the SRB. Findings represent a contribution towards the design of a One Health strategy to control livestock schistosomiasis in SSA. Such strategy would minimise the risk of PZQ resistance, safeguarding the efficacy of this essential medicine while helping to limit the spread of zoonotic schistosomes and the emergence of hybrids in the region.

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LIST OF KEY ABBREVIATIONS

PZQ: Praziquantel

SSA: sub-Saharan Africa

OH: One Health

NTD: Neglected Tropical Disease

MDA: Mass Drug Administration

PC: Preventive Chemotherapy

WASH: Water, Sanitation and Hygiene

SRB: Senegal River Basin

RT: Richard Toll, Senegal

BK: Barkedji, Senegal

ZELS: Zoonoses and Emerging Livestock Systems programme/project

TnT: Test-and-Treat

MHT: Miracidia Hatching Technique

POC-CCA: Point-of-Care Circulating Cathodic Antigen

KK: Kato-Katz

PPV: Positive Predictive Value

NPV: Negative Predictive Value

MPG: Miracidia per Gram

MRR: Miracidia Reduction Rate

BCI: Bayesian Credible Intervals

CI: Confidence Intervals

BCS: Body Condition Score

CLMM: Cumulative Link Mixed Model

GLM: Generalized Linear Model

ANOVA: Analysis of Variance

Pop-gen: Population genetics

PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction

AMOVA: Analysis of Molecular Variance

PCoA: Principal Coordinates Analysis

PREFACE

“Uncertainty is an uncomfortable position. But certainty is an absurd one.”

Voltaire, French philosopher (1694-1778)

This thesis presents work carried out by the candidate since October 2020 as part of the LIDo Doctoral Training Programme.

The PhD project was severely disrupted by the COVID-19 pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2, affecting planned fieldwork—which did not happen—and subsequent laboratory work—which was delayed and rethought. As a disruption mitigation put in place during the first year of the PhD, the candidate investigated a developing One Health topic at the time: outbreaks of SARS-CoV-2 in mink farms. By reviewing grey literature and collating publicly available data (World Animal Health Information System) on outbreak notifications by member states of the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), this study resulted in a first author opinion piece published in the scientific journal *Evolutionary Applications* included in Appendix A, an RVC alumni magazine article (1), and an interview featured in The New York Times (2).

Notwithstanding disruptions, this thesis explores a One Health (OH) approach to tackle schistosomiasis in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Chapter 1 introduces the OH approach in the context of current schistosomiasis elimination targets, highlighting the importance of livestock hosts in SSA. Chapter 2 provides a simulation of the OH approach by modelling targeted treatment of infected bovines in a highly endemic area of SSA, the Senegal River Basin (SRB). Chapter 3 assesses the efficacy of treatment against livestock schistosomiasis in SRB. Chapter 4 details the use of microsatellite molecular markers to investigate the population genetics of bovine schistosomiasis in SRB. Chapter 5 discusses key findings and implications of the work presented in the preceding thesis chapters.

Elaborating on the above, further details are as follows. Chapter 1 (General Introduction) is a modified version of a first author opinion piece published in the scientific journal *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London Series B: Biological Sciences*. The published version of this article is included in Appendix B. Chapter 2 uses data from the Zoonoses and Emerging Livestock Systems (ZELS) project—collected and collated by others before the start of the PhD—to parameterise a mathematical model of bovine schistosomiasis transmission adapted from a published human schistosomiasis model—model adaptation carried out by others, model implementation and analysis carried out by the candidate. Moreover, chapter 2 is a modified version of a first author original research article published in the scientific journal *Frontiers in Tropical Diseases*. This article is included in Appendix C. Chapter 3 presents secondary analysis conducted by the candidate of previously collected samples—primary data collection as part of a subcomponent of the ZELS project carried out by others. Chapter 4 presents further analysis on a subset of these samples. While others extracted DNA from

some of the samples and performed all species characterisation work, and an external company conducted fragment length analysis (FLA) of amplicons, the candidate conducted the remainder of the work detailed in chapter 4. Therefore, the candidate, hereby referred to as the author, performed: sample selection; miracidia and worm elutions; literature review for microsatellite marker selection; multi-locus PCR optimisation; FLA raw data processing; and all the genotyping analyses and interpretation presented in chapter 4.

Each of the data chapters (i.e., Chapters 2, 3 and 4) are consistently structured in modified scientific journal format, hence there is some content overlap between them. Relevant supplementary material for each data chapter is presented as chapter appendices. All references are gathered in a single bibliography at the end of the thesis.

Both the data analysis and written work presented in this thesis were carried out by the author under the supervision of Prof. Joanne Webster and Dr. Martin Walker from the Royal Veterinary College.

CHAPTER 1

General Introduction

1.1. Summary

The past four years has seen the launch of a new World Health Organization (WHO) Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) Roadmap, together with revised Control and Elimination Guidelines. Across all, there is now a clear emphasis on the need to incorporate a One Health approach, recognizing the critical links between human and animal health and the environment. Schistosomiasis, caused by *Schistosoma* spp. trematodes, is a NTD of global medical and veterinary importance, with over 220 million people and untold millions of livestock currently infected. Its burden remains extremely high in certain regions, particularly within sub-Saharan Africa, despite over two decades of mass preventive chemotherapy (mass drug administration), predominantly to school-aged children. In Africa, in contrast to Asia, any zoonotic component of schistosomiasis transmission and its implications for disease control has, until recently, been largely ignored. This introductory chapter reviews recent epidemiological, clinical, molecular, and modelling work across both Asia and Africa. Furthermore, this chapter outlines the evolutionary history and transmission dynamics of *Schistosoma* species, and emphasises the emerging risk raised by both wildlife reservoirs and viable hybridization between human and animal schistosomes. To achieve the 2030 WHO Roadmap elimination targets, a truly multi-disciplinary One Health perspective must be implemented.

1.2. Introduction

Momentum in the fight against Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs), 20 epidemiologically complex conditions that predominantly affect impoverished communities (3), has been building alongside a change in targets from morbidity control to elimination. With renewed emphasis on the need to incorporate a One Health approach, “an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimize the health of people, animals and ecosystems” (4) [p.viii], the World Health Organization (WHO) has launched a series of documents over the past three years, including a revised 2021-2030 NTDs Roadmap (5), a revised Guideline on control and elimination of human schistosomiasis (6), a companion One Health approach document for action against NTDs (4), a global strategy on water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) to combat NTDs (7), and a 2022-2026 One Health Joint Plan of Action in conjunction with other international agencies (8). These documents serve to embed One Health at the heart of control efforts for NTDs with significant environmental or zoonotic epidemiological characteristics and stress the importance of One Health in sustainably improving the intertwined health of humans, animals, and their ecosystems (4).

Schistosomiasis is among the most important NTDs and is estimated to infect a quarter of a billion people worldwide (9, 10). This debilitating parasitic disease is present in 78 tropical and subtropical

countries, with major foci across Asia, Africa, and South America (5), and a potentially emerging focus in southern Europe (11). However, its burden is placed overwhelmingly on sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), where 90% of human schistosome infections occur (9, 12, 13), causing approximately 24,000 deaths and at least 2.5 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) in 2016 (5). The parasite's environmental infective stages—snail-infective miracidia and mammal-infective cercariae—are restricted to freshwater habitats of the snail intermediate host, thus schistosomiasis is considered a water-borne disease (7), with ongoing debates for and against its classification as a vector-borne disease (14, 15). Importantly, the clinical consequences of infection by schistosomes are not only experienced by humans, but also by non-human mammalian definitive hosts (16), many of which can act as reservoirs of subsequent human infection for certain schistosome species (17-19).

As of January 2020, of 78 endemic countries 51 are targeted for mass preventive chemotherapy (i.e., mass drug administration, MDA, using praziquantel) by WHO due to moderate to high schistosome transmission (5). The 2030 WHO schistosomiasis elimination goals call for its elimination as a public health problem (EPHP) from all endemic countries—42 in Africa, ten in the Americas, three in Southeast Asia, six in the Western Pacific, 16 in the Eastern Mediterranean and one in Europe (20)—with EPHP defined as less than 1% heavy intensity infections (≥ 50 eggs per 10 mL urine or ≥ 400 eggs per gram of stool are indicative of a heavy intensity infection (20)). After 20 years of large-scale MDA, morbidity profiles have shifted, thus a revised EPHP definition based on overall infection prevalence instead of heavy-intensity infections has recently been advocated (21). In addition to EPHP, interruption of transmission (IoT) in 25 of the 78 endemic countries has also been set as a WHO schistosomiasis elimination goal, with IoT defined as absence of infection in humans (5). The WHO's EPHP goal has been met in China since 2015 (22) but further national control efforts aim for transmission control (defined by Chinese authorities as less than 1% infection prevalence in humans and livestock, plus two consecutive days of negative malacological surveys and no acute schistosomiasis cases (22)—although schistosomiasis is most commonly a chronic disease, an acute presentation has been described in humans (12) and livestock (23)), as well as transmission interruption (defined by Chinese authorities as absence of infection in humans, livestock, and snails for five consecutive years) (22).

The WHO Roadmap (5) identifies a number of actions required to reach the schistosomiasis elimination targets which include: more comprehensive MDA strategies (e.g., expanding to include more demographic groups, ensuring access to therapeutics, developing alternatives to praziquantel); snail control (e.g., developing appropriate guidelines for targeted snail control and alternative control methods); improved diagnostics—for humans and animals—for micro-mapping and the creation of cross-sectoral mechanisms to coordinate key sectors like WASH, environmental management, and animal health. The Roadmap also expounds on the risk posed by zoonotic reservoirs in Asia and beyond, advocating wider use of veterinary public health interventions (5). Specific points for consideration include improved sanitation and management of animal waste, keeping animals away from transmission sites and treating animals with praziquantel. The companion One Health approach WHO document (4) [p.xi] "provides guidance on the One Health actions needed by major stakeholders

and how to support a paradigm shift towards One Health in national NTD programmes", and is complemented by the One Health Joint Plan of Action (8) framework to support and expand One Health capacities at global, regional, and national level. Hence, the One Health approach is now firmly embedded within WHO guidance on eliminating schistosomiasis.

Operationalizing One Health measures for zoonotic NTDs is nevertheless challenging. For instance, despite long-standing knowledge of the effectiveness of anti-rabies dog vaccination in preventing human deaths (24) capacity building in dog management during mass dog vaccination is still a critical action required to reach the 2030 rabies elimination targets (5); whilst, the recent detection of dracunculiasis cases in animals (25) (with novel transmission pathways (26)) triggered a focus on emerging animal reservoirs to reach eradication targets (5)—there are now more cases in mammals than in humans (25).

This chapter aims to present recent advancements in understanding the evolutionary history and transmission dynamics of *Schistosoma* spp., before outlining the emerging risk posed by wildlife and livestock reservoirs of infection and hybridization between human-infective and livestock-infective schistosomes. The importance of adopting a One Health approach to eliminate schistosomiasis is underlined and potential interventions targeting livestock in SSA that could facilitate progress towards elimination are considered. Finally, the challenges and next steps associated with implementation of a One Health strategy are discussed.

1.2.1. Natural History of *Schistosoma* species

The natural history of schistosomes has been marked by their expanding geographic range, host switching and diversification. Modern molecular biology and genomics indicate an Asian origin of schistosomes, disfavoured the traditional African-origin hypothesis (16). The prevailing 'out of Asia' theory detailed by Lawton et al (16) posits that schistosomes evolved as parasites of rodents from an avian schistosomatid ancestor. The *S. japonicum* clade, which still retains distinct genomic similarities with avian parasites, is thought to be the antecedent of the genus (16). Further speciation likely followed an additional host shift to ungulates that concurred with the diversification of their molluscan intermediate hosts (16). Over 40 vertebrate species can serve as hosts for *S. japonicum* (12, 17, 27, 28), a generalist strategy which may have helped preserve ancestral genomic features (16). All three *S. japonicum* clade species responsible for human disease in Asia—*S. japonicum*, *S. mekongi* and *S. malayensis*—are zoonotic (i.e., transmitted between animals and humans) (27).

Schistosomes likely invaded Africa on at least two separate occasions (16). The first occurrence gave rise to the *S. hippopotami* clade, including two species described from hippos. A second ancestral invasion during the radiation of mammals into Africa during the mid-Miocene caused a population bottleneck that formed a proto-*S. mansoni* clade. This ultimately gave rise to two distinct clades of African schistosomes, the *S. mansoni* clade and the *S. haematobium* clade (16). The more ancestral

S. mansoni clade comprises two species which parasitize rodents, *S. rodhaini* and *S. mansoni* (29). The latter species is the predominant cause of human intestinal schistosomiasis in SSA and also infects non-human primates (30-33) (12, 34, 35) (for a review on non-human primate *S. mansoni* reservoirs in Africa see (36)), although it is often classed as an exclusively human parasite (37). The Atlantic Slave Trade is thought responsible for the geographic expansion of *S. mansoni* to the Caribbean and South America (38, 39). The more recent *S. haematobium* clade comprises nine species which predominantly generate intestinal disease, including the human-infective species *S. haematobium* (the sole cause of urogenital schistosomiasis), *S. intercalatum* and *S. guineensis*, and the species of veterinary health importance causing ruminant intestinal schistosomiasis, *S. bovis*, *S. curassoni* and *S. mattheei*; with the remaining species *S. margrebowiei*, *S. leiperi* and *S. kisumuensis*, mostly found in wildlife (40-43). The postulated reinvasion of Asia from Africa by the *S. indicum* clade, formed of three species of veterinary significance, did not involve a host switch but the continued parasitisation of ungulates and rodents (16).

Despite the prevailing perception of schistosomiasis as a predominantly human disease (12, 37), the *Schistosoma* genus has shown a remarkable ability to diverge and adapt to new hosts and habitats that has persisted beyond its evolutionary origins. This is evident not only among members of the Asian *S. japonicum* clade, but also among several species of both African clades, as exemplified by the establishment and persistence of *S. mansoni* in the Caribbean (39, 44, 45), and the recent expansion of *S. haematobium* x *S. bovis* hybrids into Europe ((46) but see (11)). This adaptability presents increasingly recognised challenges to the control and elimination of schistosomiasis and epitomizes the necessity for a holistic One Health approach.

1.2.2. Hybridization between *Schistosoma* species

Concerns about *Schistosoma* hybridization were initially raised by phenotypic observations of unusual egg and worm morphologies deemed to present intermediate characteristics of different species (23, 40, 47, 48), as well as changes in cercarial emergence and shedding patterns (49). Subsequently, enzymatic studies (40, 50-52), and crucially, molecular techniques, have uncovered strong evidence of the interspecific hybridization of schistosomes (29, 40, 53-56). Interbreeding between different species can result in the creation of hybrid offspring (hybridization) or, if backcrossing of an interspecific hybrid with a parent species, in the introduction of single chromosomal regions or genes from one species to the other (introgressive hybridization, also known as introgression) (34, 57, 58). Such processes can drive genetic variation with the potential to alter the morbidity, host range, and drug susceptibility of parasites (34, 54, 58).

Phylogenetically close schistosome species with overlapping endemicity are more amenable to hybridization. Nonetheless, cases of natural hybridization between *S. japonicum* clade species have not been found (40), while instances of likely non-viable hybridization between distantly related *S. mansoni* with *S. haematobium* have been recorded in humans in Mali (59), Cameroon (60), Senegal

(61), Côte d'Ivoire (62) and Kenya (63). Although, *S. mansoni* clade hybrids have been found in snails in Tanzania (64) and Kenya (29), most evidence of schistosome hybridization involves species within the *S. haematobium* clade, with such interspecific hybrids having been recorded across SSA (Table 1.1.; for a review on *Schistosoma* hybridizations see (40)).

The interspecific mixing of *S. haematobium* with *S. bovis* has been highlighted in several West African foci (56, 65) (Table 1.1). In particular, within different areas of the Senegal River Basin, a schistosomiasis hotspot, a heterogenous distribution of *S. haematobium* x *S. bovis* hybrids has been reported (66), and a positive association with *S. mansoni* prevalence. Possible explanations for the remarked association between the frequency of these hybrids and *S. mansoni* prevalence include increased susceptibility of humans to livestock-infective schistosomes following *S. mansoni* infection or *S. mansoni* and *S. haematobium* mixed infections; host water contact behaviour and immunology; compatibility of hybrids with the locally predominant snail species; more intensive livestock rearing around the shores of Lac de Guiers (where most hybrids have been found); and ongoing selection of *S. bovis* introgressed genes due to their possible adaptive benefits (66).

Table 1.1. Hybrids between species of the *Schistosoma haematobium* clade recently reported across sub-Saharan Africa

Reported <i>S. haematobium</i> clade interspecific hybrid combination ^a	Host infected by the schistosome hybrid	Type of sample evaluated for molecular evidence	Country	Reference ^b
<i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. haematobium</i>	Human	Miracidia	Benin	(49)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Rodent	Miracidia, plus snail infection	Benin	(67)
<i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. haematobium</i>	Ruminant (Cattle)	Miracidia, plus snail infection	Benin	(49)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i> ; and <i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. haematobium</i>	Human	Miracidia	Cameroon	(68)
<i>S. guineensis</i> x <i>S. haematobium</i> ; and <i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Human/snail	Sequencing of F1 male worms (field samples used in rodent laboratory infection)	Cameroon	(56)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Human	Miracidia	Côte d'Ivoire	(69)

<i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. haematobium</i>	Snail	Cercariae	Côte d'Ivoire	(70)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. mattheei</i> ; and <i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Human	Atypical eggs	Malawi	(71)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Human	Atypical eggs from travellers	Mali	(72)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Human/snail	Sequencing of F1 male worms (field samples used in rodent laboratory infection)	Mali	(56)
<i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. curassoni</i> ; and <i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. curassoni</i>	Human	Miracidia	Niger	(48)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i> ; and <i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. curassoni</i>	Snail	Cercariae	Niger	(73)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Human	Miracidia	Nigeria	(74)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Human/snail	Sequencing of F1 male worms (field samples used in rodent laboratory infection)	Nigeria	(56)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Human	Miracidia	Senegal	(66)
<i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. haematobium</i>	Human	Miracidia	Senegal	(18)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Snail	Cercariae	Senegal	(18)
<i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i>	Rodent	Female worm	Senegal	(75)
<i>S. bovis</i> x <i>S. curassoni</i>	Ruminant (Cattle, sheep, goat)	Miracidia	Senegal	(18)
<i>S. mattheei</i> x <i>S. haematobium</i>	Human	Sera from travellers (acute cases), followed by sequencing	South Africa	(76)

^a Hybrid combination as reported in reference.

^b Reported since Leger and Webster (40).

Interestingly, since 2013, a hybrid *S. haematobium* x *S. bovis* isolate likely originating from West Africa, seems to have adapted successfully to the local snail and human population in Corsica, France (77). This hybrid strain has caused several outbreaks of human schistosomiasis in Corsica without an apparent need for animal reservoirs (77, 78). Overwintering of the Corsica hybrid schistosome strain within the local snail host has been recently demonstrated, providing a potential explanation of local persistence in this newly established focus (79). Previous single-species infection studies in baboons produced *S. mattheei* eggs but no *S. bovis* eggs (80) nor *S. curassoni* eggs (81), suggesting the latter two livestock-specific schistosomes may require heterospecific mixing to produce viable offspring in humans (48). However, recent evidence of 'pure' *S. bovis* viable human infection in Nigeria (74) has proven that this species can in fact develop fully as a single species in people. Furthermore, contrary to prevailing thought on the epidemiology of hybridizations between livestock- and human-associated *S. haematobium* clade schistosomes, recent studies carried out in West Africa have demonstrated that human infection by *S. bovis* hybrids is common (Table 1.1).

Genome-wide restriction site associated DNA sequencing (RADseq) has shown an increased fitness and viability (so-called hybrid vigour) of *S. haematobium* clade hybrids which may, at least partially explain the change in endemic landscape over a period of 25 years from predominantly intestinal (caused by *S. guineensis*) to urogenital human cases in sympatric regions of Central Africa (56). Furthermore, recent genomic studies have found *S. haematobium* clade hybridizations to be both ancient (82) and ongoing (83). Both hybrid vigour and the rise in inter-specific schistosome encounters facilitated by the increased movement of people and animals, will likely increase the frequency of hybridizations as interventions are intensified to meet elimination goals (58).

1.2.3. Importance of a One Health approach

Several schistosome species are currently widely recognised as zoonotic, particularly livestock-infective species of the *S. japonicum* clade in Asia. In Africa, intestinal livestock-infective species of the *S. haematobium* clade (i.e., *S. bovis*, *S. curassoni* and *S. mattheei*, see (84) for an up-to-date summary of their geographic range) which tend to hybridize with urogenital *S. haematobium* can also be classified as zoonotic, though the significance of domestic ruminants as reservoirs for human transmission is yet to be clarified (65, 85). Land use change, climate change, expanding trade, migration and mobility will likely increase parasite hybridization as well as zoonotic spillover (83). The introduction of schistosomes into new habitats can be mediated by the livestock trade (e.g., the recent discovery of *S. bovis* in Zanzibar (86)), economic migration and displacement and indeed tourism (e.g., in 2017 a cluster of acute cases was reported in Belgian travellers returning from South Africa and associated with *S. mattheei* and *S. haematobium* hybridization (76)). The increased migration of animals and/or humans in conjunction with man-made ecological change (e.g., dam construction, irrigation systems, agriculture and deforestation), will continue altering schistosomes' geographic range, further complicating control efforts (4).

In China, where sustained control efforts (including livestock interventions) have successfully eliminated *S. japonicum* from many endemic foci, the risk of resurgence from both domestic and wildlife animals remains an ongoing challenge (e.g., in 2014, the infection prevalence documented in rodents, goats and dogs was above 9% in Hunan province (87). Elsewhere, the finding in 2019 of a green monkey in St. Kitts infected with *S. mansoni*—where schistosomiasis was thought to have been eliminated in the 1970s—raises several questions including reintroduction of the parasite to the island, or the existence of a sylvatic cycle maintained by non-human primates (44).

The role of wild rodents as reservoirs of zoonotic schistosomes is being progressively uncovered, with rodents found to be infected with *S. mansoni* in the Caribbean (45, 88), Brazil (89) and Africa (75, 90, 91). Moreover, in Africa, where the majority of intestinal (caused by *S. mansoni*) and urogenital (caused by *S. haematobium*) human schistosomiasis cases occur, wild rodents have been confirmed to be naturally infected with *S. bovis* and *S. haematobium* clade hybrids (67, 75). Importantly, infected livestock are also relevant sources of zoonotic spillover, particularly, cattle infected with *S. bovis* (18, 19).

At least 12 million people have been estimated to live at risk of zoonotic schistosomiasis in Asia (i.e., at risk of infection with *Schistosoma japonicum* or *Schistosoma mekongi* in the WHO's Western Pacific Region and Indonesia) (92). Such estimates are yet to be produced for Africa. Resolving the nature of multi-host transmission at a local level remains challenging (93), though recent modelling work (17, 19, 58) highlights the emerging risk of zoonotic hybrids and other zoonotic schistosomes in Africa (85) and questions whether the traditional top-down, human-centric approach to control and elimination is suitable (94). Increased understanding of the population structure of schistosomes and their response to selective pressures induced by MDA requires interdisciplinary work, including a combination of molecular, epidemiological and modelling analyses (95). Given the noteworthy high prevalence of *S. bovis* genes in parasites recently recovered from Nigerian children (estimated 89% prevalence of *S. bovis* x *S. haematobium* hybrids based on *cox1* profiling) (74), there is a prescient need to more completely understand the population structure and transmission dynamics of schistosomes infecting African livestock (96) and their spatiotemporal distribution, particularly where zoonotic hybrid prevalence is highest (66). Similarly, the role of rodents, non-human primates, and other relevant animal species warrants further research.

Improved understanding of the eco-epidemiology of schistosomiasis at the human-animal interface and the economic and sociological factors affecting the feasibility and effectiveness of control interventions, have been recently proposed as policy pillars for the sustainable elimination of zoonotic schistosomiasis (92). Zoonotic *S. japonicum* clade and *S. haematobium* clade schistosomes, as well as species that cause animal schistosomiasis, ought to be considered when setting animal health and veterinary public health goals to accompany existing public health elimination goals (5). Furthermore, the genital pathology of other *S. haematobium* clade species besides *S. haematobium* in urogenital schistosomiasis cases in women and men must be elucidated, including the risk of genital forms of disease from zoonotic hybrids.

1.2.4. Targeting livestock schistosomiasis in sub-Saharan Africa

Interventions to tackle the emerging risk of zoonotic hybrids in Africa include preventing susceptible livestock from coming into contact with contaminated water bodies (e.g., by providing drinking water in troughs, contamination of communal water with livestock faeces could be minimised (97)), treatment of infected livestock and limiting interaction with wildlife (85). Other proposed interventions such as replacement of livestock with non-susceptible species or machinery (e.g., for agricultural management of wetlands) (85) might be arguable, given schistosomes tendency for host-switching and range of potential animal reservoirs—in the case of *S. japonicum*, buffaloes, cattle, and horses are considered main reservoirs in parts of Indonesia (98), whereas, transmission between dogs and humans and between rodents and humans has been reported respectively, in areas of the Philippines (99) and China (100).

A key unresolved question for the establishment of a comprehensive One Health strategy is whether extending praziquantel treatment to relevant animal reservoirs in SSA would be epidemiologically and economically beneficial (35). For example, in 2022, a study assessing the financial impact of livestock schistosomiasis on subsistence farmers of northern Senegal indicated that the impact of withholding interventions substantially surpassed the cost of testing and treatment (101). Such findings indicate that there is a significant economic burden placed on traditional farmers by this disease, and thus favour, from an economic standpoint, the extension of praziquantel treatment to livestock in SSA.

Interestingly, the use (and misuse) of praziquantel for livestock schistosomiasis is thought to be already widespread in parts of SSA (35, 101), often employing subtherapeutic doses, inappropriate products instead of suitable veterinary formulations, and incomplete treatment regimens (i.e., misuse). Thus, anecdotally, there exists demand for animal disease control and consequently the need for a structured approach to livestock schistosomiasis control (102). Initial exploration of a herd-level test-and-treat (TnT) approach for cattle using a mathematical transmission model suggests that up to 75% of bovine case-years in highly endemic settings and up to 85% of bovine case-years in lower transmission contexts could be averted (102). The potential impact of TnT interventions could thus be substantial. There remain several outstanding challenges before TnT interventions could be implemented, including the availability of sensitive and specific point-of-care diagnostics (5, 65) (see (103) for a systematic review and meta-analysis of diagnostics for non-human schistosomiasis) and suitable veterinary formulations (102). Moreover, a TnT approach can only partially mitigate the risk of promoting drug resistance, an ominous spectre given the exclusive reliance on praziquantel for the treatment of human and animal schistosomiasis (Table 1.2). Notwithstanding, the clear contribution of cattle to spillover infections in humans and subsequent enhanced risks of hybridization, in addition to the operational feasibility of such an intervention in livestock (compared to wild animals), plus the economic benefits for impoverished communities, justify development of a comprehensive control strategy focused on domestic ruminants (102).

Table 1.2. Concepts and considerations on mitigating the risk of emerging resistance to praziquantel

Anthelmintic resistance	Anthelmintic resistance is a heritable change that allows for the survival of parasites when exposed to previously efficacious doses of chemotherapy (104). Emergence of resistance occurs as the selective advantage of drug resistant strains progressively surpasses that of the wild type and is established if the resistant phenotype remains able to be transmitted between hosts (104). Over reliance on a single anthelmintic drug (praziquantel) and current lack of pharmaceutical alternatives for the treatment of schistosomiasis (105) increases the vulnerability of control and elimination programmes to emerging resistance. There remains no conclusive evidence for the emergence of praziquantel resistance in natural schistosome populations, although instances of reduced efficacy (e.g., for <i>S. mansoni</i> human infection in Uganda (106), and unsatisfactory clinical improvement (e.g., for <i>S. haematobium</i> clade human infection caused by interspecific hybrids in Senegal (107)) have been reported.
Veterinary use of anthelmintics	The use of anthelmintics in the veterinary field is thought to increase the risk of emerging drug resistance (35), due in part to the unstructured way in which drugs are administered in some settings. A structured test-and-treat approach (102) has potential to partly counteract such risks, although the risk of emerging resistance can never be completely avoided (104). Notwithstanding, even after decades of extensive praziquantel use in livestock in China, no evidence of drug resistance under field conditions has been reported to date (104).
Evolutionary pressure of interventions and presence of zoonotic hybrids	A bidirectional effect between the evolutionary pressure of control interventions and the presence of zoonotic hybrids is probable (58), with potential impacts including reduced praziquantel efficacy and changing morbidity profiles (58), as recently reported in people infected with <i>S. haematobium</i> x <i>S. bovis</i> hybrids in Senegal (107), in addition to a potentially heightened role of animals in transmission as prevalence in humans decreases (17, 58).
Laboratory schistosomes response to selective pressures	Laboratory studies (see (104)) have produced changes in schistosome fecundity, virulence, drug susceptibility, infectivity, and population genetics (108-115) within a few generations and using a range of selective pressures. How such experimental laboratory studies translate to natural populations remains unclear.
<i>Refugia</i> of drug susceptible genes	Untreated zoonotic reservoirs may act as <i>refugia</i> —a pool of drug susceptible genes which can dilute resistant genes—which slow the

	<p>emergence of drug resistance (34, 35). <i>Refugia</i> arise within untreated individuals in the at-risk populations and other animal species relevant to the parasite's life cycle, and perhaps even immature schistosomes which are not susceptible to praziquantel (104). The size and relevance of <i>refugia</i> will vary depending on the transmission dynamics of the schistosome species. For example, since <i>S. japonicum</i> has several vertebrate hosts that can act as <i>refugia</i>, it is proposed that there exists a low likelihood of emerging resistance (104).</p>
Emerging drug resistance	<p>Mass drug administration can exert a sufficiently strong population level selective pressure for the evolution of resistant strains (104), with repeated chemotherapy predicted to exert selective pressures which favour parasite resistance alleles (116). The emergence of resistance, especially when it is a recessive trait, tends to follow a sigmoid-type temporal dynamic and therefore is often identified only during or after the exponential-type growth phase that follows an initial slow rise (104). This underlines the importance of early detection to give time for mitigating interventions to be implemented. Relaxation of constraining density-dependent processes (e.g., on parasite fecundity) after chemotherapy can enhance the spread of drug resistance, depending on the particular density-dependent process at play (116).</p>

The efficacy of praziquantel against livestock schistosomiasis—cattle and small ruminants (sheep and goats)—is a long-standing pending research need which must be answered if a One Health treatment approach is to be safely implemented, with additional knowledge gaps including ruminant species-specific praziquantel pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics, drug bioavailability and ideal administration route. Commercial veterinary formulations for the treatment of livestock schistosomiasis with praziquantel are not currently widely available in SSA (35). Hence, enhanced and alternative supply lines of praziquantel for veterinary usage will also require development to meet the increased demand.

Current estimates of the prevalence and geographic extent of livestock schistosomiasis are incomplete (18) and require a comprehensive epidemiological mapping approach to redress (35). Crucial information at a local level on domestic ruminants' exposure to contaminated water sources will further prospects for the design and implementation of strategies that complement treatment by mitigating re-infection. Continuous surveillance and monitoring to detect early signs of emerging resistance in both humans and animals is also paramount to safeguard praziquantel. Such activities would include monitoring prevalence, clinical outcomes and drug efficacy (e.g., egg reduction rates), assessment of temporospatial genetic diversity, population structure and gene flow, and measurement of allele frequency changes mediated by treatment (104) (Table 1.2).

Currently, there are no commercially available schistosomiasis vaccines for either humans or animals (27, 85), although is an active area of research and development (for recent reviews see (117) and (118)) which could potentially radically shift approaches towards control and elimination (119). The development of anti-schistosome animal vaccines began in the 1970s with *S. mattheei* irradiated larvae found to be as immunogenic in sheep as natural challenge (120), and with *S. bovis* irradiated larvae found to be protective against natural challenge in cattle (higher growth rate, reduced worm burden and reduced egg output in vaccinated animals compared to controls) (118, 121). These initial attempts were followed in the 1980s by a cryopreserved radiation-attenuated schistosomula vaccine against *S. bovis* in sheep (122) as well as irradiated *S. japonicum* vaccines in mice, pigs, sheep, cattle and buffaloes of China (123, 124). More recent efforts have focused on the use of recombinant DNA vaccine technology for livestock (mostly testing three antigens: glutathione S-transferases, paramyosin and triose-phosphate isomerase) given its antibody and cellular immunity inducing properties, its cost and logistical advantages of field deployment without relying on a cold-chain (118). Despite the encouraging results of early live-attenuated *S. bovis* and *S. mattheei* livestock vaccine candidates, the lack of recently published studies (118) highlights a delay in progress and an unmet One Health research need.

1.2.5. One Health, environmental management and WASH

Implementation of water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) measures (i.e., safe water supply, personal cleanliness and handwashing, access to facilities and services for the safe disposal of urine and faeces (7)), snail control and environmental management interventions, can reduce schistosome transmission and benefit the health of people, animals, and ecosystems. However, the success of differing interventions will vary according to the local context. For instance, while chemical snail control with niclosamide molluscicide formulations resulted in a substantial reduction of snail populations in China, its use in Laos did not have a significant impact (27). Moreover, molluscicide environmental contamination might preclude its use in other countries and hence more sustainable alternatives like environmental modification (e.g., concreting canals and/or vegetation removal in the snail habitat, land use change to avoid flood irrigation) and/or biological control (e.g., introduction of snail predators) could be explored in these contexts. In fact, the elimination of *S. japonicum* in Japan pre-dated praziquantel and relied on snail population reduction through environmental modification associated with rapid economic development, in combination with health education and animal reservoir control (27).

Key hygiene and sanitation deficiencies within Africa persist, including lack of sewage infrastructure (affecting two thirds of the continent's population) and no access to clean water (endured by almost half of the population in Africa) (85). Robust long-term measures to tackle such challenges would greatly enhance the prospects of widespread and sustained elimination of schistosomiasis and other water-borne diseases. While a One Health approach has a role to play in improving this situation, it will ultimately require continued economic development, political commitment, and stability. It remains to be seen whether elimination of schistosomiasis can be achieved without such wholesale progress.

1.3. Conclusion

The importance of One Health to the control and elimination of NTDs has gained increased recognition through its integration into the WHO 2030 NTD Roadmap (5) and companion documents (4, 6, 7). The evolutionary history of schistosomes as multi-host parasites which continue to readily hybridize and adapt exemplifies the particular importance of One Health to the effectiveness and success of interventions targeting elimination. One Health approaches—which encompass the treatment and/or vaccination of livestock, environmental management, and snail control—will be integral to reducing the risk of zoonotic spillover and mitigating the risk of resurgence in human populations and improving the economic prospects and livelihoods of communities that depend on healthy livestock. Many challenges remain to the sustainable implementation of such approaches, but this should not detract from the importance of embracing One Health to combat schistosomiasis and other NTDs.

CHAPTER 2

Simulated effect of a test-and-treat strategy in bovine schistosomiasis within the Senegal River Basin

2.1. Summary

Schistosomiasis, a neglected tropical disease (NTD), is a widespread chronic helminthiasis reported in 78 countries, predominantly those within sub-Saharan Africa, as well as Latin America, Asia, and most recently, even Europe. Species of the causative blood fluke infect not only humans but also animals, and hybrids between those previously assumed to be human-specific with animal schistosomes are being increasingly reported, particularly within the *Haematobium* group. Existing control programs across Africa focus on humans and rely heavily on mass drug administration of praziquantel, the sole drug available against schistosomiasis. Praziquantel is safe and highly efficacious but could become ineffective if resistance emerges. In order to reach the revised World Health Organization (WHO) goal of elimination of schistosomiasis as a public health problem (EPHP), and interruption of transmission within selected regions by 2030, new consideration of whether to also treat livestock with praziquantel has been raised. However, whilst there are no dedicated control programmes targeting animals outside of Asia, there are emerging reports of the use and misuse of praziquantel in livestock across Africa. Therefore, to both effectively treat livestock in Africa and to help mitigate against the potential evolution of praziquantel resistance, structured control strategies are required. Here, by means of a transmission modelling approach, the potential effectiveness of a theoretical test-and-treat (TnT) strategy to control bovine schistosomiasis which uses a currently available point-of-care diagnostic test (developed for human use) to detect circulating cathodic antigen (POC-CCA), is evaluated. This chapter shows that implementing TnT from 2022 to 2030 could be highly effective in suppressing infection, and in lower prevalence settings, could even aid in reaching nominal 'elimination' targets. The importance of enhancing the specificity of POC-CCA for use in livestock to avoid unnecessary treatments is highlighted, and the outstanding challenges associated with implementing TnT as part of a holistic One Health approach to tackling human and animal schistosomiasis are discussed.

2.2. Introduction

A substantial proportion of the world's disease burden is caused by infectious agents that lead to high mortality, morbidity, and reduced productivity among many millions of people and their animals. Schistosomiasis is a major freshwater-snail-borne neglected tropical disease (NTD) caused by blood flukes of the genus *Schistosoma*. This parasitic disease remains a public health problem in the majority of 78 tropical and subtropical countries, infecting >240 million people (125-127), 90% living in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (9, 126).

Global efforts to control human schistosomiasis rely predominantly on mass drug administration (MDA), whereby populations of mainly school-aged children are mass treated with the donated anti-helminthic, praziquantel (PZQ). Praziquantel is safe, highly efficacious, and can be administered easily. Consequently, MDA programmes have had, in general, major impacts on reducing infection prevalence and intensity and subsequent morbidity (126-130). The success of such activities has led to a revision of the World Health Organization goals for 'elimination as a public health problem' (<1% heavy intensity infections) in all affected countries, together with interruption of transmission within selected regions, by 2030 (5). The potential role of schistosomiasis in animals does, however, raise significant challenges for achieving these goals, and stresses the critical need for a One Health approach globally.

Currently, only the Asian schistosome species *S. japonicum* and *S. mekongi* are widely acknowledged as zoonotic (40). Domestic animals, notably bovines, have been suggested as responsible for up to 97% of disease transmission in Marshland regions of China (17). Consequently, China in particular has performed integrated mass PZQ treatment of both humans and bovines, as well as improvements to water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH), replacement of bovines with tractors, and has attempted to develop a bovine vaccine. These sustained efforts have yielded great progress: from being a country with the highest schistosomiasis burden in the 1950s, the overall prevalence of schistosomiasis japonica in China is now <1% in humans and livestock populations, and the majority of endemic provinces have reached the criteria of transmission control (22, 131).

In contrast, the role of animal schistosomiasis in SSA, in terms of either zoonotic risk or economic impact has, until very recently, been largely ignored, and there are no formal anti-schistosome control nor donation programmes involving animals. Livestock schistosomiasis infections due to *S. bovis*, *S. curassoni* and/or *S. mattheei* in cattle, sheep and goats are, however, prevalent in SSA (23, 40). Furthermore, while *S. haematobium*, the causative agent of human urogenital schistosomiasis, was originally believed to be an exclusively human-specific parasite, an ever-growing number of molecular studies of parasites isolated from African children and adults have identified viable hybrids between human *S. haematobium* with livestock *S. bovis*, *S. curassoni* or *S. mattheei* (18, 40, 49, 53, 71). Moreover, cases of hybridized livestock *S. bovis* with *S. curassoni* viably infecting children in West Africa have also been identified (48). Furthermore, hybridized *S. haematobium* with *S. bovis* infections are now also established within Corsica, Europe (77).

These findings demonstrate that there is an important zoonotic component of schistosomiasis transmission in SSA, and one which has been predicted to be of increasing importance as elimination programmes targeting humans intensify (19). Furthermore, in addition to the zoonotic importance of livestock schistosomiasis and its implications for reaching the WHO elimination goals, there are highly important, if also often overlooked, animal welfare, productivity, and socioeconomic impacts, which further jeopardize livelihoods, food security and nutrition amongst neglected communities (35, 101). Schistosome infection in cattle, though often classed as sub-clinical, has been associated with diarrhoea, anaemia, weight loss, growth retardation, susceptibility to infection, and/or intestinal and

hepatic lesions (23, 132, 133). Similar, or often more severe, morbidity (and mortality), combined with reduced productivity profiles have also recently been reported in infected sheep and goats (35, 101). Indeed, the financial impact projected over one year of no livestock schistosomiasis interventions was recently calculated to be substantial, where its costs surpassed those of testing and treating suspected cases in Northern Senegal (101).

The importance of veterinary public health interventions in achieving the WHO elimination 2030 targets has now been acknowledged in both the newly launched WHO NTD Roadmap 2021-2030 (5) and Schistosomiasis Guideline for control and elimination of human schistosomiasis (6). Amongst challenges identified to reach this goal are gaps in the scientific understanding of zoonotic transmission and implementation of effective interventions to address zoonotic reservoirs, as well as critical actions regarding diagnostics development including standardized point-of-care (POC) tests (5). However, it is unlikely that an equivalent MDA strategy as used in humans would be deemed acceptable for livestock because of the risk of promoting the emergence of PZQ resistance. This is critical, given there is now resistance to all known veterinary anthelmintics globally (134), and any exacerbation of the risk of emerging resistance is particularly pertinent for schistosomiasis as PZQ is the only efficacious drug for both humans and livestock.

However recent work indicates already widespread use and misuse of PZQ in livestock—including, but not exclusive to, PZQ tablets donated free via the WHO MDA programmes for school-aged children—being frequently purchased (on the market) for supply to infected livestock, with little knowledge of application or dosage requirements (35). Indeed, more than a third of respondents in a recent survey within Senegal stated that they had given anti-schistosomiasis treatment to their livestock within the preceding four years (101). These new insights highlight a previously unforeseen need and demand to treat both livestock, as well as human, schistosomiasis, within parts of SSA. There is clearly therefore a critical need to now develop a structured approach for the treatment of livestock schistosomiasis in SSA.

A test-and-treat (TnT, and/or the related *T3: Test, Treat, Track*) design for controlling livestock schistosomiasis would anchor the key recent WHO policy recommendations on diagnostic testing, treatment and surveillance in general (5, 6). Such a strategy would enable local veterinarians, veterinary technicians and/or local village chiefs within endemic countries to easily and inexpensively assess whether a herd is infected with schistosomiasis and only then distribute appropriately dosed PZQ. Such a policy could minimise the costs and suffering to the livestock and their owners, and at the same time mitigate the risk of promoting the emergence of PZQ resistance.

With the aim of assessing the potential impact of TnT, this chapter presents a theoretical TnT intervention targeting bovine schistosomiasis running from 2022 through 2030, which was evaluated using a mathematical transmission model. The model was parameterised with recent epidemiological data on the prevalence of bovine schistosomiasis collected in farming locations of Northern Senegal.

Model findings are discussed in terms of their theoretical and applied implications for integrated One Health schistosomiasis disease control and elimination policy and practice.

2.3. Materials and Methods

2.3.1. Ethical statement

Ethical approval for the fieldwork was provided by: (i) Imperial College (London, UK) application 03.36; (ii) the CRERB at the Royal Veterinary College (London, UK) application URN20151327; and (iii) the Comité National d’Ethique pour la Recherche en Santé (Dakar, Senegal) application SEN15/68. Written informed consent was obtained from all livestock owners. Livestock owners were offered standard anthelmintics for infected animals.

2.3.2. Parasitological data

Prevalence estimates presented here focus on data from cattle (live *Bos taurus*, *Bos indicus* and cross breeds) coprological surveys conducted in 2017 in a Senegal River Basin area of northern Senegal, West Africa, as part of the Zoonoses and Emerging Livestock Systems (ZELS) programme (18, 19). In this human schistosomiasis endemic area, Richard Toll and Lac de Guiers, henceforth referred to as RT, schistosome transmission is perennial due to the year-round persistence of freshwater habitats for competent snail vectors (i.e., Senegal River and the Lac de Guiers lake) (18).

Faecal samples from 200 sympatric bovines in eight RT site locations (Djidière; Mbane; Medina Cheikhou; Ndombo; Sanente; Temeye; Thiago and Yetti Yone) were collected following randomised protocols and processed using two schistosomiasis tests: Kato-Katz (KK) for presence of *Schistosoma* spp. eggs (examination of two slides per sample), and an adapted Miracidial Hatching Technique (MHT) to determine egg viability (and also used as an alternative diagnostic for the presence of eggs). Protocols for both techniques are described elsewhere (18).

Prevalence estimates derived from the results of both coprological exams informed the prevalence range explored in the modelled TnT strategy (Figure 2.1) using an imperfect POC diagnostic measuring urine levels of the adult worm gut-associated circulating cathodic antigen (CCA), hereby referred to as POC-CCA (135). This POC diagnostic is ordinarily employed for *S. mansoni* human-endemicity mapping given its superior sensitivity in comparison to the reference standard KK (12). Published preliminary sensitivity and specificity estimates of POC-CCA (136) calculated using Bayesian latent class approaches based on bovine urine samples collected during the ZELS programme—where the overwhelming majority of infected cattle shed *S. bovis* (18)—were used for modelling TnT.

Simulated Test-and-Treat strategy in an infected herd of cattle

Figure 2.1. Schematic of the proposed Test-and-Treat (TnT) strategy simulated in the herd-level transmission model. Created with BioRender.com.

2.3.3. Prevalence estimation

The KK and MHT data were modelled as two independent Bernoulli distributed variables conditional on the location-specific prevalence, π_i , and the sensitivity, se , and specificity, sp , of the respective diagnostics. Therefore, the probability that an individual tests positive for each diagnostic is

$$P(+) = se \times \pi_i + (1 - sp)(1 - \pi_i) \quad (1)$$

The sensitivity of each test was assigned an informative beta prior parameterized using published performance values ((18) test sensitivities estimated with abattoir positives as pseudo-gold standard) such that the median and central 95% percentile was 0.31 (0.16 – 0.49) for KK and 0.79 (0.60- 0.91) for MHT. The specificity of both tests was assumed to be 1 (i.e., 100%) given that both tests rely on the microscopic visualisation of identifiable eggs. The prevalence in each location was estimated using a Bayesian Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approach using the JAGS program version 4.3.0 called with the *rjags* package version 4-12 (137) for R version 4.0.2 (138).

2.3.4. Transmission model

A simple deterministic mathematical transmission model based on models published by Anderson and May (139, 140) was used, in order to track the mean number of schistosomes per host (worm burden), $W(t)$, during the TnT intervention. The Anderson and May framework was simplified by collapsing the parasite life stages which are key for transmission (i.e., miracidia and cercaria) into components of the basic reproduction number (R_0), and excluding explicit states of snail infection (i.e., uninfected, latent and shedding snails). The transmission model was thereby defined by a single ordinary differential equation,

$$\frac{dW(t)}{dt} = \frac{R_0(\mu_0 + \mu_1)\mu_2 W(t)\Phi(W(t), k)}{R_{H \rightarrow S}(\mu_0 + \mu_1)(N_1/N_2)W(t)\Phi(W(t), k) + \mu_2} - (\mu_0 + \mu_1)W(t) \quad (2)$$

where μ_0 and μ_1 denote the cattle and schistosome mortality rates respectively and the environmental and intermediate host stages of the schistosome lifecycle are compressed into $R_0 = R_{H \rightarrow S}R_{S \rightarrow H}$. The component $R_{H \rightarrow S}$ captures transmission from the definitive host to snails via miracidia, and $R_{S \rightarrow H}$ transmission from snails to the definitive host via cercaria. The snail mortality rate is denoted μ_2 and N_1/N_2 is the definitive (cattle) to intermediate (snail) host population size. The finite nature of the snail population size provides a natural negative density dependence to constrain the size of the parasite population and the mating probability, $\Phi(W(t), k(t))$ (139) is a positive density-dependent process that ensures the existence of a transmission breakpoint (141). $k(t)$ is the dynamic overdispersion parameter of the negative binomial distribution, which is assumed to capture adequately the distribution of schistosomes among hosts. The time dependency of $k(t)$ results from the changing overdispersion following initiation of treatment (142),

$$k(t) = \begin{cases} k_0, & t < t_T \\ \frac{k_0 W(t)}{(1 + k_0)W_0 - k_0 W(t)} = k_{post}, & t = t_T \\ \frac{W(t)^2(W_0 - W_1)^2}{(W_0^2/k_0)(W(t) - W_1)^2 + (W_1^2/k_1)(W(t) - W_0)^2}, & t > t_T \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where k_0 is the pre-intervention overdispersion equilibrium and W_0 is the pre-intervention endemic mean worm burden, while k_1 and W_1 are respectively the overdispersion and mean worm burden parameters immediately after treatment. t_T denotes a treatment time. The prevalence of infection, $\pi(t)$, is derived from the negative binomial distribution of worms among hosts

$$\pi(t) = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{W(t)}{k(t)}\right)^{-k(t)} \quad (4)$$

2.3.5. Baseline conditions, parametric uncertainty, and interventions

The model was run to endemic equilibrium using 100,000 parameter sets drawn from a Latin hypercube, sampling R_0 , $R_{H \rightarrow S}$, N_1/N_2 and k_0 from uniform prior distributions (Table 2.1). Then, 250 parameter sets were randomly selected within $\pm 1\%$ of 5% increments at baseline prevalence from 40% to 95%. These parameter sets were used to model the impact of the TnT intervention strategy (see Figure 2.1) using PZQ, starting in 2022 and continuing annually with the last TnT round implemented in 2030. At each TnT round, the probability of the single herd receiving treatment was given by the probability of at least one positive POC-CCA test result, $P(+)$, from n sampled animals in the single herd

$$P(+) = 1 - \left(1 - se_{POC} \times \pi(t) - (1 - sp_{POC}) \times (1 - \pi(t))\right)^n \quad (5)$$

where se_{POC} and sp_{POC} denote the sensitivity and specificity of the POC-CCA respectively. A parallel testing regimen was assumed whereby n animals were tested simultaneously and if at least one test was positive, treatment for the single herd was triggered. Combining $P(+)$ with the efficacy of PZQ, ε , thus the (average) effect of treatment at each TnT round was modelled as

$$W(t + dt) = W(t) - W(t)P(+) \varepsilon \quad t = t_T \quad (6)$$

Because of the lack of a standardised praziquantel efficacy estimate for livestock schistosomiasis, a human schistosomiasis estimate for a closely related species was used instead (Table 2.1). Notably, evidence of density-dependent fecundity in the latter species has linked inferred numbers of female worms to egg counts in a non-proportional manner (143).

Table 2.1. Fixed and varied parameters used within the herd-level transmission model.

Parameter	Definition	Value	Reference
<i>Fixed parameters</i>			
μ_0	Mortality rate of definitive host (1/average life expectancy in years)	1/5	Mean age estimate of ZELS study bovines ~ 5 years (See Appendix D1 and D2)
μ_1	Mortality rate of adult schistosomes within definitive host (1/average life expectancy years)	1/5	(140)
μ_2	Mortality rate of intermediate snail (1/average life expectancy in years)	1/0.5	(140)
se_{POC}	POC-CCA diagnostic sensitivity	0.62	(136)
sp_{POC}	POC-CCA diagnostic specificity	0.70	(136)
ε	Efficacy of praziquantel against human schistosomes	0.9	(144) Efficacy against <i>S. haematobium</i> derived from egg reduction rate
<i>Varied parameters</i>			
R_0	Schistosome basic reproductive number	1.5 – 3	This work
$R_{H \rightarrow S}$	Component of R_0 describing transmission from definitive (cattle) host to intermediate (snail) host	1 – 100	This work
N_1/N_2	Definitive (cattle) to intermediate (snail) host population size	0.01 – 0.5	This work
k_0	Overdispersion of schistosomes among definitive (cattle) hosts at (pre-intervention) baseline	0.2 – 1	This work
n	Number of cattle tested by POC-CCA per test-and-treat round	1, 2 or 4	This work

2.3.6. Test-and-treat effectiveness indicators

The effectiveness of the TnT intervention was evaluated by two metrics. For first metric, case-years averted to the end of 2030 were calculated as a percentage of the baseline prevalence in 2022 (before the first round of TnT),

$$\text{Percent case-years averted} = \frac{1}{9 \times \pi(2022)} \int_{t=2022}^{t=2030} (\pi(2022) - \pi(t)) dt \quad (7)$$

For the second metric, the percentage of simulations within each prevalence category that were nominally defined as having reached elimination, here defined as having a prevalence of less than 1% at the end of 2030, were calculated. Notably, this is different from the WHO elimination as a public health problem threshold of 1% *heavy* infections which could not be applied readily to livestock because of the difficulty in quantifying infection intensity.

2.3.7. Diagnostic performance dynamics

In addition to calculating the probability that least one POC-CCA would return a positive result (and thus trigger treatment with PZQ, Equation 5), the positive predictive value (PPV, assuming a parallel testing strategy) was calculated as an indicator of the performance of TnT in being able to detect correctly infected animals during the intervention,

$$\text{Positive predictive value} = \frac{(1 - (1 - se_{POC})^n)\pi(t)}{(1 - (1 - se_{POC})^n)\pi(t) + (1 - sp_{POC}^n)(1 - \pi(t))} \quad (8)$$

2.4. Results

2.4.1. Prevalence of bovine schistosomiasis

The observed prevalence (by either KK or MHT) and the estimated 'true' prevalence of *Schistosoma* spp. infection among cattle in the eight sampled locations in RT are shown in Table 2.2 and Figure 2.2. The high sensitivity of MHT compared to KK (~79% vs. ~31%) ensures greater concordance between the 'true' prevalence and that observed by MHT compared to KK (Figure 2.2). Bayesian posterior 'true' prevalence estimates ranged from 43% (95% credible interval, CrI: 13%, 82%) to 95% (95% CrI: 85%, 100%), with six of the eight locations having a 'true' prevalence greater than 50%. These estimates informed the prevalence range (40% to 95%) considered in the modelling of TnT.

Figure 2.2. Observed vs true prevalence of bovine schistosomiasis by diagnostic. Posterior mean ‘true’ prevalence (points) and 95% credible intervals (vertical lines) versus observed prevalence by (a) Kato-Katz (KK) and (b) Miracidial Hatching Technique (MHT), in eight locations in Richard Toll, Senegal sampled in 2017. The dotted line of $y = x$ is a guide to assess visually the degree of concordance between the observed and true prevalence by each diagnostic.

Table 2.2. Estimates of ‘observed’ and ‘true’ prevalence of bovine schistosomiasis in eight locations in Richard Toll, Senegal sampled in 2017.

Location	N_{KK}^a	Observed prevalence by KK	N_{MHT}^b	Observed prevalence by MHT	Mean posterior ‘true’ prevalence (95% CrI ^c)
Djidièry	35	66%	20	85%	95% (85% – 100%)
Mbane	11	36%	7	100%	90% (64% – 100%)
Medina Cheikhou	25	68%	22	82%	93% (80% – 100%)
Ndombo	11	27%	6	50%	60% (29% – 92%)
Sanente	12	0%	5	60%	43% (13% – 82%)
Temeye	6	0%	3	67%	50% (13% – 91%)
Thiago	29	14%	12	67%	60% (35% – 84%)
Yetti Yone	71	15%	30	97%	89% (70% – 100%)

^a Number of cattle sampled by Kato-Katz (KK); ^b number of cattle sampled by miracidial hatching technique (MHT); ^c Credible interval.

2.4.2. Infection dynamics

The modelled prevalence dynamics during a TnT intervention between 2022 and 2030 using either $n = 1$, $n = 2$ or $n = 4$ POC-CCA tests per herd are illustrated in Figure 2.3 for a (pre-intervention) baseline prevalence of 50%, 70% and 90%. Each TnT round was assumed to be implemented at the start of each year, with the reduction in prevalence being a function of the efficacy of PZQ (90%, Table 2.1) and the probability of at least one positive POC-CCA test (i.e., conditional on a positive test, all animals are treated). Consequently, the more animals tested, the greater the impact of each TnT round. Depending on the level of endemicity (baseline prevalence) and the number of tests administered per TnT round, infection dynamics can either stabilise at a suppressed 'pseudo equilibrium' or can continue to decline towards transmission breakpoints.

Figure 2.3. Modelled prevalence dynamics of bovine schistosomiasis during a test-and-treat (TnT) intervention between 2022 and 2030. Either $n = 1$ (light blue), $n = 2$ (baby blue) or $n = 4$ (sapphire blue) POC-CCA tests are administered per TnT round. Dynamics are shown for a baseline prevalence of (a) 50%, (b) 70% and (c) 90% with uncertainty generated by 250 parameter sets yielding a baseline prevalence $\pm 1\%$ of the target. In each panel, the thick solid line depicts the mean and the shaded area the 95% credible interval.

2.4.3. Overdispersion dynamics

The modelled overdispersion dynamics during a TnT intervention between 2022 and 2030 using either $n = 1$, $n = 2$ or $n = 4$ POC-CCA tests per herd are illustrated in Figure 2.4 for a (pre-intervention) baseline prevalence of 50%, 70% and 90%. Each TnT round was assumed to be implemented at the start of each year, altering the distribution of parasite burdens among cattle as defined in Equation 3. The more animals tested, the greater the impact of each TnT round on parasite overdispersion. Depending on the level of endemicity (baseline prevalence) and the number of tests administered per

TnT round, overdispersion dynamics can either stabilise at a suppressed ‘pseudo equilibrium’ or can continue to decline towards transmission breakpoints. When parasites are less overdispersed, most of the parasite burden is carried by fewer cattle (highly aggregated distributions) and their associated transmission breakpoints will be lower (142).

Figure 2.4. Modelled overdispersion dynamics of bovine schistosomiasis during a test-and-treat (TnT) intervention between 2022 and 2030. Either $n=1$ (light blue), $n=2$ (baby blue) or $n=4$ (sapphire blue) POC-CCA tests are administered per TnT round. Dynamics are shown for a baseline prevalence of (a) 50%, (b) 70% and (c) 90% with uncertainty generated by 250 parameter sets yielding a baseline prevalence $\pm 1\%$ of the target. In each panel, the thick solid line depicts the mean and the shaded area the 95% credible interval.

2.4.4. Effectiveness of test-and-treat

The reduction in bovine schistosomiasis case-years as a percentage of the baseline prevalence achieved by the end of 2030 is shown in Figure 2.5. The relative impact of interventions decreases slightly with increasing baseline prevalence. For example, when four animals are tested per TnT round, the mean case-years averted range from a maximum of approximately 85% at a starting prevalence of 40% to approximately 75% at 95% baseline prevalence. When two animals are tested per round, the corresponding reductions range from approximately 75% at 40% baseline prevalence to approximately 60% at 95% baseline prevalence. Irrespective of baseline prevalence, the maximum achievable percentage reduction in case-years over the 9-year time horizon (2022 through 2030) is approximately 85%.

Figure 2.5. Case-years of bovine schistosomiasis averted with test-and-treat by the end of 2030. Represented as percentage of the (pre-intervention) baseline prevalence in 2022 using either $n = 1$ (light blue), $n = 2$ (baby blue) or $n = 4$ (sapphire blue) POC-CCA tests administered per test-and-treat round. Solid lines depict the mean and coloured bands 95% credible intervals.

The percentage of simulations reaching a prevalence of less than 1% by the end of 2030, defined nominally here as ‘elimination’ is shown in Figure 2.6. Elimination is an unlikely outcome when using $n = 1$ or $n = 2$ tests per TnT round, but for $n = 4$ there is up to approximately 75% chance of achieving the 1% elimination target by the end of 2030 in low prevalence settings and, even in the highest prevalence settings, the chance is greater than 10%.

Figure 2.6. Nominal ‘elimination’ vs pre-intervention prevalence. Percentage of bovine schistosomiasis simulations reaching less than 1% prevalence by the end of 2030 following nine annual rounds of test-and-treat (TnT), against (pre-intervention) baseline prevalence in 2022. Either $n = 1$ (light blue), $n = 2$ (baby blue) or $n = 4$ (sapphire blue) POC-CCA tests are administered per TnT round.

2.4.5. Diagnostic performance dynamics

Modelled changes in the PPV during the TnT intervention are shown in Figure 2.7. The dynamics illustrate how the PPV (or the probability of detecting at least one truly infected animal; ‘true positive’)—while being relatively high at pre-intervention baseline—declines during TnT with the declining prevalence of schistosomiasis (Figure 2.3). By 2030, for $n = 4$ tests per TnT round, the PPV is less than 25% for 90% baseline prevalence and less than 5% for 50% and 70% baseline prevalence. The use of fewer tests retains a higher PPV because of the diminished likelihood of detecting a false positive—specificity declines in powers of n —and the reduced impact on schistosomiasis prevalence (Figure 2.3, Figure 2.5).

Figure 2.7. Modelled positive predictive value dynamics for detecting bovine schistosomiasis during a test-and-treat (TnT) intervention between 2022 and 2030. Either $n = 1$ (light blue), $n = 2$ (baby blue) or $n = 4$ (sapphire blue) POC-CCA tests are administered per TnT round. Dynamics are shown for a baseline prevalence of (a) 50%, (b) 70% and (c) 90% with uncertainty generated by 250 parameter sets yielding a baseline prevalence $\pm 1\%$ of the target. In each panel, the point depicts the mean and the vertical bars the 95% credible interval.

2.5. Discussion

2.5.1. Potential control of animal schistosomiasis in sub-Saharan Africa

The recently launched WHO guidelines for the control and elimination of human schistosomiasis include within its strategy a consideration of potential control of infection in animal reservoirs (5, 6, 10). Here, the potential effectiveness of a TnT strategy targeting bovine schistosomiasis was explored, motivated by epidemiological data collected in northern Senegal where the prevalence can be greater than 90%. The present chapter shows that a hypothetical TnT intervention running from 2022 through 2030 could have a substantial impact on bovine schistosomiasis, averting up to 85% of case-years and, in lower prevalence settings, effecting a substantial chance towards local elimination/interruption of transmission. Hypothetically, if TnT was used at scale and targeted at multiple livestock species (to minimize refugia), it could not only facilitate the WHO elimination goals for human schistosomiasis—by limiting spillover infection from animal reservoirs to humans and concurrent opportunities for interspecific hybridization—but also enhance productivity and livelihoods, further helping to lift people out of poverty.

2.5.2. Targeted point-of-care testing

Notwithstanding the potential benefits of treating livestock and reducing the burden of schistosomiasis, an equally important objective behind the TnT strategy is to avoid unnecessary treatment of uninfected herds. Achieving this objective critically depends on the specificity of the diagnostic test used. The

modelled TnT strategy used a POC-CCA diagnostic originally validated for the detection of *S. mansoni* in humans (145) which has been shown to have moderate sensitivity (~62%) and specificity (~70%) in detecting *S. bovis* infections in cattle (136). The estimates used here serve to illustrate the challenges associated with trying to maximize effectiveness while minimizing unnecessary treatment. Parallel use of multiple POC-CCA tests enhances sensitivity and effectiveness but at the cost of reduced specificity.

The use of a POC test—as opposed to more specific traditional faecal parasitology—is important to facilitate the ease of implementing TnT strategies at scale. Moreover, the data presented here clearly shows that parasitology based on KK of livestock stool has very poor sensitivity. However, the estimated specificity of currently available POC-CCA may be too low to satisfy confidence requirements to avoid initiation and continuation of TnT in uninfected herds, thus ongoing work to enhance specificity for livestock usage should be prioritized, even at the cost of sensitivity. With improved specificity, adaptive strategies could also be developed to help meet the dual TnT objectives. For example, the use of a single test to identify and initiate TnT would minimize the risk of an initial false positive and subsequent testing could be implemented only after several completed treatment rounds to lower the number of potentially missed treatments. Alternatively, initial testing could aim to quantify herd-level prevalence (adjusting for sensitivity and specificity) and mathematical modelling could be used to project the likely number of treatment rounds required to reach pre-defined objectives.

2.5.3. Transmission modelling and uncertainty

Modelling of the transmission dynamics of human schistosomiasis has been used extensively in recent years to evaluate the impact of MDA and to inform decision making on strategies to reach the WHO's elimination goals (146-148). In contrast, modelling has been seldom applied to livestock schistosomiasis although some key modelling analyses have quantified contributions of zoonotic reservoirs and human-animal schistosome hybrids to infection dynamics in humans (17, 19). Nonetheless, there remains great uncertainty in the understanding of the population biology and transmission dynamics of livestock schistosomiasis, which has been reflected in the modelling presented here. Some uncertainties are common to both human and livestock infection. For example, the role of acquired immunity, while long suspected to contribute to the epidemiological patterns observed in human schistosomiasis (149, 150) has not been elucidated completely in either humans or animals, yet its effects may alter the effectiveness of MDA (151). Other processes that regulate schistosome populations—such as density-dependent fecundity—are also debated and incompletely understood in both humans and animals (143). Moreover, a recent eco-evolutionary hypothesis linking worm-directed concomitant immunity and epidemiological patterns in humans presents further (potential) consequences for schistosome control (152). The impact on the transmission breakpoint (i.e., the minimum infection level that can sustain parasite transmission) of repeated MDA rounds has, however, been explored in a recent mathematical analysis of helminth burdens within a human population (142). Treatment non-compliance was highlighted as a key challenge that increases parasite overdispersion (smaller k) and further complicates elimination (by 336 increasing parasite population

resilience) (142). This important phenomenon has been incorporated in the present model via a dynamic overdispersion parameter that varies through repeated TnT rounds (142).

The hypothetical TnT intervention evaluated in this chapter was simulated with a (single) herd-level deterministic model and parametric uncertainty. For instance, due to a lack of standardised praziquantel efficacy estimates for livestock schistosomiasis, an alternative estimate based on a related human-infective schistosome species was used. Nonetheless, as described in Chapter 3, this alternative estimate was not dissimilar to preliminary anti-schistosomal PZQ efficacy estimates derived from a small trial conducted on naturally infected Senegalese livestock. Conspicuously, there is a lack of information about the distribution of schistosome infection among herds in the northern Senegal study area, with transhumance practices and shared ownership among several households adding to the complexities to fill this research gap. In addition, modelling schistosome dynamics in livestock is complicated by the fragmented nature of livestock herds in small rural communities and limited understanding of environmental exposure (i.e., waterbody interaction) among dispersed populations.

Given these uncertainties, the modelling presented here should be viewed as illustrative of the potential impact of TnT. Animals within herds are assumed to experience similar infection risk as they will be exposed to potentially contaminated water sources as a group. Given that the modelled population of interest was a single herd it is implicitly assumed that baseline prevalence values are the same across herds. In the proposed simulated strategy, a representative small number of animals are tested to determine whether the herd is likely to be infected, and the whole herd is treated when an infected member of the group is detected. For simplicity and as proof-of-principle, the model simulates the schistosome burden in one animal host (bovines) within a perennial transmission location, given that in the northern Senegal study area upon which model parameters are based, bovines are thought to act as the primary zoonotic reservoir (19). Notwithstanding, it is apparent, that both large and small ruminants can be heavily infected with blood flukes across Africa, and with *Schistosoma* species that can infect humans through viable hybridization with *S. haematobium*. In addition to this, wildlife, notably rodents and non-human primates can also play a significant role in zoonotic transmission of both intestinal and urogenital schistosomes to humans (34, 153). Thus, the model deliberately omits many structural (e.g., inter-connected nature of herds) and biological (e.g., role of acquired and/or concomitant immunity) complexities that would alter the transmission dynamics. Nonetheless, the clear contribution of cattle in spillover to humans in SSA in conjunction to the feasibility and numerous benefits of implementing control measures in these domestic ruminants (public and veterinary health benefits plus economic benefits) justify efforts to design a coherent and comprehensive strategy that includes them.

Additionally, there are numerous practical and logistical challenges that must be overcome to make TnT viable. Appropriate veterinary dosages and commercially available products tailored to livestock alongside stakeholder education would contribute to avoid the current *ad hoc* use (and misuse) at livestock owners' discretion (35) and minimize the risk of PZQ resistance. Critically, within Africa, PZQ is currently donated for human use only and while there may be some market to purchase PZQ by

larger farmers because of the productivity benefits—particularly for small ruminants(101)—, it is highly unlikely that a livestock-centric schistosomiasis programme would be sustainable without some form of third-party donation.

Yet while there remain major challenges to the implementation of TnT, the evidence is now incontrovertible that livestock act as reservoirs for schistosome hybridization (18, 40, 48, 49, 71), and that livestock schistosomiasis causes significant economic and productivity losses (35, 101), compounding further the lives and livelihoods of impoverished populations. The need to address this challenge has been articulated by the WHO (5, 6). The findings presented here confirm that a TnT approach has the potential to be an effective strategy in controlling livestock schistosomiasis within a broader One Health approach to eliminate NTDs.

2.6. Conclusion

The simulated impact of a theoretical bovine test-and-treat strategy on schistosomiasis prevalence in farming locations of the Senegal River Basin could be substantial. This chapter underlines the illustrative potential for One Health strategies targeted at a relevant animal reservoir in an African schistosomiasis transmission hotspot. Nonetheless, alongside the limitations of the proof-of-principle herd-level deterministic model and related knowledge gaps abovementioned, operational uncertainties remain since the positive predictive value of the evaluated POC test rapidly declines. Ongoing work to enhance specificity for livestock usage is therefore needed to avoid initiation and continuation of TnT to uninfected herds. Moreover, future extensions of the model presented here (e.g., metapopulation model with variable baseline prevalence between herds) are necessary to compare between different control interventions.

CHAPTER 3

Efficacy of praziquantel chemotherapy against *Schistosoma* spp. in domestic ruminants of the Senegal River Basin

3.1. Summary

When assessing the worldwide socioeconomic impact of parasitic diseases, schistosomiasis is second only to malaria. Indeed, in 2021, large-scale (preventive) schistosomiasis treatment in countries with moderate to high transmission was required for at least 250 million people. Praziquantel (PZQ), an essential anthelmintic originally developed for veterinary use, is the sole drug used as treatment in such large-scale human schistosomiasis campaigns, upon which public health elimination efforts rely on. Despite its safety and ease of use against human schistosomes, the efficacy of PZQ against the schistosomes of African livestock has yet to be standardised. Notably, livestock have been recently recognised as key maintenance or spillover hosts in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). With the intent of filling this research gap and motivated by reports of inadequate use of PZQ to treat livestock schistosomiasis in SSA, naturally infected domestic ruminants of a high endemicity area of northern Senegal were recruited, tested, treated, and re-tested to evaluate drug efficacy after oral administration of 25 mg/kg of PZQ. This chapter presents statistical analysis stemming from this small drug efficacy trial, using an indicator of drug efficacy against viable infections, miracidia reduction rate. Notably, a differential response to treatment among the domestic ruminant species was found, with high efficacy of PZQ against schistosome infection, in bovines only. Interestingly, evidence of body condition score improvement resulting from treatment was recorded not only for bovines but also for sheep. Findings represent a contribution towards a truly One Health approach, an approach needed to reach elimination of this disease as a public health problem.

3.2. Introduction

Schistosomiasis is placed second to malaria in the global ranking of impactful parasitic diseases (154). Chronic ill-health of the definitive host—including humans and non-human mammals—is a consequence of egg retention in tissues (see Figure 3.1 for a summary of the parasite's life cycle). Depending on the localisation and number of trapped eggs, this translates to clinical signs such as distension of the abdomen, bloody urine, and diarrhoea (155), anaemia and reduced growth. In some cases, an acute systemic hypersensitive reaction may also ensue within weeks of infection (37).

Figure 3.1. Schistosome life cycle (Source: <https://www.cdc.gov/dpdx/schistosomiasis/index.html>). Following female and male worm copulation within the blood-vessels of the mammalian host, eggs are excreted via urine or faeces, depending on the parasite species, and hatch after contact with freshwater, swimming as miracidia that go on to infect intermediate snails. Subsequently, larvae burst from the mollusc as cercariae into surrounding water. When a mammal is exposed to the schistosome contaminated waterbody, infective cercaria have a chance to enter the host by piercing its skin.

Female adult *Schistosoma* spp. blood flukes (flatworms) can live for years alongside their male partners within the blood vessels of mammals, where they release large masses of eggs that become trapped and cause an inflammatory response in the lumen of the bladder or intestine, the parenchyma of the liver or other organs, or else are shed via urine or faeces (23, 155). When schistosome eggs are released into the aquatic habitat of freshwater snails they hatch into miracidia. This free-swimming larval infective stage actively penetrates the intermediate mollusc to develop asexually, later bursting from the snail into water as another free-swimming larval stage known cercaria. The infective cercaria swim and burrow into the skin of the definitive host while shedding the tail (156). The parasite, now turned schistosomula, migrates through the lungs and heart, reaches the liver where it develops and later exits through the portal system when mature (37). Depending on the species, adult worms reside and

copulate either in the venous plexus of the bladder (urogenital schistosomiasis) or in the mesenteric veins (intestinal schistosomiasis).

Global schistosomiasis control consists of large-scale preventive chemotherapy (PC) targeting communities in 51 schistosomiasis endemic countries with moderate to high transmission (157). In 2021 at least 250 million people required PC, predominantly within sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (157). Such intervention campaigns have been scaled-up in the last decade (157), with recent modelling showing a reduction in prevalence of 58.3% among the targeted high-risk population (i.e., school-age children)—67.9% decrease of *S. haematobium* and 53.6% decrease of *S. mansoni*, based on data from 44 SSA countries (130). In the absence of commercially available anti-schistosomal vaccines, these effective mass drug administration (MDA) campaigns have relied heavily on praziquantel (PZQ).

PZQ is an acetylated quinoline-pyrazine anthelmintic (158), used as the treatment of choice against cestodes and schistosomes (159). Initially approved for schistosomiasis veterinary treatment in the late 70s, improved synthetic methods of the early 80s (160) assured its present status as the sole drug used against human schistosomiasis. The advantages of PZQ are its operational convenience—administered orally, no cold chain required; efficacy—90% egg reduction rates (144); safety—well tolerated in the different clinical forms of the disease with only mild short-term adverse reactions (160, 161); and price—currently at 0.20 USD per treatment (160). The main drawbacks of PZQ include around 30% of treated patients remain egg-positive after treatment (162), and varying response to the drug among the parasite's stages and sexes, with adult females and juvenile schistosomes being naturally less susceptible (162). Importantly, the mechanism of action of this essential drug was recently elucidated (162, 163). Using a combination of ligand-and-target-based methods and genome-wide association studies, researchers demonstrated that PZQ activates a transient receptor potential (TRP) melastatin ion channel in schistosomes causing calcium influx and associated paralysis in worms (162, 163).

The western SSA country of Senegal has persistent hyperendemic areas (human schistosomiasis endemicity map of western Africa in Appendix E1) where nearby waterbodies are inhabited by suitable intermediate freshwater snail hosts. Land use changes resulting from the Diama Dam construction completed in 1985, have altered the ecology of northern Senegal both expanding the habitat range of the intermediate molluscs and facilitating prolonged exposure of definitive hosts to schistosome contaminated water (18, 164). The salt-wedge Diama Dam prevents sea water from entering the Senegal river (165). Its impact on *S. mansoni* and *S. haematobium* prevalence became apparent from 1988 and 1989, respectively, given that salinity no longer served as a deterrent on freshwater intermediate snails (164). In the Senegal River Basin (SRB), six competent schistosome vector snail species were reported in the 1990s (*Biomphalaria pfeifferi*, *Bulinus truncatus*, *Bu. globosus*, *Bu. forskalii*, *Bu. senegalensis* and *Bu. umbilicatus*), in addition to four species of schistosome, *S. mansoni*, *S. haematobium*, *S. bovis*, and *S. curassoni* (164).

More recently, transmission hotspots with zoonotic transmission have been identified in northern Senegal (18, 66), involving areas with perennial or seasonal transmission, several schistosome species and their crosses, as well as diverse definitive hosts (58). Two recently surveyed areas in this region henceforth referred to as Richard Toll (RT) and Barkedji (BK) are endemic for schistosomiasis (18). In RT, which covers locations in the SRB including the town of Richard Toll and villages surrounding Lac de Guiers, the largest lake of the SRB, perennial schistosome transmission is maintained by year-round persistence of contaminated waterbodies. In comparison, in BK which spans locations in the Vallée du Ferlo including the towns of Barkedji and Linguère and nearby villages, there is seasonal transmission sustained by rainy season temporary ponds (18). Livestock have been recognised as key maintenance hosts in the SRB: bovines for *S. bovis* and small ruminants for *S. curassoni* (18). Both of these schistosome species have veterinary significance (133), owing to productivity losses registered in infected livestock including growth retardation, reduced milk yield and reproductive capacity, and even death (23, 35, 101, 166). Consequently, the off-label use of human formula PZQ (often from MDA campaigns) to treat livestock schistosomiasis (at inappropriate doses) has been reported in the area (35, 101), which motivated the present study. Moreover, uncertainty regarding PZQ's efficacy against African livestock schistosomes remains, as the standard method used in veterinary parasitology (i.e., faecal egg counts (FEC)) performs poorly with schistosome eggs in ruminant stools, with alternative diagnostics explored (18, 103, 136). Such challenges represent a barrier in the development of potential structured animal interventions for the control of livestock schistosomiasis in SSA (102).

This chapter attempts to fill some of the knowledge and operational gaps identified above, by performing statistical analyses on SRB data from a small 2018 drug efficacy study in which, adequately dosed veterinary praziquantel was used to treat livestock schistosomiasis.

3.3. Materials and Methods

3.3.1. Pre- and post-praziquantel study

Livestock ruminants of two schistosomiasis endemic areas of SRB with contrasting schistosome transmission (18) were examined and sampled by fieldwork teams. RT with perennial transmission, was surveyed between May and June 2018, and BK with seasonal transmission, was surveyed between July and August 2018. The RT study site included 5 villages: Djidièry (approximate Google Maps decimal degrees coordinates: 16.459833, -15.661083); Mbane (16.266833, -15.795306); Medina Cheikhou (16.419657, -15.705997); Ndombo (16.434361, -15.698694); and Thiago (16.396154, -15.719644). The BK study site included 2 villages: Barkedji (15.276826, -14.867839); and Loubel Lana (15.280583, -14.708056).

Pre-sampling prevalence levels of *S. bovis* among bovines in RT reached 94% in 2017, while *S. curassoni* 2017 prevalence levels in BK reached 86% in goats and 77% in sheep ((18) see map in Appendix E2). The aim of the longitudinal study entitled "A One Health platform for sustainable

schistosomiasis control amongst African livestock” funded via a Global Challenges Research Fund Impact Accelerator Award (GCRF-IAA) (Ref BB/GCRF-IAA/17/19), a subcomponent of the Zoonoses and Emerging Livestock System (ZELS) programme, was to determine clearance and/or reduction of *Schistosoma* spp. infection in livestock after treatment with veterinary praziquantel (PZQ) at the recommended dose. Therefore, sampling targeted high-risk ruminant species for each area, namely bovines in RT (main *S. bovis* host identified by ZELS), and goats and sheep in BK (main hosts of *S. curassoni* identified by ZELS). Recruitment of specific villages was based on a previously recorded high positivity rate for the target ruminant species (18). Owing to the coprological tests’ low sensitivity in infected ruminants—in cattle, goats, and sheep, 31%, 21% and 28% for Kato-Katz (KK) test, and 79%, 40 and 44% for miracidia hatching technique (MHT), respectively (supplementary material of (18)), all livestock owners in the recruited villages were invited to participate. A target of at least 40 animals recruited per site was set based on expected number of positives.

Each animal was given a study identifier linked to village and species (animal ID) and their ear tag number and owner name were annotated for follow up. Animals were assessed for biometric data (sex, age, live weight) and body condition score (BCS), and faecal samples were collected and weighted, aiming for 15g of stool from bovines and 5g from small ruminants (Caprinae subfamily which includes goats and sheep). Only animals confirmed to be infected with schistosomes by KK and/or MHT were included in the longitudinal study. Co-infection with other parasites, including liver flukes (*Fasciola* spp.) and nematodes of the *Strongyles* family, assessed during KK was recorded. With owner’s consent, schistosomiasis treatment with PZQ was administered by oral drenching at a recommended dose of 25 mg/kg (23, 133). Since a veterinary product containing only PZQ was not available at the time in Senegal, a commercial veterinary product with a PZQ composition of 3.75% w/v (37.5 mg/ml), was imported from South Africa (5 L presentation, Bayer (PTY) Ltd). Treatment was followed by BCS re-evaluation and faecal resampling, 24 to 38 days later. Post-PZQ resampling was scheduled before potential reinfections could have produced eggs (i.e., intestinal schistosomes mature by 6 weeks), thus helping to ascertaining positivity corresponded to apparent treatment failures. Known causes of the latter include juvenile parasite’s low PZQ susceptibility and/or potential resistance (167).

Host age was estimated by teeth examination (i.e., age estimate based on eruption times of incisors) following established guidelines (84) for each domestic ruminant species (see Appendix E3). Host weight was estimated using body weight tapes specific to each domestic ruminant species.

Pre- and post-PZQ BCS evaluation was undertaken by the same three assessors to ensure consistency using an objective 1-5 scoring system where 1 is extremely thin and 5 extremely obese. Details of standardised body condition score for bovines (168), goats (169) and sheep (170), are found elsewhere.

The final tally of recruited, confirmed infected, treated, and followed up longitudinal study ruminants was 62 RT bovines and 61 BK small ruminants. The proportion still infected post-PZQ was 17.742% of

bovines (11/62), 75.862% of goats (22/29), and 87.500% of sheep (28/32) (Webster et al, 2018, not published).

The present work is an analysis of previously collected data and associated faecal samples from the longitudinal study. In comparison to KK, which has a lower sensitivity due to poor egg visibility caused by the high fibre content in ruminant stools, MHT allows a more accurate estimation of infection intensity comprising a diagnostic for both egg presence and viability (i.e., only viable eggs in stool hatch into the miracidia larval stage) (18, 103, 136). Therefore, in the present work, only animals whose pre- and post-PZQ faecal samples were processed by MHT are analysed. 59 sympatric live-sampled bovines (*Bos taurus*, *Bos indicus* and cross breeds) from 5 RT villages (24 in Djidièry; 18 in Mbane; 7 in Medina Cheikhou; 4 in Ndombo and 6 in Thiago); 22 goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) from 1 BK village (Loumbel Lana); and 22 sheep (*Ovis aries*) from 2 BK villages (5 in Barkedji and 17 in Loumbel Lana) are hereby investigated.

3.3.1.1. Ethical statement

Ethical approval for the ZELS project in West Africa was attained at the RVC and the CNERS in Senegal (applications URN20151327 and SEN15/68, respectively). Written informed consent was obtained from livestock owners. Farmers were provided with vitamins for their livestock, together with optional treatment for animals that remained infected after administration of the 25mg/kg PZQ dose. Animal inclusion depended upon owner willingness and informed consent to participate, plus veterinary assessment of the livestock's suitability. Any animals displaying poor body condition were excluded. Exclusion of clinically affected animals, especially those presenting poor body condition, was based on the risk of thrombosis arising from paralysed or dead worms following treatment of high intensity infections (23).

3.3.2. Miracidia reduction rate and infection clearance

The number of miracidia hatched by MHT (i.e., miracidial counts) and corresponding faecal sample weight in grams, henceforth referred to as miracidia per gram (MPG), were recorded pre- and post-PZQ. Values for stool weight post-PZQ were missing for 4 goats and 2 sheep. Since these values were assumed missing at random, the mean post-PZQ value for the corresponding ruminant species was inputted as post-PZQ stool weight.

The rate of reduction of miracidia after treatment was weighed by stool weight, hence miracidia reduction rate (MRR) was calculated for each animal using,

$$\text{MRR} = 1 - \frac{\text{post-PZQ MPG}}{\text{pre-PZQ MPG}} \quad (1)$$

Arithmetic mean estimates were used to calculate MRR per ruminant species as an indicator of drug efficacy. In addition, the same methodology was applied, within species and village, to detect potential differences between locations. A non-parametric block bootstrap method (171) was used to obtain 95% confidence intervals (CIs) associated to these MRRs. Briefly, matrices of both pre-and post-PZQ miracidial counts and stool weights were built with the number of rows set to the corresponding number of observed values and the number of columns set to 10,000 (i.e. number of bootstrap samples). MRRs were estimated from these matrices, with percentile CIs drawn from the 2.5% and 97.5% of the MRR bootstrap sampling distribution. By randomly resampling blocks of observed data with replacement, this method accounts for correlation among observations from the same animal.

In addition, the number of animals which cleared the infection (i.e., had zero miracidia post-PZQ) per grouping (species and village) were tallied and associated percentile block bootstrap CIs calculated, with the number of bootstrap samples set to 10,000.

3.3.3. Statistical analyses

All computational analyses presented in this chapter were carried out in R (172).

Univariate analysis of pre-and post-PZQ BCS was conducted with paired t-tests, moreover, a non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to corroborate BCS change after treatment. Subsequently, to further evaluate the effect of treatment per ruminant species, the categorical response variable BCS was analysed as an ordered factor using ordinal logistic regression. A two-sample paired (i.e., pre- and post-PZQ) ordinal model approach was taken (173), with animal ID entered explicitly as a blocking variable, using a logit link function and a flexible threshold with the *clmm* R function of the *ordinal* package (174). Briefly, a basic cumulative link mixed model (CLMM) was fitted with the Laplace approximation to explore the fixed effect of treatment status (pre vs post) on BCS. Building upon this basic CLMM, additional explanatory variables such as clearance and/or co-infection with other parasites were explored for all ruminant species, whereas the effect of treatment status grouping by village was explored only for bovines. To distinguish the best fit CLMM describing the relationship between explanatory variables and BCS, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) model selection was carried out with the *AICcmodavg* R package (175).

Cumulative link models are expressed as,

$$h[P(Y_i \leq j | x_i)] = \alpha_j + \beta' x_i, \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, c - 1, \quad (3)$$

where h represents a link function and parameters α_j are category thresholds of the response variable. The model links the cumulative probabilities to a linear predictor, $\beta' x_i$, using the linear predictor to describe effects of explanatory variables on ordinal categorical measurement of Y_i (176). The logit link

function $h(u) = \log \left[\frac{u}{1-u} \right]$ is the inverse of the standard logistic cumulative distribution function (cdf) (176).

Lastly, Fisher's exact test was used to evaluate the significance of specific co-variables highlighted by the ordinal logistic regression model.

3.4. Results

3.4.1. Pre- and post-praziquantel study

3.4.1.1. Biometric data (sex, age, live weight)

Sex was heavily biased towards females. Only five out of the 59 bovines were males, whereas all recruited small ruminants were females.

Teeth examination was not recorded for 31 bovines and 2 goats. 75% of examined bovines had an estimated age of 3.5-4 years, while 85% of examined goats had 2.5-4 years. In sheep, 68% had an estimated age of 2.5-3 years. Graphical representation of the distribution of recorded dental age estimates is presented in appendices E4, E5 and E6 for bovines, goats, and sheep, respectively.

Live weight in bovines ranged between 120 to 200 kg (mean= 195.76 kg, SD= 16.53), with a respective range of administered PZQ volume between 80 to 130 ml. Either 15, 20 or 25 kg of live weight were estimated in goats (mean=22.86 kg, SD = 3.38) with a corresponding administered PZQ volume of either 10, 14 or 17 ml. In sheep either 20 or 25 kg of live weight were estimated (mean= 24.77 kg, SD= 1.07) with 14 or 17 ml of treatment given.

3.4.1.2. Summary epidemiological statistics

103 infected ruminants evaluated pre- and post-PZQ were analysed. Infection intensity indicated by the arithmetic mean MPG varied among ruminant species. Before treatment, mean values were 0.80 MPG (SD=0.95) in bovines, 8.41 MPG (SD=7.68) in goats and 2.64 MPG (SD=2.81) in sheep. After treatment, mean values were 0.15 MPG (SD=0.50) in bovines, 7.22 MPG (SD=14.64) in goats and 7.06 MPG (SD=12.89) in sheep. Stratification by village highlights further variation by locality. Descriptive epidemiological data for the seven northern Senegal villages studied is summarised in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Intensity of *Schistosoma* spp. infection pre- and post-PZQ per species and village.

Species	Study site	Villages	n	Pre-PZQ		Post-PZQ	
				Mean MPG (SD)	Counted miracidia (min–max)	Mean MPG (SD)	Counted miracidia (min–max)
Bovine	RT	Djidiéry	24	1.14 (1.26)	1–52	0.09 (0.42)	0–31
		Mbane	18	0.38 (0.38)	1–17	0.33 (0.73)	0–42
		Medina Cheikhou	7	0.57 (0.70)	1–14	0 (0)	0–0
		Ndombo	4	1.43 (0.48)	11–27	0.13 (0.13)	1–5
		Thiago	6	0.50 (0.47)	1–18	0 (0)	0–0
Goat	BK	Loumbel Lana	22	8.41 (7.68)	1–55	7.22 (14.64)	0–303
Sheep	BK	Barkedji	5	1.25 (1.23)	2–17	9.54 (21.08)	0–241
		Loumbel Lana	17	3.05 (3.03)	1–48	6.33 (10.22)	0–184

Abbreviations: n, number of animals; MPG, miracidia per gram of stool; SD, standard deviation; min, minimum; max, maximum.

Moreover, depiction of paired (i.e., pre- to post-PZQ) MPG by subject suggests overall response to treatment patterns per ruminant species (Figures 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4). For instance, the maximum MPG value recorded amongst bovines was 5 at pre-treatment, with most grey lines connecting pre-PZQ (in blue turquoise) and post-PZQ (in persian red) levels falling diagonally towards 0 (see Figure 3.2). This indicates a pattern of decreasing infection intensity in bovines after treatment. In contrast in goats, the maximum MPG value recorded was close to 60 at post-treatment, the highest value recorded amongst study ruminants. Grey connecting lines present a mixture of directions, indicating variability in the response to treatment in goats (see Figure 3.3). In sheep, the maximum MPG value was close to 50, also recorded at post-treatment. Grey connecting lines are predominantly horizontal in addition to substantial outliers of rising lines (see Figure 3.4). The former indicates a pattern of stable infection intensity in sheep after treatment while a rebound effect can be inferred from the distinct outliers.

Figure 3.2. Paired MPG for bovines before and after PZQ administration. Grey lines connect pre-PZQ (in blue turquoise) with corresponding post-PZQ (in persian red) values. Note that the maximum MPG recorded in this species was 5, before treatment.

Figure 3.3. Paired MPG for goats before and after PZQ administration. Grey lines connect pre-PZQ (in blue turquoise) with corresponding post-PZQ (in persian red) values. Note that the maximum MPG recorded in this species was 57.17, after treatment.

Figure 3.4. Paired MPG for sheep before and after PZQ administration. Grey lines connect pre-PZQ (in blue turquoise) with corresponding post-PZQ (in Persian red) values. Note that the maximum MPG recorded in this species was 47.255, after treatment.

Additional graphical exploration of the differing patterns of treatment response among ruminant species was conducted by plotting further stratification by age (Figure 3.5, 3.6, 3.7). The treatment response in the larger bovine age group (78.571% of the 28 bovines with age estimates were older than 3 years old) was similar to that observed in the smaller (and younger) age group (Figure 3.5), despite an overall higher range of pre-PZQ infection intensity recorded in older cattle (right-hand side violin plot in Figure 3.5). The single older bovine with a post-PZQ intensity of infection notoriously higher than the group mean (Persian red point above the red dotted line), did not have an above-mean intensity of infection before treatment (connecting blue turquoise point below the dotted line). In goats, the larger age group (85% of the 20 goats with age estimates were 2.5 years old and above) had overlapping pre- and post-PZQ MPG means (turquoise and red dotted lines in right-hand side plot of Figure 3.6), while also aggregating the subject variability in treatment response for the species. In contrast, treatment reduced MPG among the 3 remaining younger goats. In sheep, no overall response to treatment (overlapping pre- and post-PZQ MPG means indicated respectively by turquoise and red dotted lines of Figure 3.7's left-hand side plot) were observed in the smaller and younger age group (27.273% of 22 sheep with age estimates were less than 2.5 years old), whereas mean infection intensity tripled after treatment in the larger and older age group (72.727% of 22 sheep with age estimates were 2.5 years old and above).

Figure 3.5. Age stratification of paired MPG for bovines before and after PZQ. Horizontal dotted lines depict pre-PZQ (in blue turquoise) and post-PZQ (in persian red) mean MPG. Note that the corresponding mean MPG pre and post values were respectively 0.721 and 0.011 in younger bovines, and 0.869 and 0.058 in older bovines.

Figure 3.6. Age stratification of paired MPG for goats before and after PZQ. Horizontal dotted lines depict pre-PZQ (in turquoise) and post-PZQ (in red) mean MPG per age group (<2.5 years old on the left; ≥ 2.5 years old on the right). Note that the corresponding mean MPG pre- and post-PZQ values were respectively 7.198 and 2.840 in younger goats, and 8.977 and 8.844 in older goats.

Figure 3.7. Age stratification of paired MPG for sheep before and after PZQ. Horizontal dotted lines depict pre-PZQ (in turquoise) and post-PZQ (in red) mean MPG per age group (<2.5 years old on the left; ≥ 2.5 years old on the right). Note that the corresponding mean MPG pre- and post-PZQ values were respectively 2.022 and 2.213 in younger sheep, and 2.873 and 8.874 in older sheep.

Lastly, further stratification by co-infection (with other parasites) status was graphically represented to explore potential factors associated with differing response to treatment among ruminants (Figure 3.8, 3.9, 3.10). Among co-infected bovines (88.136% of 59) treatment reduced infection intensity excepting a few animals for which post-PZQ MPG was above the pre-treatment mean (3 persian red points above the turquoise dotted line in the left-hand side plot of Figure 3.8). The overall effect of treatment was almost null among not co-infected (turquoise and red dotted lines almost overlap in right-hand side plot of Figure 3.8). In goats, most animals were not co-infected (81.818% of 22) with a varying effect of treatment by subject and a slight overall decrease in infection intensity (turquoise dotted line above the red dotted line in right-hand side plot of Figure 3.9). For the remaining co-infected goats (4 of 22) contrasting effects of treatment were observed (half below the pre-PZQ MPG mean and half above). In sheep, no overall response to treatment (overlapping pre- and post- PZQ MPG means indicated respectively by turquoise and red dotted lines of Figure 3.10's left-hand side plot) were observed among co-infected (31.818% of 22), whereas mean infection intensity more than tripled after treatment among not co-infected (68.182% of 22 sheep).

Figure 3.8. Co-infection (with other parasites) status stratification of paired MPG for bovinies before and after PZQ. Horizontal dotted lines depict pre-PZQ (in turquoise) and post-PZQ (in red) mean MPG per co-infection status (co-infected group on the left; not co-infected on the right). Note that the corresponding pre- and post-PZQ values were 0.800 and 0.072 in co-infected, and 0.761 and 0.705 in not co-infected bovinies.

Figure 3.9. Co-infection (with other parasites) status stratification of paired MPG for goats before and after PZQ. Horizontal dotted lines depict pre-PZQ (in turquoise) and post-PZQ (in red) mean MPG per co-infection status (co-infected group on the left; not co-infected on the right). Note that the corresponding pre- and post-PZQ values were 1.676 and 7.928 in co-infected, and 9.906 and 7.064 in not co-infected goats.

Figure 3.10. Co-infection (with other parasites) status stratification of paired MPG for sheep before and after PZQ. Horizontal dotted lines depict pre-PZQ (in turquoise) and post-PZQ (in red) mean MPG per co-infection status (co-infected group on the left; not co-infected on the right). Note that the corresponding pre- and post-PZQ values were 3.523 and 3.661 in co-infected, and 2.230 and 8.643 in not co-infected sheep.

3.4.1.3. Variation in praziquantel efficacy against schistosomiasis

As mentioned above, MRR estimates derived from MPGs pre- and post-PZQ were used as proxy for drug efficacy. Percentage MRR per species and village alongside CIs, as well as the percentage clearance (i.e., proportion of animals that cleared the infection after treatment) and corresponding CIs are presented in Table 3.2. This analysis was carried out on data from 103 ruminants (59 bovines, 22 goats and 22 sheep) which were evaluated by MHT before and after PZQ treatment. At ruminant species level, the MRR ranged from 81.53% (95% CI, 55.01 to 94.69) in bovines, to 14.22% (95% CI, -132.58 to 70.25) in goats and -167.19% (95% CI, -519.03 to 13.64) in sheep.

Table 3.2. Miracidia Reduction Rate (MRR) and *Schistosoma* spp. infection clearance per ruminant species and village after PZQ treatment.

Species (n)	MRR, % (95% CI)	Cleared, (n) % (95% CI)	Villages (n)	MRR, % (95% CI)	Cleared, (n) % (95% CI)
Bovines (n=59)	81.53 (55.01–94.69)	(n=48) 81.36 (71.19–89.83)	Djidièry (n=24)	92.22 (67.36–100)	(n=22) 91.67 (79.17–100)
			Mbane (n=18)	11.77 (-123.68–85.71)	(n=13) 72.22 (50–88.89)
			Medina Cheikhou (n=7)	100 (100)	(n=7) 100 (100)
			Ndombo (n=4)	90.70 (80.72–96.08)	(n=0) 0 (0)
			Thiago (n=6)	100 (100)	(n=6) 100 (100)
Goats (n=22)	14.22 (-132.58–70.25)	(n=10) 45.45 (22.73–68.18)	Loumbel Lana (n=22)	14.22 (-132.58–70.25)	(n=10) 45.45 (22.73–68.18)
Sheep (n=22)	-167.19 (-519.03–13.64)	(n=5) 22.73 (9.09–40.90)	Barkedji (n=5)	-662.20 (-3582.96–97.18)	(n=2) 40 (0–80)
			Loumbel Lana (n=17)	-107.43 (-405.20–32.03)	(n=3) 17.65 (0–35.29)

Abbreviations: n, number of animals; MRR, miracidia reduction rate; 95% CI, 95 percent bootstrap confidence interval.

Among bovines, the lowest MRR was seen in the village of Mbane (11.77%, 95% CI, -123.68 to 85.71) while the remaining four villages had MRRs above 90%. In the villages of Medina Cheikhou and Thiago all recruited bovines cleared the infection (MRR = 100%, clearance = 100%), followed by Djidièry where almost all animals cleared the infection (MRR= 92.22%, clearance = 91.67%). In contrast, in Mbane despite the low MRR, more than two thirds of animals cleared the infection (MRR = 11.77%, clearance = 72.22%), while none of the recruited bovines from Ndombo cleared the infection (MRR = 90.70%,

clearance = 0%). In total, 11 bovines out of 59 remained infected after treatment (i.e., non-responders: 2 in Djidiéry, 5 in Mbane, and 4 in Ndombo). The population genetics of schistosomes recovered pre- and post-PZQ from these non-responder bovines in conjunction to pre-PZQ schistosomes from some of the responder bovines is analysed in the next chapter (Chapter 4).

A single village, Loumbel Lana, was recruited for goats. Here MRR was low and less than half of the animals cleared the infection (MRR= 14.22%, clearance = 45.45%). 12 out of 22 goats were non-responders. In sheep, MRR and clearance were even lower than in goats at both species (MRR= 167.19%, clearance = 22.73%) and village level (see Table 3.2). 17 out of 22 sheep were non-responders, 3 of 5 from Barkedji and 14 of 17 from Loumbel Lana.

When the relationship between co-infection and clearance was explored with Fisher's exact test, no significant association was found in bovines (p-value = 0.112) nor in goats or sheep (p-value = 1). The proportion of bovines that were co-infected among those that cleared and did not clear schistosome infection was respectively 84.62% (44/52) and 15.38% (8/52). Most bovines were co-infected, with only 7 out of the 59 recruited, not co-infected (cleared 4/7 and did not clear 3/7). The inverse was true for goats, most were not co-infected (cleared 8/18 and did not clear 10/18) and only 4 out of the 22 recruited were co-infected (cleared 2/4 and did not clear 2/4). Similarly, most sheep were not co-infected (cleared 4/15 and did not clear 11/15) and only 7 out of the 22 recruited were co-infected (cleared 1/7 and did not clear 6/7).

3.4.1.4. Variation in body condition score pre- and post-praziquantel

There was a highly significant increase in BCS following treatment in bovines (pre-PZQ mean= 2.398, SD = 0.438; post-PZQ mean = 2.593, SD =0.389; mean of differences= 0.194, SD= 0.553; paired t-test p-value =0.006; n=54), and in sheep (pre- PZQ mean= 2, SD = 0.229; post- PZQ mean = 2.4, SD =0.262; mean of differences= 0.4, SD= 0.262; paired t-test p-value < 0.001; n = 20). No such significant effect of treatment on BCS was observed in goats (pre- PZQ mean= 2.386, SD =0.343; post- PZQ mean = 2.409, SD = 0.197; mean of differences= 0.023, SD= 0.326; paired t-test p-value = 0.374; n=22).

Paired-BCS data visualization ratifies these findings with most points (i.e., observations or individual animals) falling above and to the left of the blue line in bovines (Figure 3.11 A) and sheep (Figure 3.13 A), indicating cases for which BCS was greater after. Such trend was not seen in goats (Figure 3.12 A). Graphical representation of BCS difference (i.e., post-PZQ BCS minus pre-PZQ BCS) further highlights variation in relation to treatment not only between species but also individuals (Figures 3.11 B, 3.12 B, 3.13 B).

Figure 3.11. BCS variation in bovines during pre-and post-praziquantel study. A) Paired BCS (post- vs pre-PZQ) scatter plot with one-to-one blue line. There was a significant overall increase in BCS of bovines after treatment (non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test p-value = 0.013). B) BCS difference per subject bar plot. An increase in BCS following treatment was seen in 28 bovines, while BCS decreased in 9. No BCS difference was observed in 17 out of 54 bovines evaluated.

Figure 3.12. BCS variation in goats during pre-and post-praziquantel study. A) Paired BCS (post- vs pre-PZQ) scatter plot with one-to-one blue line. No significant overall increase in BCS after treatment (non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test p-value = 0.412). B) BCS difference per subject bar plot. An increase in BCS following treatment was seen in 3 goats, while BCS decreased in 3. No BCS difference was observed in 16 out of 22 goats evaluated.

Figure 3.13. BCS variation in sheep during pre-and post-praziquantel study. A) Paired BCS (post- vs pre-PZQ) scatter plot with one-to-one blue line. Significant overall increase in BCS after treatment (non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test p-value < 0.001). B) BCS difference per subject bar plot. An increase in BCS following treatment was seen in 15 sheep, with no BCS difference observed in the remaining 5, out of 20 sheep evaluated.

Further evaluation of the effect of treatment on BCS as well as of additional co-variates was conducted using a type of ordinal logistic regression, mixed-effects ordinal regression, also known as cumulative link mixed models.

Initial per species exploration of the basic cumulative link mixed model (basic CLMM, simulates the fixed effect of treatment plus random effect of animal ID as predictors of BCS) confirmed differences between species. In bovines, the effect of treatment (i.e., pre- vs post-PZQ status) on BCS was highly significant (ANOVA comparison of basic CLMM vs null CLMM, p-value = 0.003) alongside non-significant inter-individual variability (ANOVA comparison of basic CLMM vs fixed CLM without blocking by animal ID, p-value= 0.521). In goats, a non-significant effect of treatment on BCS (p-value = 0.906) was accompanied by significant inter-individual variability (p-value= 0.045). In sheep, both the effect of treatment on BCS ($p < 0.001$) and inter-individual variability (p-value < 0.001) were highly significant.

Basic CLMM results highlighted a significant positive association between treatment and BCS in bovines (B=1.144; SE=0.404; p-value = 0.005; 95% CI = 0.352 to 1.936) and sheep (B=16.48; SE=4.50; p-value < 0.001 ; 95% CI = 7.656 to 25.295), likened to a higher likelihood of moving into any next-highest-ordered BCS category after treatment. A summary of results per ruminant species of the two-sample paired ordinal test, basic CLMM model is presented in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3. Basic cumulative link mixed model (CLMM) evaluating the effect of praziquantel treatment on body condition score in domestic ruminants.

Basic CLMM for bovines (n=54)					
AIC: 263.05; Variance animal ID (Intercept): 0.338					
Regression coefficient		Estimate	SE	z value	Pr (> z)
		1.1436	0.4041	2.83	0.005**
Threshold coefficients	Ordered BCS	Estimate	SE	z value	
	1.5 2	-3.7231	0.7725	-4.819	
	2 2.5	-0.6090	0.3089	-1.971	
	2.5 3	2.1474	0.4167	5.153	
	3 3.5	3.5199	0.5637	6.245	
Basic CLMM for goats (n=22)					
AIC: 65.81; Variance animal ID (Intercept): 23.76					
Regression coefficient		Estimate	SE	z value	Pr (> z)
		0.1297	0.9969	0.13	0.897
Threshold coefficients	Ordered BCS	Estimate	SE	z value	
	1.5 2	-7.810	2.272	-3.437	
	2 2.5	-4.971	1.758	-2.828	
	2.5 3	7.449	2.270	3.282	
Basic CLMM for sheep (n=20)					
AIC: 54.71; Variance animal ID (Intercept): 190.8					
Regression coefficient		Estimate	SE	z value	Pr (> z)
		16.48	4.50	3.661	<0.001**
Threshold coefficients	Ordered BCS	Estimate	SE	z value	
	1.5 2	-13.180	4.344	-3.034	
	2 2.5	8.672	2.869	3.023	
	2.5 3	32.198	9.913	3.248	

**Significance $p < 0.01$. Abbreviations: CLMM, cumulative link mixed model; n, number of animals; AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; SE, standard error; BCS, body condition score.

Treatment had no overall effect on the BCS of goats, while in sheep and bovines, treatment improved BCS.

Lastly, a closer look at individual animals (per ruminant species) for which BCS was reduced, flagged a reduction in BCS post-PZQ amongst bovines (Figure 3.11 B) and goats (Figure 3.12 B), however, such reduction was not observed in sheep (Figure 3.13 B). The proportion of animals that cleared the infection among those with decreased, unchanged, and increased BCS post-PZQ was respectively 88.89% (8/9), 76.47% (13/17) and 92.86% (26/28) in bovines; and 0% (0/3), 56.25% (9/16) and 33.33% (1/3) in goats. The proportion of sheep that cleared infection among those with unchanged and increased BCS post-treatment was 20.0% (1/5) and 13.33% (2/15). No association between clearance and a decreased BCS post-PZQ (i.e., negative BCS difference) was found in bovines (Fisher's exact test p-value = 1) nor goats (Fisher's exact test p-value = 0.221).

3.5. Discussion

3.5.1. Variation in PZQ efficacy and treatment response

In the context of revised human schistosomiasis elimination efforts, control interventions in *Schistosoma* spp. animal reservoirs of SSA have been recently considered (5, 6, 10), and recognition of livestock ruminants as key maintenance hosts within a zoonotic schistosomiasis hotspot in Senegal has been attained (18, 19). Motivated by the lack of standardised estimates of PZQ efficacy for the treatment of livestock schistosomiasis (102, 177), preliminary values of PZQ efficacy against schistosomes sampled from Senegalese livestock were presented in this chapter, per village and ruminant species (Table 3.2), via MRR calculation (Equation 1). The level of uncertainty of these preliminary efficacy estimates is given by non-parametric block bootstrap confidence intervals which, akin to published work (106), account for pre-and-post MPG correlation of samples from the same study subject.

Striking differences not only on MRR but also on clearance were found amongst ruminant species (Table 3.2), with PZQ being most efficient at reducing viable eggs and clearing infections in bovines. The overall MRR estimate for bovines of 81.53% was not dissimilar to the 90% efficacy estimate used in the previous chapter's bovine test-and-treat (TnT) model (102), and even though the MRR bootstrap confidence interval reflects a level of uncertainty (55.01–94.69), only a single per village MRR was below 90% (i.e., that of Mbane, see Table 3.2). In goats and sheep both MRR and clearance were below 50% (Table 3.2), with a 'rebound' effect seen in both species post-PZQ (Figure 3.3 and 3.4). Previous reports in humans have stated PZQ efficacy against schistosomes is dependent on intensity of infection (159). Coincidentally, small ruminants had the highest number of counted miracidia among all study animals (Table 3.1).

Both age and co-infection with other parasites (in this case, either *Fasciola* spp and/or *Strongyle* nematodes) were graphically explored as potential factors associated with differential response to

treatment in ruminants. In bovines there was no discernible effect of age in treatment response (Figure 3.5) whereas in small ruminants (Figure 3.6 and 3.7), a differing response was observed between age groups, although most recruited small ruminants were in fact in the older age group. In older goats, treatment had no effect on infection intensity while in the few younger goats it did reduce it (Figure 3.6). In older sheep, intensity of infection tripled after treatment while in younger sheep treatment had no overall effect (Figure 3.7). A more even distribution of age categories in larger future studies is recommended to allow for evaluation of age as potential explanatory factor. Interestingly, a differing response to treatment was noted by co-infection status among bovines (Figure 3.8) and sheep (Figure 3.10). In bovines, co-infection had a seemingly protective effect (i.e., infection intensity reduction among co-infected after treatment (Figure 3.8)). In sheep, while co-infection was not protective, a notable rebound in infection intensity was seen after treatment among not co-infected (Figure 3.10). Notably, an effect on schistosome fecundity has been recently reported in bile export pump-knockout mice, where an increase in serum bile acids and lower blood pH were associated with a reduction of *S. mansoni* fecundity and milder symptoms, when compared to wild type mice (186). Hypothetically, a change in bile acids composition and/or density-dependent fecundity resulting from resource competition, host's immune response, or parasite interactions (187), may explain the suggested contrasting response to treatment in co-infected cattle and sheep vs not co-infected. The reproducibility of this finding and its possible causes should be explored in future studies.

An unexpected further finding was that BCS significantly improved post-PZQ not only among bovines (Figure 3.11) but also among sheep (Figure 3.13). The ordinal models applied to both ruminant species (bovines and sheep) ratified treatment as a significant predictor of BCS (Table 3.3). Such counterintuitive post-PZQ improvement in BCS among sheep despite an abysmal MRR (MRR % = -167.19, see Table 3.2) and less than a quarter of subjects clearing the infection, might be only partially explained by PZQ's activity against cestodes such as *Moniezia expansa* which have been reported in Senegal (178). This perplexing finding (i.e., improved BCS in sheep) deserves further exploration. A similar effect to that of antibiotics (particularly ionophores) which have been used as feed efficiency enhancers/growth promoters (179, 180) could perhaps offer an alternative explanation.

Standard categories of intensity of infection in human schistosomiasis have been established (20). A similar approach was attempted for the livestock schistosomiasis causative species present in the study area (i.e., *S. bovis* and *S. curassoni*) nonetheless, the single intensity categorisation found for livestock (181), dealt with EPG of a notoriously more prolific Asian species (*S. japonicum*) (182, 183). In that publication, the infection intensity in 5 grams of stool collected from cattle and buffaloes of the Philippines was categorised as light (1-100 eggs), moderate (101-400) and heavy (>400) (181). Consequently, application of this categorisation to data from livestock (cattle and small ruminants) naturally infected by less fecund African schistosomes was decided against—comparative mean numbers of uterine eggs for *S. bovis*, *S. curassoni* and *S. japonicum* are respectively, 29, 50 and 161 (23). Therefore, the present work used MPG instead of EPG as a more accurate measure of infection burden/intensity of infection in domestic ruminants. However, the future development of standard

categories of infection intensity specific for livestock schistosomiasis in SSA, could assist in the monitoring of control interventions, such as the bovine schistosomiasis TnT strategy simulated in the previous chapter (Chapter 2) (102).

3.5.2. Livestock schistosomiasis treatment must be optimised

Previous studies in livestock have reported a successful therapeutic effect of two doses of praziquantel (23, 184, 185), either as a combination product (185) or singly (184). For instance, a flock of 104 Indian sheep showing diarrhoea and gradual emaciation, confirmed infected with *S. indicum* were treated twice in a 21-day interval with a veterinary product (Fenta plus®, Fenbendazole 1.5% w/v and Praziquantel 0.5% w/v)(185). Authors reported declining FEC 15 days after the first dose, and no eggs 10 days after the second dose, in conjunction with clinical improvement. Nevertheless, because the dosing of the combination product was set to the dose of Fenbendazole, noteworthy underdosing of PZQ ensued. Furthermore, the short follow-up period may have meant remnant eggs in tissues slowly released after treatment, were undistinguishable from freshly laid eggs (144, 185). In another study, four 9-month-old Sudanese zebu calves, experimentally infected with thousands of *S. bovis* cercaria (10,000 percutaneously), were treated twice with 20 mg/kg of human PZQ (Biltricide ®) in a 5-week interval (at 9 and 14 weeks post-infection (wpi)), and kept under experimental conditions for the duration of the study, ruling out reinfection (184). Weekly FEC evaluations showed non-zero egg counts from 6 wpi and negative FECs in all animals (n=4), 4 weeks after the first dose and 2 after the second (184). Authors counted live worms perfused at 16 wpi and compared the number recovered from treated vs untreated infected controls, reporting a 98.9% reduction (184). Nonetheless, at 16 wpi two treated bovines had several live worms—one of them 7 (2 female worms and 5 male) and another 121 (1 female and 120 male) (184) (i.e., non-patent infections. Note the pre-patent period of *S. bovis* is ~41 days (23)). Thus, despite the significant decrease in FECs, 50% of the treated could be re-classified as non-responders to PZQ treatment. The latter non-patent infections were evidenced only with a direct diagnostic post-mortem, in contrast to commonly used indirect diagnostics.

11 non-responder bovines were identified in three of the 5 recruited villages analysed here: 2 in Djidièry, 5 in Mbane, and 4 in Ndombo. The schistosomes recovered from these non-responder bovines in 2018, were subsequently analysed with molecular methods. A recount of the resulting molecular and population genetics analyses is given in the next chapter (Chapter 4). Notably, two of the 3 villages which had non-responder bovines in the present study, namely Djidièry and Mbane, had a ≥90% prevalence of bovine schistosomiasis in 2017 (102). The Bayesian approach used to estimate these high prevalence levels was described in the previous chapter (Chapter 2).

Interestingly, Mbane, located in the shores of lake Lac de Guiers, presented the highest intensity of infection post-PZQ among all bovine villages despite having the lowest baseline pre-PZQ intensity (Table 3.1). The single distinctly inefficacious response to PZQ mentioned above (below 90% MRR for

bovines), was recorded in this location (MRR % = 11.77, see Table 3.2). Indeed, per village MRR estimates in Mbane were 7.835-fold lower than in Djidiéry, where most recruited bovines were located. Given concerns among local farmers regarding livestock schistosomiasis and the documented misuse of human PZQ to treat their animals (35), as well as the in-country availability of veterinary formulations limited at the time to combined products which lead to underdosing, an effort was made to import and treat recruited SRB ruminants with a PZQ only veterinary formulation at the recommended dose of 25 mg/kg (23). Nonetheless, since the 2018 fieldwork for the pre- and post-PZQ study took place, dose recommendations for cattle have been updated to 30 mg/kg (186). Moreover, a recent small longitudinal study (n=8) treated *Schistosoma* spp. infected Malawian cattle with 40 mg/kg of PZQ (human formula) (187, 188). Despite 0% prevalence by MHT maintained between week 1 and 4 after treatment, a rise to 12.5% and 75% prevalence was recorded by week 6 and 8, respectively due to rapid re-infection (187).

Therefore, building upon the findings presented here, future studies should use a higher than 25 mg/kg dose of veterinary PZQ—at least to 30 mg/kg for cattle (186), plus a second dose of treatment in agreement with others (23, 184). Additionally, multiple days of pre- and post-PZQ sampling to reflect egg output variation (144) are recommended, as well as a bigger sample size with a more even sex and age distribution. The latter changes may reflect both parasite overdispersion (102, 139, 142) and naturally occurring infection intensity variation with host age observations (23). Thus, the potential for developing age-prevalence curves for livestock schistosomiasis, akin to classical human curves (140) exists. It is advised both the MHT diagnostic and the MRR (complementing clearance) methodology used here are maintained, given the higher sensitivity of the former in comparison to FEC (136), and the more representative nature of the latter in evaluating efficacy of the drug to counteract viable infections.

Finally, the negative impact of several factors known to affect the assessment of anthelmintic drug efficacy (144) was reduced during the pre- and post-PZQ study. For instance, instead of choosing previously used FEC for the statistical analysis of collected data (144), an appropriate efficacy indicator such as MRR (Equation 1) was selected. The use of a good quality veterinary product, which was appropriately dosed increased confidence in the drug regimen (144). The negative impact of some factors inherent to the parasite (144), was reduced by the choice of follow-up timing (i.e., slow release of remnant eggs in tissues) and the use of MHT as diagnostic (i.e., non-viable eggs are not counted). Nevertheless, other factors inherent to the parasite could not be avoided including density-dependent fecundity, day-to-day variation in egg excretion and the poor efficacy of PZQ against immature schistosomes (144). Confounding factors such as changes in accuracy of the diagnostic test linked to changes in staff were only partially avoided by ensuring that the same assessors who undertook the BCS evaluation also conducted the MHT. Importantly, confounders inherent to the host (144), which might explain the disparate response to treatment recorded among the three domestic ruminant species, must be considered in future studies to discern potential factors that affect drug absorption and bioavailability.

3.6. Conclusion

The methodological approach applied here for the statistical assessment of PZQ efficacy against livestock schistosomiasis in SRB, represents a significant preliminary step towards a standardized measurement of PZQ efficacy in domestic ruminants of SSA. An outstanding need to optimise the schistosome treatment dose for each domestic ruminant species was nonetheless identified. It is not clear whether the differential response to treatment among domestic ruminants detected here is intrinsic to the host and/or the schistosome species infecting them. Clarification of the latter and other questions raised in this study could be achieved with larger and well-designed future drug efficacy studies which ideally include some of recommendations highlighted here. The work presented in this chapter (and in the previous chapters) contributes to One Health, an approach needed to reach elimination of this disease as a public health problem.

CHAPTER 4

Disentangling schistosomiasis population genetics before and after praziquantel treatment of infected bovines from the Senegal River Basin

4.1. Summary

The importance of schistosomiasis animal reservoirs for reaching the latest World Health Organization (WHO) elimination goals has been acknowledged for sub-Saharan Africa. The highest burden of human schistosomiasis is found in this region, alongside a substantial veterinary and economic impact from livestock infection. Hybridisation between livestock schistosomes and human urogenital species is common, with cattle identified as the primary zoonotic reservoir in Senegal. In the context of newly revised WHO elimination measures, previous chapters have explored a bovine schistosomiasis test-and-treat strategy and the effect of praziquantel treatment among schistosome infected livestock from Senegal. Accordingly, this chapter details population genetic analyses conducted on parasites collected from the latter. Based on *S. bovis* population genetics published literature regarding adult worms recovered from slaughtered bovines, the present study evaluated for the very first time, miracidia recovered from live bovines. The optimisation of a multi-locus microsatellite PCR assay for larval *Schistosoma* spp. from cattle is detailed here, as is a subsequent bioinformatics pipeline of genotyping analyses used to uncover its genetic population structure. Resulting insights about the within and between host genetic variability among samples from three Senegal River Basin villages with distinct praziquantel performance, are presented.

4.2. Introduction

Schistosomiasis is among the most important neglected tropical diseases (NTD) in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (9, 12, 96), a region estimated to accumulate 90% of global human schistosome infections (9). Six of the known 23 *Schistosoma* species are considered medically important with research overwhelmingly conducted on *S. mansoni*, cause of intestinal schistosomiasis, and *S. haematobium*, cause of urogenital schistosomiasis (96). Consequently, molecular studies on the population structure of schistosomes have tended to focus almost exclusively on the human host (96). However, with the recent all-important recognition by the World Health Organization (WHO) that livestock schistosomiasis in SSA has veterinary, socio-economic and public health relevance—particularly to the likelihood of achieving the 2030 elimination goals (5, 6)—is a fillip to elucidate the role of domestic ruminants in transmission using population genetics.

In SSA, the ruminant-associated schistosome species, *S. bovis*, *S. curassoni* and *S. mattheei*, are prevalent (23, 40). Notably, within the Senegal River Basin (SRB)—an area explored in previous chapters, cattle infections are predominantly caused by *S. bovis* (18), and around 70% of infected children and 88% of infected adults shed *S. bovis* hybrids (18).

Indeed, the need for uncovering the population structure of schistosomes infecting African livestock has been underlined in a recent review (96). *S. bovis* population genetics literature is nevertheless scarce, with a single study focused on *S. bovis* from cattle in Cameroon (189), and an SRB human and cattle epidemiological study analysing the population differentiation between *S. haematobium* and *S. bovis* (190). Both studies used a *S. haematobium* multi-locus PCR (191) with which, 218 worms from 22 Cameroonian cows (189) and 62 worms from 4 Senegalese cows (190) were evaluated. 14 out of the 18 loci were successfully amplified in the former study (189), and 11 out of 16 in the latter (190). Thereby, both studies applied microsatellite markers to characterise the population genetic structure of adult schistosomes collected at abattoir from cattle.

Microsatellites are very short, repetitive, and ubiquitous sequences—mainly found in the non-coding DNA of eukaryotes, which have high mutation rates and thus, high diversity (192, 193). Also known as short tandem repeats (STRs) or simple sequence repeats (SSRs), microsatellites are usually composed of di- or three nucleotide repeats and occur because of slippage during DNA replication or recombination (192). Hypervariability in the number of microsatellite-repeats across a given locus can be visualized as differences in length, making them a useful molecular tool to assess genetic variation (192).

Building upon findings from preceding chapters, this chapter focuses on microsatellite molecular work of SRB schistosomes. Previously collected *Schistosoma* spp. miracidia samples hatched from live bovine faeces, were examined for the very first time with the abovementioned multi-locus PCR. Selection criteria and steps to PCR optimisation are described. Subsequent microsatellite fragment length analysis and ensuing genotypic data processing were followed by software analysis with a bioinformatics pipeline. Lastly, population genetic analyses were interpreted to help elucidate the structure of larval schistosome populations, before and after praziquantel treatment of their animal hosts.

4.3. Materials and Methods

The work presented here pertains to miracidia recovered from a subsample of bovines from the pre- and post-praziquantel study described in the last chapter (Chapter 3). More specifically, this chapter focuses on miracidia collected pre- and post-PZQ across the three RT villages where non-responder bovines (i.e., bovines which remained infected despite treatment) were recorded: Djidiéry, Mbane and Ndombo.

4.3.1. Extraction of DNA from miracidia

Following *Schistosoma* spp. egg hatching with a MHT technique described elsewhere (136), free-swimming miracidia were individually pipetted onto Whatman FTA® indicator cards by field teams for cell lysis and DNA storage (194). A maximum target of 50 miracidia were collected for each bovine onto

a single FTA card per time point with a final range of 1-46 pre-PZQ and 0-44 post-PZQ miracidium collected per animal. All the schistosomes isolated from a single host are hereby referred to as an infrapopulation. Genomic DNA (gDNA) was extracted from miracidial samples contained in FTA cards following a published protocol (191). Briefly, each 2.0 mm punch, made with a Harris micro-punch, contained a single larval sample and was incubated in two different elution solutions to obtain eluted DNA. The resulting DNA was stored in labelled 96-well plates at -20 °C for consequent polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification.

A randomly selected subsample of eluted miracidia from the pre- and post-praziquantel study was characterised by others to species-level—before the present doctoral studies took place—via PCR amplification and sequencing, using a fragment of the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (*cox1*) and the complete nuclear ribosomal DNA internal transcribed spacer (ITS) gene motifs, as described elsewhere (18). Of the 329 pre-PZQ miracidial samples from 56 of the 59 bovines analysed in the last chapter, 188 were characterised as *S. bovis* (62.458%). The remainder could not be conclusively characterised (i.e., amplification/sequencing failure). A single post-PZQ miracidia of the 58 evaluated from non-responder bovines was characterised as *S. bovis* (1.724%). Notably, none of the evaluated samples were characterised as *S. curassoni* nor as hybrids. Pre- and post-PZQ *cox1* and ITS results per animal are tabulated in Appendix F1.

4.3.2. Genotyping schistosome DNA

A total of 15 microsatellite loci originally designed for the human-infective species *S. haematobium* but known to also amplify successfully with the closely related species *S. bovis* (189, 190), were assessed. 14 of these markers, namely Sh9, Sh3, C102, Sh1, Sh14, Sh6, C111, Sh13, Sh4, Sh11, Sh15, Sh2, Sh5, Sh12, are detailed by Webster and colleagues (191, 195). The remaining marker Sha_104176_i13, hereby referred to as Sha, is detailed by Boon and colleagues (190). The 15 molecular markers were divided into two multiplex PCR panels in accordance with published *S. bovis* marker distributions (189, 190). A PCR protocol known to work with *S. bovis* worms (189) was initially tested with reference *S. bovis* worm gDNA sourced from the Schistosomiasis “SCAN” collection at the Natural History Museum (196), firstly as a single-plex and then as a multiplex assay. Utility of the assay (i.e., clear bands of the expected size) was confirmed by gel electrophoresis (2% agarose gel ran at 120 volts for 50 minutes), flanking samples with Bionline’s 100 bp HypperLadder® (Bionline Reagents Limited | Meridian Bioscience, London, UK).

Miracidial eluates were amplified with the multiplex assay alongside positive (reference *S. bovis* gDNA) and negative (molecular water) controls. In addition, PCR multiplex amplification of 8 adult worms (4 female-male couples) collected at abattoir during the ZELS project (18) was conducted in conjunction with positive and negative controls. Samples from ZELS hosts recorded as infected with either *S. curassoni*, hybrid and/or a mixture of schistosome species were avoided to reduce the likelihood of selecting non-*S. bovis* worms. Consequently, the 8 worms recovered from two RT infected bovines were

eluted following manufacturer instructions, using the DNeasy® Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). The DNA yield of these eluted worms was quantified by nanodrop (DeNovix DS-11 NanoDrop), while accurate measurement of eluted miracidia was achieved with a fluorometer (Invitrogen® Qubit® 4 Fluorometer 1)—due to salt carryover plus lower DNA yield, the nanodrop consistently failed in providing a miracidia DNA reading (DNA yield results are tabulated in Appendix F2).

Microsatellite PCRs were carried out in a SimpliAmp® Thermal Cycler (ThermoFisher Scientific | Applied Biosystems, Warrington, UK), using the Type-it Microsatellite PCR Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), with fluorescently-labelled-forward and unlabelled-reverse primer pairs (ThermoFisher Scientific | Applied Biosystems, Warrington, UK). The multiplex PCR for Amplification of microsatellite loci using Q-solution protocol (Qiagen's December 2009 Type-it® Microsatellite PCR Handbook) was followed, initially using 2.5 µl of DNA template per 12.5 µl reaction, 2 µM of each primer pair and 30 thermal cycles (189). To optimise amplification, the number of cycles was increased to 35, the amount of miracidial DNA template to 3 µl, and the concentration of the Sha primer pair to 4 µM, while the positive control was lowered to 1.5 µl. As evidenced in Figure 4.1, the latter optimised conditions clearly improved amplification. The optimised PCR protocol is detailed in Appendix F3.

Figure 4.1. Microsatellite multiplex PCR optimisation (P1: Panel 1; P2: Panel 2). Gel electrophoresis comparison of sample duplicates (i.e., same samples in top and bottom of 2% agarose gel) amplified with different PCR conditions. Brighter bands observed in the bottom wells show enhanced template amplification. Top wells: 30 thermal cycles, 3.5 µl of miracidia DNA, and 2.5 µl of positive (+ve) control. Bottom wells: 35 cycles, 3 µl miracidia, and 1.5 µl +ve control.

Microsatellite reactions (i.e., amplicons) were diluted in molecular water (1:2 dilution for miracidia DNA and 1:10 for worm DNA), before being sent to Eurofins Genomics Europe (Ebersberg, Germany) for fragment length analysis (FLA) (Applied Biosystems® Genetic Analyzer 3100/3130xl), peak calling and genotype determination with GeneScan® LIZ 500 size standard (GeneMapper Software 5).

12 of the 15 microsatellites were successfully amplified on the tested schistosome samples. Allelic dropout was recorded for loci C102, while C111 and Sh5 were poorly amplified in less than 20% of tested samples, hence these three markers were excluded from the multiplex. Details of the 12 selected microsatellite loci and characteristics of both PCR multiplex assay panels are presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1. Details of the 12 selected microsatellite loci and characteristics of both PCR multiplex assay panels. All loci from Webster et al., 2015 (see erratum) except for Sha from Boon et al., 2019.

Loci	Forward primer 5' - 3'	Reverse primer 5' - 3'	Dye ^a	Observed ^b size range (bp)	Repeat	Djibouty		Mbane		Ndombo	
						Ho	He	Ho	He	Ho	He
Sh9 ¹	GGGATGATGCAGACTTG	TTGTTGGCTGCAGTAAC	6-FAM	187-247	AAT	0.845*	0.811	0.800***	0.792	0.760**	0.767
Sh3 ¹	GCTGAGCTTGAGATTG	CTTCTGTCCCATCGATACC	6-FAM	294-363	AAT	0.891**	0.929	0.869	0.935	0.850	0.926
Sh1 ¹	GCATCCAATTCGTACAC	CCACATTAGGCCAACAAAG	VIC	242-281	AAT	0.983	0.889	0.924	0.908	0.882	0.893
Sh14 ¹	GTCCTCTCCCTCTTTG	CACATTCGTCTAGATATCG	NED	184-248	ACTC	0.877	0.734	0.708	0.657	0.706	0.643
Sh6 ¹	GGTGATTACGCAATAG	TTAATCAACCGGGTGTC	NED	305-326	AAT	0.491***	0.670	0.429***	0.729	0.541	0.742
Sha ¹	TTCTTGACGACTACTTCCAA	CGACAACATACCCACTCTTA	PET	277-342	CT ^c	0.420***	0.786	0.350***	0.756	0.342***	0.679
Sh13 ²	GAGCAGCTATTTCGTATCG	ACCGTGGACAGTTCATCAG	6-FAM	160-226	AAT	0.948	0.913	0.924	0.917	0.960	0.901
Sh4 ²	CCCATCGCTGATATTAAG	TCTAGTCGTCTTGGGATCC	6-FAM	268-316	AAT	0.870	0.888	0.898	0.884	0.830***	0.846
Sh11 ²	TTGGTTAGAAAATACATCAC _C	CCAAACAATTAATGGACAGC	VIC	173-194	ATC	0.605	0.609	0.518	0.637	0.675	0.694
Sh15 ²	CTTTCAGTAGGATTTGTTG	CGACGTCGAAGCACTGTAC	VIC	271-280	ATC	0.268	0.287	0.133*	0.208	0.273	0.241
Sh2 ²	TTAGTGTGTTGGCTTCAAC	CCTCGAATGAAATCCTGAC	NED	151-217	AAT	0.912	0.920	0.859	0.929	0.900***	0.911
Sh12 ²	CGCTTAGTGAGCCAGATG	CTGGTGACATCATCAG	PET	249-261	AAC	0.638	0.578	0.631	0.585	0.588	0.592

Abbreviations: bp, base pairs; Ho, observed heterozygosity; He, expected heterozygosity (Ho & He from pre-PZQ samples only); HWE, Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. ¹ Panel 1 markers. ² Panel 2 markers. ^a Fluorescent-dye label of the forward primer: 6-FAM, blue; VIC, green; NED, yellow; PET, red. ^b Observed for 200 genotyped miracidia (175 pre-PZQ and 25 post-PZQ isolates). ^c Not published. Information shared by the corresponding author (Tine Huyse). HWE departure significance: *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.

Eurofins' FLA raw data processing (i.e., fitting ladders, setting loci and binning microsatellites) was conducted with Geneious prime software (<https://www.geneious.com>) version 2023.1.2. Size range optimisation for loci setting was achieved by computing observed minimum and maximum values from existing *S. bovis* data shared by the corresponding author, Jerome Boissier (189) (see Table 4.2 's third column for values used in loci setting). Given that both miracidia and worm samples persistently presented Sh15 peaks of 271 base pairs (bp), the size range for this locus was extended. In the case of the Sha locus (190), the corresponding author, Tine Huyse, indicated a size of 373 bp. Following size range optimisation of this dinucleotide repeat, a range of 273-373 bp was adopted. A comparison between published size ranges from previous studies and the ranges observed in the present study for the selected microsatellites is presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2. *Schistosoma haematobium* clade inter-species specificity of the optimised two-panel multiplex microsatellite assay. Size range comparison in base pairs.

Loci	Zanzibaris and Nigerien <i>S. haematobium</i> miracidium from children ^a	Cameroonian <i>S. bovis</i> worms from bovines ^b	Senegalese <i>S. bovis</i> from bovines tested during the present work		
			175 Pre-PZQ miracidium (# not amplified)	25 Post-PZQ miracidium (# not amplified)	8 ZELS worms
Sh9	197-227	187-253	187-247 (2)	187-202 (2)	190-199
Sh3	270-366	294-375	294-363 (19)	297-339 (7)	318-342
Sh1	245-284	242-290	242-281 (0)	242-278 (3)	242-269
Sh14	184-240	184-250	184-248 (2)	184-200 (2)	184-192
Sh6	309-321	305-329	305-326 (27)	305-317 (9)	305-308
Sha	N/A	N/A	277-342 (27)	299-315 (9)	299-323
Sh13	163-211	160-232	160-226 (1)	175-217 (3)	175-211
Sh4	268-313	262-316	268-316 (15)	271-304 (4)	277-307
Sh11	183-213	173-194	173-194 (36)	179-191 (13)	179-191
Sh15	274-301	274*- 280	271-280 (15)	274-277 (14)	271-274
Sh2	155-218	148-223	160-217 (4)	151-199 (5)	166-205
Sh12	245-278	249-264	249-261 (1)	249-255 (4)	249-255

Abbreviations: N/A, not applicable. ^a Webster et al, 2015 erratum (195). ^b Djuikwo-Teukeng et al, 2019 (189). *Loci setting range modified during size range optimisation to 271-280.

Financial and logistical restrictions limited the number of miracidia to be genotyped with microsatellites for the present study, thereby, parasites collected from the 11 non-responder bovines of the pre- and post-PZQ study took priority, closely followed by responder bovines from the same 3 RT villages for comparison. Briefly, a subsample of 8 randomly chosen miracidia per selected infrapopulation was initially tested, prioritising isolates freshly eluted by the author and isolates with a *cox1* and/or ITS

positive result. If the initial test was encouraging and more infrapopulation samples were available, ≤8 further miracidia were tested at a time. Isolates with at least 50% of loci amplified for both panels (i.e., minimum 3 positive markers per panel) were considered successfully genotyped. The *S. bovis* *cox1*/ITS characterisation (carried out by others) of successfully genotyped isolates is presented in Table 4.3. Moreover, a summary of the successfully genotyped miracidial isolates by village and treatment status is given in Table 4.4.

Table 4.3. Number of successfully genotyped isolates by village of origin and host treatment status characterised as *S. bovis* by *cox1* and ITS (superscripts distinguish between downstream genotyping analysis performed).

Village	# <i>S. bovis</i> miracidia (# <i>cox1</i> /ITS evaluated miracidia)			# <i>S. bovis</i> among genotyped isolates ^b
	Pre-PZQ ^a	Subset of pre-PZQ ^b	Post-PZQ ^b	
Djidièry	29 (29)	0 (0)	0 (0)	29
Mbane	38 (50) ^c	5 (15) ^d	0 (7) ^e	38
Ndombo	9 (24) ^f	0 (0)	0 (0)	9
Total	76 (103)	5 (15)	0 (6)	77

^a 1st genotyping analysis: pre-PZQ isolates. ^b 2nd genotyping analysis: subset of pre-PZQ vs post-PZQ isolates from 5 non-responder bovines. Results of remaining *cox1*/ITS evaluated miracidia: ^c 12 *cox1* negative and ITS *S. bovis*; ^d 10 *cox1* negative and ITS *S. bovis*; ^e 5 *cox1* negative and ITS *S. bovis*, plus 2 *cox1* and ITS negative; ^f 14 *cox1* negative and ITS *S. bovis*, plus 1 *cox1* and ITS negative.

Table 4.4. Number of successfully genotyped isolates by village of origin and host treatment status (superscripts distinguish between downstream genotyping analysis performed).

Village	# Miracidia isolates (# bovines sampled)			Total # of isolates
	Pre-PZQ ^a	Subset of pre-PZQ ^b	Post-PZQ ^b	
Djidièry	58 (8)	0 (0)	0 (0)	58
Mbane	66 (12)	19 (4)	24 (4)	90
Ndombo	51 (4)	13 (1)	1 (1)	52
Total	175 (24)	32 (5)	25 (5)	200

^a 1st genotyping analysis: pre-PZQ isolates. ^b 2nd genotyping analysis: subset of pre-PZQ vs post-PZQ isolates from 5 non-responder bovines.

4.3.3. Codominant genotypic data analyses

Allele tables (i.e., codominant genotypic data) resulting from raw data processing of successfully genotyped isolates, were used in downstream analyses. Two sets of microsatellite genotyping analyses were conducted to assess genetic diversity, genetic variance, and potential genetic structure. The first set, referred to as pre-PZQ, evaluated successfully amplified pre-PZQ isolates from bovines across three villages: Djidièry, Mbane and Ndombo. The second set, referred to as pre-vs post-PZQ, evaluated successfully amplified isolates from non-responder bovines with both pre-and post-PZQ isolates of two villages: Mbane and Ndombo. Details of the number of schistosome isolates and corresponding definitive hosts per genotyping analysis are presented in Table 4.4 above. Figure 4.2 below summarises work stages carried out by the author (in bold) towards studying the population genetics of bovine-infective schistosomes. The bioinformatics pipeline rectangle (Figure 4.2) depicts steps both sets of genotyping analyses (i.e., pre-PZQ, and pre-vs post-PZQ) have in common.

Figure 4.2. Steps taken to obtain and analyse genotypic data for population genetic studies of schistosomes from Senegalese cattle (In bold, those undertaken by the author). Created with BioRender.com.

Genetic diversity assessment included observed heterozygosity (H_o), expected heterozygosity (H_e), number of alleles (A), allelic richness (A_r) and inbreeding coefficient (F), at each of the 12 selected microsatellite loci, using version 6.5b of the Microsoft Excel package *GenAlEx* (197, 198). Differences

in genetic diversity estimates between populations of the pre-PZQ analysis were evaluated using pairwise Friedman rank tests followed by pairwise Wilcoxon rank sum tests with Bonferroni correction if significance was found, while Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were used for the pre-vs post-PZQ analysis. Statistical tests were paired by locus. Additional estimates computed in *GenAlEx* such as number of private alleles (A_p), and Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium summary of Chi-squared are presented on the chapter appendices (Appendix F4 and F5). Ar computation was conducted with the “allelic.richness” function of the *hierfstat* R package (199) version 0.5.11, using a rarefaction method to standardise unequal samples to the same sample size. The latter was set to the smallest sample size among evaluated populations per corresponding analysis (i.e., “min.n” argument of the “allelic.richness” function set respectively to 74 and 24, based on the minimum sample size (N) value across markers indicated in Tables 4.5 and 4.6, multiplied by two due to diploidy). Moreover, the genetic differentiation between villages in the case of the pre-PZQ genotyping analysis, and between treatment status in the case of the pre-vs post-PZQ genotyping analysis, was assessed using pairwise F_{st} calculated via the frequency option with *GenAlEx*. Additional genetic differentiation estimates such as unbiased Nei genetic distance (NeiD) and unbiased Nei genetic identity (NeiI) were also computed with *GenAlEx*.

Genetic variance assessment was performed via analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) using the “poppr.amova” function of the *poppr* package (200, 201) version 2.9.6 in R with “ade4” method, “quasieuclid” correction, without removing loci nor isolates in case of missing data. Considering each village as a population, three hierarchical levels of genetic variance amongst pre-PZQ isolates were evaluated: i) among populations; ii) among animals within population; and iii) within animals. In the case of the pre- vs post-PZQ analysis, four hierarchical levels were evaluated: i) among populations; ii) among animals within population; iii) among treatment status within animals; and iv) within treatment status. Subsequent significance testing was carried out with a randomization test using the “randtest” function of the *ade4* R package (202, 203) version 1.7.22.

Potential genetic structure among isolates was assessed using a principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) implemented in *GenAlEx*. Finally, to establish the uppermost hierarchy of population structure, a Bayesian clustering approach was implemented using version 2.3.4 of the software STRUCTURE (204, 205). Thereby, the number of clusters (K) were tested from K=1 to K=10 with 20 runs per K. For the pre-PZQ genotyping analysis, 100,000 iterations after a burn-in period of 100,000 were computed using an admixture model and other parameters set to default. In the case of the pre- vs post-PZQ genotyping analysis, 1,000,000 iterations after a burn-in period of 250,000 were computed. STRUCTURE results were uploaded into the web-based software STRUCTURESELECTOR (206) to select the best K estimate based on Delta K values, using the Evanno method (207). Genetic population structure graphs were generated in STRUCTURESELECTOR to visualize genetic clusters after verifying convergence in Clumpak (208).

4.4. Results

4.4.1. Microsatellite multiplex PCR optimisation

Given that miracidia are far smaller than schistosome adults— 150 μm vs 7-20 mm long among human-infective species (209), it was to be expected that DNA extractions of the former would yield far less DNA than worm extractions. Indeed, among the samples for which DNA was quantified (tabulated per sample values in Appendix F2), the pre-PZQ miracidia DNA yield ($\text{ng}/\mu\text{l}$) was at least 70.592-fold smaller in comparison to female worms and at least 107.485-fold smaller in comparison to males —females are longer but slenderer than males. *S. bovis* female length 13-44 mm (23). Thus, the published PCR protocol originally developed for worms (189) was optimised for miracidia by increasing both the amount of DNA template and the number of thermal cycles in the multiplex.

4.4.2. Genotyped schistosome DNA

As indicated in Table 4.4 above, 175 pre-PZQ isolates collected from 24 bovines of three Senegalese villages were successfully genotyped, whereas 25 post-PZQ isolates collected from 5 bovines of two Senegalese villages were successfully genotyped. Among these genotyped isolates, 76 of the pre-PZQ and none of the post-PZQ were previously characterised as *S. bovis* (see Table 4.3 above). The tally of tested but not successfully genotyped samples (i.e., with less than 3 markers amplified per panel) was 43 pre-PZQ from 15 bovines and 31 post-PZQ from 9 bovines of the three Senegalese villages. Specifically, 10 pre-PZQ samples from 6 bovines had amplification of at least 1 marker from either panel, while the remaining 33 samples had no marker amplification (most likely caused by miracidia collection failure). 12 post-PZQ samples from 6 bovines had amplification of at least 1 marker from either panel while the remaining 19 samples had no amplification.

4.4.3. Microsatellite codominant genotypic data analyses

4.4.3.1. Genetic diversity by genotyping analysis

Standard genetic diversity indexes (He, A, Ar, and F) of the pre-PZQ analysis are presented in Table 4.5, while Ho and He are presented side-by-side in Table 4.1. At 0.05 significance, a difference between populations of the three analysed villages was observed for Ho ($X^2 = 6.167$; $df = 2$; $p\text{-value} = 0.046$)—particularly between Djidièry and Mbane ($p\text{-value} = 0.01$), in addition to a difference for F ($X^2 = 8.667$; $df = 2$; $p\text{-value} = 0.013$)—specifically between Djidièry and Mbane ($p\text{-value} = 0.026$). No difference between villages was observed for He ($X^2 = 2.167$; $df = 2$; $p\text{-value} = 0.339$), A ($X^2 = 3.405$; $df = 2$; $p\text{-value} = 0.182$), Ar ($X^2 = 2$; $df = 2$; $p\text{-value} = 0.368$), nor Ap ($X^2 = 0.800$; $df = 2$; $p\text{-value} = 0.670$) (Ap pre-PZQ value in Appendix F4). Ho and Ap of the pre-vs post-PZQ analysis are tabulated in Appendix F5, while standard genetic diversity indexes (He, A, Ar, and F) are presented in Table 4.6. No difference between populations by treatment status were observed for Ho ($V = 15$; $p\text{-value} = 0.065$), He ($V = 29.5$; $p\text{-value} = 0.48$), A ($V = 36$; $p\text{-value} = 0.408$), Ar ($V = 61$; $p\text{-value} = 0.092$), F ($V = 63$; $p\text{-value} = 0.065$), nor Ap ($V = 29$; $p\text{-value} = 0.473$).

Table 4.5. Expected heterozygosity (He), number of alleles (A), sample size (N), Allelic richness (Ar), and Fixation index or inbreeding coefficient (F) per loci of pre-PZQ schistosome isolates by location. Allelic richness is based on a minimum of 37 diploid isolates.

Loci	Djidiéry (n=58)			Mbane (n=66)			Ndombo (n=51)			Overall (n=175)						
	He	A (N)	Ar	F	He	A (N)	Ar	F	He	A (N)	Ar	F	Ht	A	Ar	Fst
Sh9	0.811	14 (58)	12.339	-0.041	0.792	14 (65)	12.811	-0.010	0.767	12 (50)	11.913	0.009	0.794	13.333	12.630	0.005
Sh3	0.929	20 (55)	19.258	0.041	0.935	21 (61)	20.358	0.070	0.926	18 (40)	17.768	0.082	0.936	19.667	20.035	0.007
Sh1	0.889	14 (58)	13.437	-0.106	0.908	14 (66)	13.467	-0.018	0.893	13 (51)	12.504	0.012	0.904	13.667	13.093	0.008
Sh14	0.734	6 (57)	6.613	-0.194	0.657	9 (65)	8.258	-0.077	0.643	5 (51)	4.926	-0.098	0.685	6.667	6.780	0.010
Sh6	0.670	5 (55)	5.864	0.268	0.729	7 (56)	7.038	0.412	0.742	5 (37)	5.725	0.272	0.724	5.667	6.438	0.015
Sha	0.786	18 (50)	16.387	0.466	0.756	13 (60)	12.142	0.537	0.679	12 (38)	11.402	0.496	0.751	14.333	14.033	0.014
Sh13	0.913	18 (58)	16.377	-0.039	0.917	18 (66)	16.191	-0.008	0.901	19 (50)	18.394	-0.065	0.919	18.333	17.169	0.009
Sh4	0.888	15 (54)	15.210	0.020	0.884	13 (59)	13.208	-0.017	0.846	16 (47)	15.652	0.019	0.878	14.667	14.415	0.006
Sh11	0.609	8 (43)	7.907	0.008	0.637	7 (56)	7.533	0.187	0.694	7 (40)	7.579	0.027	0.653	7.333	7.533	0.009
Sh15	0.287	3 (56)	3.855	0.067	0.208	3 (60)	3.561	0.359	0.241	3 (44)	3.927	-0.133	0.246	3.000	3.826	0.004
Sh2	0.920	19 (57)	18.788	0.009	0.929	19 (64)	18.578	0.075	0.911	17 (50)	16.538	0.012	0.927	18.333	17.927	0.008
Sh12	0.578	3 (58)	3.000	-0.103	0.585	4 (65)	4.726	-0.079	0.592	4 (51)	3.725	0.006	0.586	3.667	4.101	0.001
Mean	0.751	11.917	11.586	0.033	0.745	11.833	11.489	0.119	0.736	10.917	10.838	0.053	0.750	11.556	11.498	0.008
SE	0.055	1.877	1.693	0.051	0.060	1.696	1.544	0.060	0.056	1.699	1.593	0.050	0.057	0.989	1.610	0.001

Abbreviations: n, number of analysed isolates; SE, standard error of the mean; Ht, total expected heterozygosity; Fst, effect on F of subpopulations compared to the overall total population.

Table 4.6. Expected heterozygosity (He), number of alleles (A), sample size (N), Allelic richness (Ar), and Fixation index or inbreeding coefficient (F) per loci of schistosome isolates by treatment status. Allelic richness is based on a minimum of 12 diploid isolates.

Loci	Pre-PZQ (n=32)				Post-PZQ (n=25)				Overall (n=57)			
	He	A (N)	Ar	F	He	A (N)	Ar	F	Ht	A	Ar	Fst
Sh9	0.752	10 (30)	7.987	0.069	0.782	9 (24)	6.186	0.148	0.771	9.500	7.482	0.005
Sh3	0.911	18 (24)	12.661	0.314	0.912	15 (17)	10.402	0.226	0.924	16.500	11.744	0.014
Sh1	0.891	12 (30)	10.481	0.177	0.874	12 (24)	10.481	0.047	0.897	12.000	10.776	0.016
Sh14	0.653	7 (32)	5.037	0.330	0.699	6 (23)	5.280	0.005	0.684	6.500	5.521	0.011
Sh6	0.690	5 (24)	5.117	0.517	0.642	4 (12)	5.208	0.611	0.706	4.500	5.087	0.057
Sha	0.701	6 (23)	5.919	0.690	0.766	8 (20)	6.194	0.674	0.740	7.000	6.298	0.008
Sh13	0.870	13 (29)	12.014	0.167	0.899	15 (24)	9.930	0.073	0.900	14.000	11.328	0.017
Sh4	0.878	12 (29)	9.441	0.293	0.775	9 (20)	9.659	0.355	0.855	10.500	9.475	0.033
Sh11	0.578	5 (17)	5.649	0.389	0.613	6 (15)	3.466	0.130	0.599	5.500	4.751	0.005
Sh15	0.239	2 (18)	3.289	0.768	0.238	3 (15)	2.867	-0.121	0.239	2.500	3.070	0.003
Sh2	0.924	18 (29)	13.595	0.366	0.900	13 (22)	11.684	0.141	0.919	15.500	12.893	0.008
Sh12	0.579	4 (30)	4.196	0.021	0.638	4 (22)	3.966	0.074	0.612	4.000	4.245	0.005
Mean	0.722	9.333	7.949	0.342	0.728	8.667	7.110	0.197	0.737	9.000	7.722	0.015
SE	0.057	1.544	1.033	0.066	0.054	1.233	0.902	0.069	0.057	0.969	0.972	0.004

Abbreviations: n, number of analysed isolates; SE, standard error of the mean; Ht, total expected heterozygosity; Fst, effect on F of subpopulations compared to the overall total population.

Notably, the across loci fixation index for Mbane was approximately twice that of Ndombo and almost four (4) times that of Djidièry, indicating a higher degree of inbreeding present in Mbane. The per loci fixation index highlighted the Sha locus in Djidièry ($F = 0.471$), Mbane ($F = 0.537$) and Ndombo ($F = 0.496$) for partial inbreeding (i.e., $F = 0.5$) even though the percentage of missing data (i.e., no amplification) for this locus was respectively 13, 9 and 25%. The same locus was also highlighted with other related overall (i.e., across villages) F-statistics of inbreeding ($F_{is} = 0.501$; $F_{it} = 0.508$).

Allelic patterns pre-PZQ in the villages of Djidièry ($n=58$), Mbane ($n=66$) and Ndombo ($n=51$) are depicted in Figure 4.3. Comparison across the three villages suggested non-significant trends for lower mean allele number (i.e., total number of alleles divided by the corresponding number of evaluated loci) (Djidièry = 11.917; Mbane = 11.833; Ndombo = 10.917), and (expected) heterozygosity (Djidièry = 0.751; Mbane = 0.745; Ndombo = 0.736)—including unbiased heterozygosity corrected for sample size (Djidièry = 0.758; Mbane = 0.751; Ndombo = 0.744). In contrast, a non-significant trend for higher mean number of private alleles was observed (Djidièry = 0.750; Mbane = 0.833; Ndombo = 0.917).

Figure 4.3. Allelic patterns across populations of the pre-PZQ analysis. Abbreviations: DB, Djidièry; MB, Mbane; NB, Ndombo; Na, number of alleles; No, number of; He, expected heterozygosity.

Pairwise F_{st} comparison (Table 4.7 A) among populations for the pre-PZQ analysis found less than 1% variation between village pairs. The least similar villages were Djidièry and Ndombo which had 0.8% variation between them. The dissimilarity between these two villages is corroborated by having both the highest pairwise genetic distance ($NeiuD = 0.019$, Table 4.8 A) and the lowest pairwise genetic identity ($NeiuI = 0.982$, Table 4.8 A). The remaining village pairs had the same pairwise F_{st} value (0.5% variation), although Mbane and Ndombo were more genetically similar (lowest pairwise genetic distance and highest pairwise genetic identity, see Table 4.8 A).

A higher pairwise F_{st} value was found in the pre- vs post-PZQ analysis (Table 4.7 B), with 1.5% variation when comparing populations by treatment status, which was ratified by a higher pairwise genetic distance ($NeiuD = 0.028$, Table 4.8 B) and lower pairwise genetic identity ($NeiuI = 0.973$, Table 4.8 B).

Table 4.7. Pairwise population Fst values (below the diagonal) of schistosome isolates in both genotyping analyses.

A) Pre-PZQ	Djidièry	Mbane	Ndombo
Djidièry	-		
Mbane	0.005	-	
Ndombo	0.008	0.005	-

B) Pre- vs post-PZQ	Pre-PZQ	Post-PZQ
Pre-PZQ	-	
Post-PZQ	0.015	-

Table 4.8. Pairwise population unbiased Nei genetic distance (NeiuD) and unbiased Nei genetic identity (NeiuI) values of schistosome isolates in both genotyping analyses.

A) Pre-PZQ	Population 1	Population 2	NeiuD	NeiuI
	Djidièry	Mbane	0.005	0.995
	Djidièry	Ndombo	0.019	0.982
	Mbane	Ndombo	0.003	0.997

B) Pre- vs post-PZQ	Population 1	Population 2	NeiuD	NeiuI
	Pre-PZQ	Post-PZQ	0.028	0.973

4.4.3.2. Genetic variance by genotyping analysis

In the pre-PZQ AMOVA analysis (Table 4.9 A), 99% of the genetic variation was observed within hosts, with less than 1% of the variation found between animals and villages (each village is considered a population). In the pre-vs post-PZQ AMOVA analysis (Table 4.9 B), 97% of the genetic variation was observed within treatment status and just above 1% between treatment status within animals, with less than 1% of the variation found between animals or between villages. Significance testing over 999 permutations indicated no significant population differentiation at all hierarchical levels of the pre-PZQ analysis (p-values: between villages = 0.125; between animals = 0.141; within animals = 0.076), nor of the pre-vs post-PZQ analysis (p-values: between villages = 0.388; between animals = 0.276; between treatment status = 0.366; within treatment status = 0.076).

Table 4.9. Analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) within and among schistosome populations by genotyping analysis.

A) Pre-PZQ	df	Sum of squares	Variance components (sigma)	% of variation
Among populations	2	12.352	0.011	0.202
Among animals within population	21	113.551	0.037	0.702
Within animals	151	779.120	5.160	99.096
Total	174	905.023	5.207	

B) Pre-vs post-PZQ	df	Sum of squares	Variance components (sigma)	% of variation
Among populations	1	8.407	0.0513	0.837
Among animals within population	3	20.516	0.0413	0.675
Among treatment status within animal	5	31.315	0.0754	1.230
Within treatment status	47	279.965	5.957	97.258
Total	56	340.204	6.125	

4.4.3.3. Genetic structure by genotyping analysis

Less than 20% of the variation was explained in the first two axes of the PCoA plots for both genotyping analyses: 12.45% for the pre-PZQ analysis by village (Figure 4.4); and 17.65% for the pre-vs post-PZQ analysis (Figure 4.5).

Figure 4.4. Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) plot of pre-PZQ genotyping analysis. Each genotyped isolate is represented by a coloured geometric shape. Blue rhombi are isolates from Djidièry (DB), orange rectangles from Mbane (MB) and grey triangles from Ndombo (NB). The first and second axis explained respectively, 6.66% and 5.79% of the genetic variation.

Figure 4.5. Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) plot of pre- (pr) vs post- (po) PZQ genotyping analysis. Blue rhombi are pre-PZQ isolates while orange rectangles are post-PZQ isolates. The first and second axis explained respectively, 10.49% and 7.16% of the genetic variation.

Further evaluation of potential genetic structure with a Bayesian clustering approach identified four genetic clusters (K=4) with the Evanno method in the case of the pre-PZQ analysis. This best K choice (based on delta K plot, see plot in Appendix F6) was verified via simulation convergence in Clumpak (number of concordant runs by major mode = 18/20; mean similarity score = 0.942). The genetic population structure among pre-PZQ isolates for the best K estimate is plotted in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6. Genetic population structure of Senegal River Basin *Schistosoma* spp. sampled from cattle before PZQ treatment. Tilted numbers underneath the graph correspond to village: 1) Djidière; 2) Mbane; and 3) Ndombo. Vertical lines divide these three populations. Dashed vertical lines divide infrapopulations (i.e., samples per animal) with corresponding animal identifiers inside the black-border rectangles. Within infrapopulations, each coloured rectangular bar corresponds to a genotyped parasite. Four genetic clusters (K=4) were identified with the Evanno method.

In pre- vs post-PZQ analysis, only two genetic clusters (K=2) were identified with the Evanno method. Convergence of simulations associated to this best K (see corresponding delta K plot in Appendix F7), was verified in Clumpak (number of concordant runs by major mode = 19/20; mean similarity score = 0.985). The genetic population structure among pre-and post-PZQ isolates for the best K estimate is plotted in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7. Genetic population structure of Senegal River Basin *Schistosoma* spp. sampled from cattle before and after PZQ treatment. Tilted numbers underneath the graph correspond to treatment status: 1) pre-PZQ; and 2) post-PZQ. The vertical line divides both populations. Dashed vertical lines divide infrapopulations (i.e., samples per animal) with corresponding animal identifiers inside the black-border rectangles. Within infrapopulations, each coloured rectangular bar corresponds to a genotyped parasite. Two genetic clusters (K=2) were identified with the Evanno method.

The genetic population structure bar plots above show no differential genetic clustering between villages nor treatment status, in support of PCoA results.

4.5. Discussion

4.5.1. Optimised microsatellite markers for livestock-infective schistosomes

Previously published microsatellite genetic population studies conducted in African livestock (from Cameroon (189); and from Senegal (190)) have focused on adult *S. bovis* worms collected from cattle at abattoirs (189, 190). The present work aimed to test those microsatellite markers in hatched larval stages of schistosomes (i.e., miracidia), recovered in 2018 from SRB live bovines, to study their population genetics.

The sampled SRB area had a 92% prevalence of *S. bovis* in cattle in 2016-2018 (18), and during later live sampling the predominance of *S. bovis* infection was corroborated (Webster et al, not published). Likewise, the isolates analysed here were most likely *S. bovis*, even though less than 50% of the pre-PZQ and none of the post-PZQ miracidia were characterised as such, which does not rule out the possibility of infection with other schistosome species and/or hybrids.

In accordance with published *S. bovis* work (189, 190), microsatellite primer details were derived from Webster et al. (191, 195). Disparities between that reference and its original references were discovered—original references used by Webster et al. for C102 (210) and for Sh6 (211). Specifically, Webster et al.'s C102 forward primer sequence had one nucleotide less than the original reference (missing Thymine as the 10th nucleotide), and the Sh6 repeat motif was a tri- instead of a di-nucleotide repeat (AAT instead of AC).

PCR multiplex optimisation for miracidial samples was achieved by increasing both the volume of DNA template and the number of thermal cycles, in contrast with published *S. bovis* work (189, 190). Authors of the Senegalese study—which was also conducted in SRB but in 2010—reported that locus C102 and C111 did not amplify with their *S. bovis* worms, while Sh5 amplified poorly (190). The same three microsatellite markers had to be excluded from the miracidia multiplex. Therefore, findings by Boon et al. on SRB worms have been confirmed in SRB miracidia. In contrast, those three markers amplified well with Cameroonian cattle worms (189).

A total of 200 miracidia collected during a pre- and post-praziquantel (PZQ) efficacy trial (see Chapter 3 for details), were successfully genotyped in the present study with 12 out of the 15 assessed microsatellites. Of these 200 isolates, 175 were pre-PZQ miracidia and 25 were post-PZQ miracidia (see Table 4.4 for a per village breakdown). Fragment length raw data of successfully genotyped isolates was processed by setting loci to existing *S. bovis* values, as detailed in section 4.3.2. The existing *S. bovis* values fell within the *S. haematobium* size range (191, 195), with the exemption of Sh15 and Sh12 (Table 4.2). A slight shift in size ranges was nonetheless detected between *S. haematobium* and *S. bovis* (see Table 4.2), two different but closely related species from the *S. haematobium* clade. Furthermore, a size range difference in Sh15 between cattle samples of

Cameroonian origin (274-280 bp) and some of the present Senegalese origin samples (271-280 bp) was also detected. Such was the case for SRB pre-PZQ miracidia and worms from the ZELS project, but not for post-PZQ miracidia (Table 4.2).

4.5.2. Genotypic analyses of miracidia from SRB cattle before and after PZQ

A graphical summary of steps included in the relevant bioinformatics pipeline is given in Figure 4.2. Components of the genotypic analyses included genetic diversity, genetic variance, and genetic structure.

In the genetic diversity analysis, significant differences in observed heterozygosity (H_o) and inbreeding coefficient (F) were detected between Djidièry and Mbane, pre-PZQ. Moreover, significant departures from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) were detected in locus Sh3 only for Djidièry; in locus Sh4 and Sh2 only for Ndombo; in locus Sh6 for Djidièry and Mbane; and in locus Sh9 and Sha for the three villages (see Table 4.1). The HWE departures in the latter locus were highly significant. Highly significant departures were also detected for this locus by treatment status (Sha pre- vs post-PZQ in Appendix F5). Departures from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE)—a hypothetical state which assumes random mating in the population, are commonly induced by inbreeding (193). Indeed, the Sha locus was highlighted for partial inbreeding in the three villages (Table 4.5), with the highest inbreeding coefficient detected in Mbane ($F = 0.537$). It is possible to observe inbreeding in some loci but not others since the magnitude of the effect (i.e., reduction in heterozygosity and increase in homozygosity) would depend among other factors, on how many alleles are present at each locus and what their frequencies are (193). Despite the high mutation rates of microsatellites which could partially mask the effects of inbreeding, the higher partial inbreeding found in Mbane suggests the analysed schistosome population from this village is not panmictic. This, coupled to the fact that Mbane is in the lake shore of Lac de Guiers (unlike the other two villages), suggests a higher exposure and reinfection rate to the cercaria shed by lake inhabiting snails among Mbane cattle (in comparison to animals from the other villages). Moreover, the higher partial inbreeding and constant opportunities for reinfection due to its lake shore location could explain the distinctly poor PZQ performance observed in Mbane (pre- and post-praziquantel study: ~ 12% miracidia reduction rate in Mbane (MRR) vs $\geq 90\%$ in Djidièry and Ndombo, see previous chapter for details). Indeed, most of the miracidia (75%) examined in the pre- vs post-PZQ analysis were collected from 4 non-responder bovines from Mbane (~ 60% pre-PZQ vs 96% post-PZQ)—the remainder were from 1 non-responder bovine from Ndombo (see Table 4.4).

A low level of variation (less than 1%) by pairwise F_{st} comparison was detected among the schistosome populations of the three villages (Table 4.7 A), with a slightly higher low level of variation (1.5%) detected by treatment status (Table 4.7 B). Miracidial samples are likely to be less diverse than adult worm samples given that the former may only partially reflect the genetic variability of the latter (the specific MHT sampling time captures a proportion of excreted eggs, resulting from successful matings, that hatch). The pairwise F_{st} values obtained from miracidial populations of northern Senegal were

nonetheless higher than those reported for spread out worm populations recovered from slaughtered Cameroonian cattle (189). The least similar villages by pairwise *F*_{st}, genetic distance, and genetic identity, were Djidièry and Ndombo, whereas the most similar by genetic distance and genetic identity were Mbane and Ndombo. These findings do not correlate to geographic distance. There are approximately 5.5 km between Djidièry and Ndombo, while Mbane and Ndombo are separated by approximately 23 km, and Mbane and Djidièry are even further apart (around 27.6 km) (geographic distances calculated using Google Maps). However, direction of water-flow may better correlate with the similarity findings. There are two main waterbodies in the SRB: the Senegal River in the north (with west to east water-flow) (212), and the lake Lac de Guiers in the south (with south to north water-flow) (213). While Djidièry is located very near the Senegal River, Mbane is in the shores of Lac de Guiers. Ndombo has a nearby canal which appears to receive water from Lac de Guiers and eventually connects with the Senegal River. Therefore, cattle from Ndombo might have had more contact with contaminated water (i.e., containing schistosome cercaria) from Lac de Guiers, at least respective to the time of sampling, which might explain the genetic similarity found between Mbane and Ndombo.

In the genetic variance analysis by AMOVA, 99% of the genetic variation was observed within hosts among isolates analysed before treatment (i.e., pre-PZQ genotyping) (Table 4.9 A), in agreement with the Cameroonian study which had 98.09% (189). In the other analysed set of isolates however (i.e., pre- vs post-PZQ genotyping), 97% of the genetic variation was observed within treatment status (Table 4.9 B). Nonetheless, no significant AMOVA population differentiation was detected at all hierarchical levels of both genotyping analyses.

Lastly, in the genetic structure analysis, for both genotyping analyses less than 20% of the PCoA variation was explained in the first two axes (Figures 4.4 and 4.5). In support of this, genetic population structure bar plots showed no differential genetic clustering between villages (Figure 4.6) nor treatment status (Figure 4.7).

Thus, the potentially focal genetic structure of genotyped schistosomes was ruled out by the results obtained with PCoA and the Bayesian clustering approach, as well as the AMOVA, with very little variation between villages. However, the level of variation found here among three SBR villages was slightly higher than that found among four abattoir locations in Cameroon separated by large geographical distances (189). The latter study found a major demographic difference between cattle schistosomes and urogenital schistosomes from humans, and concluded this difference could be explained by the pressure exerted by PZQ mass drug administration rounds in people. Even though the pre- vs post-PZQ genotypic analysis presented here had a small number of isolates (*n*=57) predominantly from Mbane (*n*=43) a greater level of genetic variation (pairwise *F*_{st} 1.5%) was found between pre-PZQ and post-PZQ samples than between villages. Furthermore, the AMOVA analysis highlighted most of the hierarchical variation occurred within treatment status. Both findings confirm a differential effect of treatment in Mbane, the village with the lowest MRR and therefore where most non-responder bovines were located. Miracidial isolates from Mbane were also the most partially inbred,

with more consanguineous mating decreasing heterozygosity. Indeed, the lowest observed heterozygosity was recorded in Mbane (mean H_o (SE): Djidiéry = 0.729 (0.068) > Ndombo = 0.692 (0.064) > Mbane = 0.670 (0.075)). This was also underlined by the significant differences in genetic diversity (H_o and F) between Djidiéry and Mbane.

Among the factors expected to genetically homogenize schistosome populations is gene flow among mobile organisms like planktonic larvae (i.e., free-swimming larval schistosomes) that could be carried long distances by freshwater currents (193); host dispersal linked to cattle movement; lack of structured PZQ treatments in cattle potentially fostering population expansion; and a projected large effective size for *S. bovis* (189). Notwithstanding these factors, the present work found evidence of differential diversity among the three villages of SRB which had non-responder bovines. This warrants further exploration. Analysis of more genotyped isolates from these three villages as well as other SRB villages in conjunction with information on bovine movement patterns linked to season and exposure to waterbodies would aid in furthering the work presented here.

Finally, this study analysed miracidia hatched from eggs collected from live cattle, instead of adult worms retrieved from cattle at abattoir as was done in the referenced microsatellite genetic population studies conducted in African livestock (189, 190). The use of miracidia is more representative of the genetic composition of schistosome populations found in contaminated water sources to which animals and humans are exposed. Moreover, parasitological surveys from live animals conducted in their locations of origin, allow for collection of more precise geographical information in comparison to abattoir surveys. Nevertheless, the use of GPS (as in (187, 188)) would yield even more precise geographical information and importantly, informative cattle movement data about visited waterbodies and the time, length, and frequency of exposure to them. Such studies would further increase understanding of livestock schistosomiasis.

4.6. Conclusion

Microsatellite polymorphisms have been used for decades as a molecular tool to study population genetic diversity. These markers are a cost-effective alternative to whole genome sequencing which in this study were prohibitively expensive and of unclear added benefit. The optimised microsatellite multiplex approach used here for the very first time with miracidia from SRB cattle allowed genotyping of multiple loci per larval isolate. Novel insights into the population genetics of Senegalese *S. bovis* from cattle are provided in this study, including features of inbreeding in one of the evaluated villages which may be linked to poor praziquantel chemotherapy performance. More population genetic structure studies of cattle-infecting schistosomes are clearly needed in this SRB hotspot with perennial schistosomiasis transmission, where evidence of bovines' role as maintenance hosts of *S. bovis* has been previously found. A greater number of intra- and inter-population samples collected would allow investigation of the degree of relatedness and gene flow in SRB. Moreover, in tandem genotyping of schistosomes collected from other relevant definitive hosts would enhance understanding of transmission within SRB. Crucial data derived from such studies could help characterise the role of livestock in schistosomiasis transmission within SSA and thus inform targeted schistosomiasis control in animal reservoirs with potential impacts on both human and animal health, as well as food production.

CHAPTER 5

General Discussion

The health of the inhabitants of the biosphere is intertwined. This concept is known as One Health. The need for a One Health approach to tackle schistosomiasis in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), the region where 90% of worldwide human cases occur and most preventive chemotherapy is concentrated, has been recently recognised, with an anew focus on relevant animal reservoirs. Based on previous identification of one such group of animal reservoirs, domestic ruminants, this thesis explored the transmission, control, and population genetics of livestock schistosomiasis in an area of Senegal, the Senegal River Basin (SRB), which is considered a schistosomiasis hotspot (66).

With the intent of furthering potential One Health control strategies against schistosomiasis targeted at livestock, this thesis addressed the following main questions: i) why is a One Health approach focused on livestock ruminants important? (Chapter 1); ii) how would a theoretical bovine test-and-treat strategy impact schistosomiasis prevalence in farming locations of northern Senegal? (Chapter 2); iii) what is the efficacy of treatment with praziquantel against livestock schistosomiasis in locations of northern Senegal? (Chapter 3); iv) what is the population genetics of bovine schistosomes collected in locations of northern Senegal before and after praziquantel treatment? (Chapter 4).

5.1. Applied methodology

To answer those four main questions recognised ways of researching were applied. In the introductory chapter (Chapter 1) a literature review was carried out, the result of which was published as an opinion piece entitled “Reaching the WHO elimination targets for schistosomiasis: the importance of a One Health perspective” (see Appendix B). In the first data chapter (Chapter 2), Bayesian prevalence levels based on recent epidemiological data were used as baseline for a transmission control modelling approach to evaluate a proposed (single) herd-level test-and-treat intervention. In the second data chapter (Chapter 3), statistical analysis of epidemiological data from a small longitudinal drug efficacy study was conducted to derive preliminary estimates of praziquantel efficacy per domestic ruminant species, further stratified per recruited village. Trends before and after treatment were visually explored, and ordinal logistic regression was used to evaluate the effect of treatment on BCS. In the last data chapter (Chapter 4), a subset of samples from bovines of the longitudinal study were tested with microsatellite markers for the molecular characterisation of pre- and post-PZQ miracidia (larval stage of the parasite). The resulting genotyping data was then incorporated into a bioinformatics pipeline to evaluate their genetic diversity, variance and structure at a population level.

5.2. Key findings

The introductory literature review (Chapter 1) made apparent that numerous cases of interspecific hybridization amongst species of the *Schistosoma haematobium* clade have been reported in hosts of SSA. This information was compiled and summarised in Table 1.1. Importantly, hybrids between the livestock-infective schistosome species *S. bovis* and a urogenital human schistosome, *S. haematobium*, are involved in such hybridization events, and are commonly reported across SSA, including in SRB. Moreover, contrary to previous knowledge, cases of pure *S. bovis* infection in humans have been recently recorded in Nigeria, highlighting the importance of researching schistosome species thought to only infect livestock.

Current 2030 WHO schistosomiasis elimination targets necessitate the inclusion of relevant animal reservoirs in control interventions. The relevance of targeting livestock in a true One Health manner within SSA was therefore highlighted and advocated for (Chapter 1, Appendix B). Interventions targeted at livestock could include treatment with praziquantel (PZQ), nonetheless, given that human schistosomiasis control and elimination relies heavily on this drug, several considerations must be taken into account to mitigate the risk of emerging resistance to PZQ. Such considerations as well as related concepts were summarised in Table 1.2. Thus, motivated by previous evidence published by others of the importance of cattle for maintenance of *S. bovis* in the SRB, in conjunction with reports of off-label use of praziquantel (PZQ) in SRB to treat livestock schistosomiasis, an illustrative structured control intervention tackling bovines of SRB was explored in Chapter 2.

Bayesian posterior estimates of bovine schistosomiasis prevalence ranged from 43% to 95% with 6 out of 8 SRB locations above 50% (Table 2.2). Four locations had particularly high prevalence equal or above 90%: Djidièry, Mbane, Medina Cheikhou, and Yetti Yone (Table 2.2). The value of MHT as diagnostic technique was evidenced by the greater concordance of bovine schistosomiasis true prevalence estimation with MHT apparent prevalence in comparison to KK apparent prevalence (Figure 2.2). This finding is attributable to the greater sensitivity of the former test in comparison to the latter (79% vs 31%). Since it had been established by others that the cattle in those locations were (and had been) predominantly infected with *S. bovis*, the simulated test-and-treat transmission model described in Chapter 2, focused on *S. bovis* infected cattle in a perennial transmission area of SRB. A prevalence range of 40 to 95% based on the Bayesian posterior estimates was used as pre-intervention baseline in the model, which simulated annual rounds of test (with POC-CCA), and (if at least one bovine is positive within the tested herd), treat (with PZQ) from 2022 to 2030. Effectiveness indicators included bovine case-years averted after 9 test-and-treat (TnT) rounds as percentage of baseline prevalence, and percentage of simulations per prevalence category that nominally reached elimination (i.e., prevalence of less than 1%). Simulations established not only that the more animals tested the greater the impact of each TnT round, but also that the relative intervention impact decreases with increasing baseline prevalence (Figure 2.3 and 2.4). When applying 4 tests per annual round of herd TnT during 9 consecutive rounds, up to 85% of bovine-case years can be averted in settings with a baseline

prevalence of 40% and up to 75% at baseline prevalence of 95% (Figure 2.5). Nominal elimination (or a prevalence of less than 1%) is only achieved when using 4 tests per round, with a 75% chance of achieving such elimination over the 9 rounds in low prevalence settings and more than 10% chance in high prevalence settings (Figure 2.6). Besides the probability of having at least one POC-CCA positive test result in the single herd at each TnT round (i.e., true and false positives), the positive predictive value (PPV, probability of detecting a true positive) as indicator of diagnostic performance was also calculated. PPV was relatively high at pre-intervention but declines with declining prevalence at each TnT round. After 9 rounds with 4 test per round, PPV is less than 25% at 90% baseline prevalence, and less than 5% at 50% and 70% baseline prevalence (Figure 2.7). Using less tests retains higher PPV owing to the lower likelihood of detecting a false positive and reduced impact of TnT on prevalence. The deterministic model applied in Chapter 2 is illustrative with many biological and operational uncertainties remaining. Nevertheless, this work demonstrates the potential value of a One Health approach targeting bovines in SRB. Among the uncertainties highlighted is the lack of a standardised drug efficacy estimate for the treatment of livestock schistosomiasis with PZQ in Africa. Analysis of previously collected data to produce a preliminary praziquantel efficacy estimate among schistosome-infected domestic ruminants of SRB was thus explored in Chapter 3.

As was underscored in Chapter 2 (and previously by others), miracidia based diagnostic techniques have a higher sensitivity for diagnosis of livestock schistosomes and evaluate egg viability. Analysis of miracidial summary epidemiological statistics established that infection intensity (MPG) varied among ruminant species and localities (Table 3.1). Paired subject-level pre- and post-PZQ MPG reflects variation in treatment response by species, with a pattern of decreasing infection intensity seen in bovines, variable response to treatment in goats, and stable infection intensity in sheep. Outliers with high infection intensity post-treatment were recorded among goats and sheep. Further stratification by age evidenced differing patterns of response to treatment among age groups of goats and sheep—intensity of infection remained the same after PZQ in older goats, whereas it tripled in older sheep, nevertheless groups were heavily skewed toward older animals. Stratification by co-infection status evidenced differing patterns of response to treatment among co-infected and not co-infected bovines and sheep—intensity of infection reduction after PZQ in co-infected bovines, whereas it rebounded in not co-infected sheep, nevertheless groups were heavily skewed. The seemingly protective effect of co-infections among bovines linked to lower post-PZQ miracidial counts deserves further exploration.

Importantly, a drug efficacy indicator based on reduction of miracidial counts with treatment (i.e., miracidia reduction rate, MRR) was used instead of standard FEC counts, for a more accurate statistical assessment of PZQ efficacy. MRR estimates were highest among bovines (81.53%) and not dissimilar to the efficacy estimate used in Chapter's 2 bovine model (i.e., 90% PZQ efficacy). The lowest MRR among bovines was seen in the village of Mbane (11.77%), while the remaining 4 villages had MRR equal or above 90%. Infection clearance was recorded >70% of Mbane animals, in none of the Ndombo animals, and in ≥90% of bovines in the remaining villages. A total of 11 of 59 bovines remained infected post-PZQ (2 non-responders in Djidièry, 5 Mbane and 4 Ndombo). In goats, MRR was low (14.22%),

less than half cleared the infection, with 2 out of 22 non-responders. In sheep, MRR and clearance were even lower (-167.19% and 22.73%, respectively), with 17 out of 22 non-responders. Counterintuitively, however, there was a highly significant positive effect of treatment on body condition score (BCS) in both bovines and sheep. This positive association between treatment and BCS was likened to a higher likelihood of moving into any next-highest ordered BCS category after treatment, with the basic CLMM. Paired subject-level pre- and post-PZQ BCS reflects variation in BCS by species as response to treatment: while 28 bovines improved, 17 remained the same, and 9 worsen; in goats, 3 improved, 16 remained the same, and 3 worsen; and in sheep, 15 improved and 5 remained the same.

Interestingly, despite the high efficacy of PZQ treatment against bovine schistosomiasis, three of the 5 bovine villages had animals which remained infected despite treatment (non-responders): Djidièry, Mbane and Ndombo. Miracidia samples collected pre- and post-PZQ from bovines of those three villages were examined in Chapter 4.

The last data chapter investigated the population genetics (pop-gen) of schistosomes collected before and after PZQ treatment of bovines from Djidièry, Mbane and Ndombo. Notably, a microsatellite PCR multiplex protocol previously used by others with *S. bovis* adults collected from cattle at abattoir, was successfully optimised for use with miracidia samples collected from live cattle from SRB. 12 out of the 15 microsatellite markers tested were amplified and genotyped successfully. Subsequent pop-gen analyses using microsatellite marker genotypic data found a difference in the genetic diversity indexes of H_o and F , between the 3 villages for the pre-PZQ analysis, particularly between Djidièry and Mbane, for both indexes. Interestingly, indication of a higher level of inbreeding—almost twice than in Ndombo, and almost 4 times than in Djidièry—was found in Mbane, the worst performing bovine village (i.e., Mbane had the lowest MRR). Pairwise F_{st} comparison found less than 1% variation pre-PZQ between village pairs (least similar Djidièry and Mbane 0.8% variation); and 1.5% variation pre-vs post-PZQ between treatment status. Pairwise unbiased estimates of genetic distance and identity showed greatest similarity between Mbane and Ndombo, and the least similarity between Djidièry and Ndombo. These findings of similarity were not correlated to geographical distance, but potentially correlated to direction of waterflow. Moreover, genetic diversity evaluation by AMOVA analysis indicated almost all genetic variation (99%) pre-PZQ was found within hosts (less than 1% variation between animals and villages); and almost all genetic variation (97%) pre-vs post-PZQ was found within treatment status (just above 1% variation between Tx status within animals, and less than 1% between animals and villages). Genetic structure analysis found that less than 20% of variation was explained in the first two PCoA axes of both sets of genotyping analyses (i.e., pre-PZQ and pre-vs post-PZQ). In support of the PCoA results, no differential genetic clustering by Bayesian clustering analysis between villages nor treatment status was found. The potentially focal genetic structure by village of genotyped schistosomes was ruled out.

In agreement with previous studies little genetic structuring was found among villages, and most of the genetic variation in the analysis of pre-PZQ samples only was found within hosts (which are said to act

as genetic mixing bowls). Interestingly, when comparing pre-PZQ and post-PZQ samples most of the genetic variation was found within treatment status (greater level of genetic variation between treatment status than between villages by pairwise F_{st} , plus AMOVA variation occurred mostly within treatment status). Most of the genotyped miracidial isolates ($n=57$) were sampled in Mbane ($n=43$). Thus, a differential effect of treatment indicated by the pop-gen analysis presented in Chapter 4, in conjunction with the low MRR estimate of PZQ efficacy in Mbane highlighted in Chapter 3, justifies further exploration in Mbane. Miracidial isolates from Mbane before treatment were also the most partially inbred (more consanguineous mating decreasing heterozygosity), with significant differences in genetic diversity (H_o and F) between Djidièry and Mbane. The higher partial inbreeding found in Mbane indicates the analysed schistosome population from this village is not panmictic (non-random mating). More intensive livestock rearing around the shores of Lac de Guiers (where most *S. haematobium* x *S. bovis* hybrids have been found) was considered by Boon et al 2018, as a potential reason for the heterogeneous distribution of hybrids in SRB. Mbane is in fact the only village located in the shores of this lake among the villages evaluated here. The distinct and poor response to PZQ treatment seen among bovines of this village (Mbane) coupled with a higher likeliness of hybridization and potential for consequent human infection, warrants further studies in this particular location.

5.3. Limitations and future studies

The deterministic transmission model presented in Chapter 2 had limitations. The effect of a TnT intervention was simulated for a single herd, using prevalence ranges derived from relevant epidemiological data. However, comparison between intervention strategies was not possible with this model. Future models, for instance metapopulation models, could incorporate different baseline prevalences to better emulate the focal nature of schistosomiasis. Consequently, interventions could be compared against a strategy of blanket treatment. Even though the efficacy of PZQ estimate used in the model (i.e., ERR of *S. haematobium* in humans) was not too different from the bovine MRR estimate obtained in Chapter 3, the efficacy parameter in equation 6 is applied to mean worm burden. The model therefore makes the simplifying assumption that egg count is indicative of worm burden. Given that adult worms reside in the vasculature of their definitive host, indirect methods evaluating presence and/or viability of schistosome eggs in stool are used as proxy to calculate drug efficacy, for instance, via egg or miracidia reduction rates. Moreover, some evidence of density dependent fecundity in *S. haematobium* human infections exists in the literature (143), and efforts to estimate (adult) helminth burdens using sibship reconstruction (of juvenile genotypes) (214) continue.

Since the pre-and post-praziquantel study analysed in Chapter 3 took place, there are now appropriate single compound PZQ veterinary products commercially available in Senegal. Larger studies are required to explore the differential effect of PZQ for the treatment of livestock schistosomiasis found among domestic ruminants. The co-infections recorded during the pre-and post-PZQ study included liver flukes (*Fasciola* spp.) and nematodes of the *Strongyles* family. To further evaluate the seemingly

protective effect of co-infection detected in Chapter 3 among schistosome infected bovines, a more systematic recording of parasite co-infection is recommended for future studies. Besides the dynamics of nematode and trematode (including *Fasciola* and *Schistosoma* spp.) co-infections of veterinary importance, other potential topics to expand upon the present work could include within host ecology during immunologically distinct life stages (e.g., faecal egg/miracidial counts and diversity within young vs adult animals), by sex (for instance, males vs females; before and after parturition; during lactation) and/or by season. Furthermore, given the differential effect PZQ treatment had amongst schistosome infected bovines, goats and sheep from SRB (Chapter 3), a need for future studies of the pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of PZQ in domestic ruminants is apparent, as is the need to optimise therapeutic regimens against livestock schistosomiasis. Interestingly, pharmacokinetic optimisation to enhance parasite exposure and the use of a mixture of chemical compounds have been highlighted as valid strategies to mitigate selection for further resistance (215).

Given the small sample sizes of the population genetics analysis carried out in Chapter 4, future studies should include more miracidial samples. Moreover, improved sampling strategies (e.g., multiple sampling times and/or days) would enhance the output of such studies to better reflect the genetic composition of the population. Differences in allele frequencies between life stages of the same organism resulting from demographic, ecological or selection pressure factors could nonetheless bias variability estimates. For instance, density-dependent fecundity might lead to a reduction in genetic diversity of analysed miracidia compared to the adult population. Complementing miracidial genetic data with adult data could minimise such bias. In addition, a greater number of microsatellites should be analysed for a more complete evaluation of genetic diversity. Furthermore, a greater number of samples collected within and between hosts would allow for measurement of kinship and gene flow. Kinship information could also be used for studies on helminth burden estimation using sibship reconstruction (214). A greater number of samples collected from a variety of relevant definitive hosts has been used in the past to draw inferences on the directionality of indirect schistosome transmission between animal hosts (99). Potential for the identification of host species driving transmission in this multi-host parasite system also exists (17). Importantly, population genetics inferences could be used to inform the development of geographically structured meta-population transmission models to explore optimal TnT intervention strategies for livestock schistosomiasis. The relevance of such work goes beyond animal health and productivity.

5.4 Conclusion

The zoonotic relevance of cattle as maintenance animal reservoirs of *S. bovis* in the transmission hotspot of SRB as well as reports of informal use and misuse of PZQ on livestock by SRB farmers had been previously established. Consequently, motivated by the need for structured control interventions targeted at livestock ruminants of SRB, this doctoral thesis investigated three interconnected lines of enquiry. Transmission control, via a simulated bovine TnT strategy using a POC-CCA test; chemotherapy control, via praziquantel efficacy analysis against schistosomes of domestic ruminants; and population genetics, via microsatellite markers applied to a subset of schistosome samples from distinct bovines of SRB. Key findings from this work include the illustrative substantial impact a TnT strategy targeting SRB infected cattle herds could have on current high prevalence levels in SRB; the high efficacy of PZQ in treating schistosome infections in cattle; and the need for further characterisation of SRB farming locations with differential PZQ efficacy and genetic features. This thesis presents a contribution towards the design of a relevant One Health approach that includes bovines, if schistosomiasis elimination 2030 targets are to be reached in SSA. Such approach would minimise the risk of PZQ resistance, safeguarding the efficacy of this essential medicine while helping to limit the spread of zoonotic schistosomes and the emergence of hybrids in the region.

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PERSPECTIVE

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Surveillance and control of SARS-CoV-2 in mustelids: An evolutionary perspective

Abstract

The relevance of mustelids in SARS-CoV-2 transmission has become increasingly evident. Alongside experimental demonstration of airborne transmission among ferrets, the major animal model for human respiratory diseases, transmission of SARS-CoV-2 within- and/or between-commercial mink farms has occurred and continues to occur. The number of mink reared for the luxury fur trade is approximately 60.5 million, across 36 mustelid-farming countries. By July 2021, SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks have been reported in 12 of these countries, at 412 European and 20 North American mink farms. Reverse zoonotic transmission events (from humans to mink) have introduced the virus to farms with subsequent extensive mink-to-mink transmission as well as further zoonotic (mink-to-human) transmission events generating cases among both farm workers and the broader community. Overcrowded housing conditions inherent within intensive mink farms, often combined with poor sanitation and welfare, both guarantee spread of SARS-CoV-2 and facilitate opportunities for viral variants, thereby effectively representing biotic hubs for viral transmission and evolution of virulence. Adequate preventative, surveillance and control measures within the mink industry are imperative both for the control of the current global pandemic and to mitigate against future outbreaks.

2013); it has sustained increasingly large human populations, altered a range of ecosystems and set the conditions for otherwise unlikely interspecies encounters. Both animal farming and animal trade lead to the aggregation of host species that can maintain and enhance emergence of human-shared pathogens and serve as a bridge between wildlife and humans. All three highly infectious human coronaviruses (hCoVs) that have emerged in the 21st century are thought to have jumped to human hosts after sequential spillover from their likely bat reservoir to domesticated or marketed mammals.

The first emergent hCoV of this century, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV or SARS-CoV-1), recombined in masked palm civets—which are caught in the wild and/or farmed and sold in markets as exotic food (Shi & Hu, 2008)—before infecting humans during two independent animal-to-human transmission events in South China in 2002–2003 and 2003–2004 (Kan et al., 2005; Shi & Hu, 2008). The second emergent hCoV, Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), a highly prevalent virus of dromedary camels, spilled over to humans in Saudi Arabia in 2012 (Cui et al., 2019), and thousands of human cases of a particular MERS-CoV lineage have since been linked to direct or indirect contact with camels (Chafekar & Fielding, 2018). The third emergent hCoV, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), was identified in a cluster of atypical pneumonia cases connected to a live animal market in Wuhan, Central China, at the end of 2019 (Chen et al., 2020; Lu et al., 2020).

The hypothesized adaptation of SARS-CoV-2 from bats to an intermediary host or hosts (Andersen et al., 2020; Oude Munnink et al., 2021), and from this unclarified link to humans (Latinne et al., 2020; WHO Team, 2021), has resulted in sustained high levels of human-to-human transmission and a global pandemic of coronavirus disease (COVID-19). The rapid expansion of SARS-CoV-2 among human populations on every continent (Williams & Burgers, 2021) has, in turn, created opportunities for the virus to adapt to new hosts, particularly domestic and farmed animals. Reverse zoonotic transmission from humans to pet dogs (*Canis lupus familiaris*) and cats (*Felis catus*), and recently, a pet ferret (*Mustela putorius furo*) has been reported (OIE, 2021b), although experimental evidence of high susceptibility in companion animals to date only implicates

1 | INTRODUCTION

Pathogens are capable of rapid evolution in response to human activities (Ewald, 1998). No other human activity has had a more remarkable effect in shaping civilization than agriculture (Ehrlich & Ehrlich,

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cats, golden Syrian hamsters (*Mesocricetus auratus*) and ferrets, with documented additional intra-species transmission in the latter three (OIE, 2021a). Susceptibility to SARS-CoV-2 has been discounted in cattle, chicken, ducks, turkeys and pigs (OIE, 2021a), but other farmed animals such as rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) and raccoon dogs (*Nyctereutes procyonoides*) have proved moderately and highly susceptible to experimental infection, respectively, with evidence of subsequent transmission between raccoon dogs (OIE, 2021a). Most notably, however, two members of the mustelid family, ferrets and American mink (*Neovison vison*, see Box 1), are not only highly susceptible to experimental infection but can also acquire and transmit the virus naturally (OIE, 2021a).

Overview of the global density of farmed mink using information from the SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment on fur farms gathered by the Joint FAO-OIE-WHO Global Early Warning System for health threats and emerging risks at the human-animal-ecosystems interface (WHO et al., 2021). SARS-CoV-2 susceptible animals are commercially farmed for fur in 36 countries in the world including the following: Argentina, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cambodia, Canada, China (People's Rep. of), Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, India, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Malaysia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russian Federation, Slovakia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Thailand, Turkey, Ukraine, United States of America, Uruguay and Vietnam.

Map created using the Free and Open Source QGIS 3.16.6-Hannover.

BOX 1 Facts about American mink

- *Neovison vison*, also known as *Mustela vison*, are fur-bearing, semi-aquatic mammals which are part of the largest family in the Carnivora order, Mustelidae, that includes weasels, otters, badgers, wolverines, martens and ferrets.
- Native to the United States and Canada in North America, American mink are now found in other continents including South America, Europe and Asia (see Figure 1).
- These solitary and territorial animals are opportunist predators of rodents, waterbirds, crustaceans, amphibians, reptiles and fish. With such a generalist carnivore diet, they adapt quickly to a range of aquatic and riparian habitats, making them a very successful invasive species (Palazón & CABI, 2014).
- Territorial encroachment of this invasive species impacts native wildlife. For example, decimation of water vole (*Arvicola amphibius*) populations in the UK and European mink (*Mustela lutreola*) in Eurasia is not least due to American mink predation and competition, respectively (Martin & Lea, 2020).

2 | SARS-CoV-2 IN MUSTELIDS

Ferrets are one of the major established animal models for human respiratory diseases (Muñoz-Fontela et al., 2020), used to evaluate the airborne transmission potential of influenza viruses (ECDC, 2020), being natural hosts for both type A and B human influenza (Maher & DeStefano, 2004). Moreover, they are used to investigate the pathogenesis and transmission of human respiratory syncytial virus (hRSV) and SARS-CoV-1 (Stout et al., 2021). Accordingly, ferrets are also key animal model hosts for experimental studies on SARS-CoV-2 pathogenicity and transmission (ECDC, 2020; Kim et al., 2020; Muñoz-Fontela et al., 2020; Stout et al., 2021), presenting mild clinical signs of upper respiratory tract infection including fever and nasal discharge (Stout et al., 2021). In addition to efficient SARS-CoV-2 infection via ferret-to-ferret direct contact (one to three days after exposure), indirect airborne transmission between animals housed in cages 10 cm apart (three to seven days postexposure) has been documented experimentally (Richard et al., 2020).

Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 among American mink (*Neovison vison*), farmed for its fur (see Figure 1 and Box 2), is both highly efficient and prevalent, with ongoing outbreaks reported (up to 6 July 2021) in commercial units from 12 countries, in order of first occurrence: the Netherlands, Denmark, Spain, USA, Sweden, Italy, Greece, France, Lithuania, Canada, Poland and Latvia (OIE, 2021b). Further outbreaks are likely to have been missed amid high background morbidity and mortality levels inherent to such intensive production system (Compo et al., 2017; Honoré et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2014; Wilson et al., 2015). Mink infected with SARS-CoV-2 display a range of clinical signs from asymptomatic infection, watery to mucoid nasal discharge and/or inappetence, to severe dyspnoea and sudden deaths (Molenaar et al., 2020), with varying morbidity and mortality among farms (Boklund et al., 2021; Hammer et al., 2021; OIE, 2021a).

Mink farm outbreaks are facilitated by housing conditions which typically consist of adjoining bare wire cages that allow for both free airflow and animal contact within densely populated facilities (ECDC, 2020). The virus, seeded and regularly re-introduced into farms by staff (Boklund et al., 2021), is thus efficiently maintained and amplified through both mink-to-mink contact and likely airborne transmission. Accentuated by the risk of initial misdiagnoses, SARS-CoV-2 can spread undetected for weeks within and between mink farms, as was realized in the first two reporting countries in the world, the Netherlands and Denmark (Hammer et al., 2021). In both nations, despite a subsequent integrated response that involved tight biosecurity, targeted culls and active surveillance (see Box 3), transmission chains proved difficult to break and the mode of transmission between some Dutch farms remains elusive (Oude Munnink et al., 2021). The risk of SARS-CoV-2 diagnosis among Danish units has been associated with farm size and distance to nearest affected farm, although between-farm transmission routes beyond direct human contact remain unclear (Boklund et al., 2021). Pertinently, mink-specific SARS-CoV-2 variants evolved in both countries, accumulating mutations such as those in the ORF3a

FIGURE 1 Farmed mink density worldwide as of 20 January 2021

gene (H182Y) and in the spike gene (Y453F) (Hammer et al., 2021). Mutation Y453F (Hodcroft, 2021), along with another three spike protein mutations (an amino acid deletion, H69del/V70del; and two substitutions, I692V and M1129I; SSI, 2020), arose in a particular Danish mink variant known as 'Cluster 5', a variant linked to twelve human cases that proved less susceptible to human convalescent neutralizing antibodies, drawing attention to the possible implications of mink-related SARS-CoV-2 mutations on vaccine efficacy and human health (BMJ & Dyer, 2020; Hodcroft, 2021; SSI, 2020; WHO, 2020). Moreover, some of the mink variants potentially increased transmissibility (Hammer et al., 2021) and enhanced mink's role as an amplifying host.

It has been reported that most Dutch mink farms developed a farm-specific SARS-CoV-2 genomic signature which was employed to confirm animal-to-worker transmission events (Koopmans, 2021). Examination of the initial 16 Dutch farm outbreaks found evidence of SARS-CoV-2 infection in 68% of tested mink farm residents and employees (66 of 97 people tested), and nanopore sequences from infected mink and farm workers were phylogenetically grouped into five clusters (Oude Munnink et al., 2021). In contrast to the Dutch case, where spillover into the local community was not apparent, two of the three initially affected Danish farms were epidemiologically linked to a local COVID-19-positive nursing home, and moreover, viral sequencing indicated people in the area with no contact to either farm or the nursing home were part of the same chain of transmission (Larsen, 2020b). Aggregation of farms in the

North Jutland region might explain such early spillover (BMJ & Dyer, 2020), as does the sheer numbers of mink involved: before the late November 2020 mink cull, there were roughly three times more mink than humans living in Denmark (approximately 17 million mink vs. 5.8 million humans). As recognized by the WHO (WHO, 2020), mink acted as a significant virus reservoir in Denmark and clearly contributed to ongoing transmission.

Spillover potential of mink is not limited to humans. The occurrence of mink escapes from commercial units is not uncommon and can lead to the introduction of SARS-CoV-2 into wild populations of mustelids and other animal species (Jo et al., 2020; Koopmans, 2021; Olival et al., 2020). In the United States, besides the presence of the virus in two mink presumed to have escaped from farms (Fine Maron, 2021; see Box 3) and seropositivity of a further 11 escaped mink (Shriner et al., 2021), the SARS-CoV-2 sequence recovered from a wild mink matched that found in an affected farm close to the sampling location (Miles, 2020; see Box 3). In January 2021, lymphatic tissue from two of 13 feral mink trapped in Valencia, Spain, showed a low RT-PCR SARS-CoV-2 load later confirmed by Sanger sequencing (Aguiló-Gisbert et al., 2021). These authors proposed such findings were not; however, the result of farm escapes and hypothesized two independent wastewater sporadic infection events among mink of stable riverside feral colonies in Spain had occurred (Aguiló-Gisbert et al., 2021). Interestingly, SARS-CoV-2 infection from a yet-to-be-clarified source was recently confirmed in four Asian small-clawed otters (*Aonyx cinereus*) kept in an American aquarium (OIE, 2021b),

BOX 2 The mink industry

- Only American mink (*Neovison vison*) are farmed, and not the smaller European mink (*Mustela lutreola*), a distant critically endangered cousin.
- These small mustelids have been selectively bred for their attractive fur since 1866 (Fur Commission USA, 2014).
- Mink hides continue to be used as luxury clothing items: 15–20 pelts can make a short coat whereas 20–30 animals can make a long coat (EIA, 2020).
- Mink regularly escape from farms and have established long-standing feral colonies in the wild (ECDC, 2020; Palazón & CABI, 2014).
- Reported behavioural changes such as fearfulness, self-mutilation and infanticide reflect welfare shortcomings (Xia et al., 2020).
- The environmental impact of producing 1 kg of mink fur has a five times higher carbon footprint than that involved in producing 1 kg of wool (Xia et al., 2020).
- The production cycle of mink farms involves a closed system, meaning all steps of production from birth to slaughter (breeding, whelping, weaning, growing), and pelting (skinning), take place within the same farm, over 1 year (ECDC, 2020).
- Between 22 and 23 countries in Europe harvest half of the world's mink fur: over 27 million pelts per year are produced by 2750 European mink farms according to some estimates (ECDC, 2020; Koopmans, 2021), or around 30 million pelts produced in 5000 European farms according to other estimates (WHO et al., 2021).
- In 2018, the biggest fur producers in Europe were Denmark (17.6 million animals), followed by Poland (5 million), the Netherlands (4.5 million), Finland (1.85 million), Greece and Lithuania (both 1.2 million) (WHO et al., 2021). In the former four fur-producing countries, there were approximately 1200, 300, 125 and 900 mink farms, respectively (Fenollar et al., 2021).
- Other significant mink producers in the world include China (20.7 million animals in 2018), the United States of America (3.1 million in 2018) and Canada (1.7 million in 2018) (WHO et al., 2021). The number of mink farms in these countries was estimated to be around 8000 and 245, respectively, in China and the USA (Fenollar et al., 2021), and more than 200 in Canada in 2017 (CMBA, 2020).
- By 2020, around a third of global mink fur demand was supplied by Denmark (BMJ & Dyer, 2020). China is the biggest mink fur consumer in the world, with a reported annual consumption of 12 million domestic pelts plus a million imported from Denmark, Finland and the United States (EIA, 2020).

an additional mustelid species with high susceptibility to natural infection (OIE, 2021a).

Co-infection among susceptible mustelids with the betacoronavirus SARS-CoV-2 and species-specific alphacoronaviruses (e.g. ferret enteric coronavirus (FRECV), ferret systemic coronavirus (FRSCV) or mink coronaviruses (MCoVs) which include the implicated cause of epizootic catarrhal gastroenteritis in mink; Stout et al., 2021) could, in theory, lead to further recombination and generation of novel recombinant viruses (Stout et al., 2021).

3 | EVOLUTION OF VIRULENCE

Most concerning are the potential evolutionary consequences of allowing unchecked SARS-CoV-2 transmission in large, highly susceptible and densely populated mink populations. The adaptive trade-off theory of pathogen evolution of virulence posits that there frequently exists a direct link between virulence—defined as pathogen-induced damage to the host—and transmission, where virulence and transmissibility are positively associated with increasing within-host replication (Acevedo et al., 2019).

The limits to virulence implied by the adaptive trade-off theory both depend on a pathogen's mode of transmission and the epidemiological context in which transmission occurs. For instance, some pathogens are limited to an intermediate level of virulence because opportunities for transmission depend on a reasonably healthy and active host (e.g. HIV-1 (Blanquart et al., 2016; Fraser et al., 2007)). For other pathogens, such as those transmitted by vectors (e.g. malaria (Mackinnon & Read, 2004)) or indirectly through the environment (e.g. cholera (Cressler et al., 2016; Ewald, 1991)), opportunities for transmission are less constrained by the health of the host and can thus evolve higher virulence. In the case of directly transmitted pathogens, evolutionary limits to virulence may be much more context dependent; if opportunities for transmission are abundant because of a constant supply of susceptible hosts in close contact, or where host populations are large and densely clustered together, evolution towards more severe virulence can go undeterred (Borovkov et al., 2013). For example, it has been proposed that the persistence of highly pathogenic avian influenza viruses in farmed populations is a consequence of the conditions created by large-scale industrial poultry farming (Lebarbenchon et al., 2010).

Contexts which provide abundant opportunities for transmission therefore have potential to facilitate evolution of increased virulence. Indeed, the emergence of SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern (VOCs) from late 2020 (Fontanet et al., 2021) is associated with intense transmission (MacLean et al., 2021). Additionally, within-host adaptation in chronic infection and responses to selective pressure to evade the immune system may have also played a role in the emergence of VOCs (MacLean et al., 2021). Notably, a recent study reported the occurrence of SARS-CoV-2 infection, recovery and three months after, reinfection among 75% of tested mink in a Danish farm, possibly as a result of continued viral replication within susceptible hosts with access to the premises (Rasmussen

BOX 3 Varying responses to the farmed mink epidemic: three case studies**The Netherlands****Initial detection**

The first apparent human-to-mink SARS-CoV-2 transmission event in the world happened in the Netherlands, a country with an estimated mink herd in excess of 4 million (WHO et al., 2021). Investigations due to respiratory and gastrointestinal signs in two mink farms confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection in mink in late April 2020, with affected farms placed under movement restrictions immediately (Bruschke, 2020a). Further epidemiological examinations concluded the virus had probably circulated for more than a month before detection (Bruschke, 2020b).

Surveillance and spread

A surveillance system for the active detection of subclinical and clinical cases in farmed mink was put in place in late May 2020 (Oude Munnink et al., 2021), consisting of mandatory notification, an early warning system linked to mink mortalities, and serological screening of all farms (Bruschke, 2020d). This comprehensive surveillance identified SARS-CoV-2 incidence in 13 farms by the beginning of June (Bruschke, 2020d), and a tally of 24 a month later (Bruschke, 2020e). Control measures instated included culls of all animals within infected farms, testing of symptomatic farm staff, intensified biosecurity, personal protective equipment (PPE) for staff exposed to animals and a 10-day waiting period for employees working in different locations (Bruschke, 2020d). Sequencing analysis implied infected employee-to-mink as introduction route for some farms but an unknown route for others, plus viral clustering between several farms (Bruschke, 2020e).

Risk and containment

A second, longer lasting wave of infections was anticipated since SARS-CoV-2 arrival preceded the birthing season and juvenile mink kits could be expected to become gradually susceptible to COVID-19 as maternal antibodies waned (Bruschke, 2020d). Rampant transmission among large numbers of susceptible animals coinciding with a period of increased human-mink exposure (birthing, weaning and scheduled core vaccination), plus the possibility of mutations, was deemed a persistent viral source which posed an increased risk to human health (Bruschke, 2020d). Therefore, given that surveillance and control measures had been insufficient to break the chain of transmission, the Dutch outbreak management team for zoonoses recommended stopping mink farming in the Netherlands after November's furring season (Bruschke, 2020c). Consequently, stamping out among infected units took place (69 farms up to December 2020), and the mink in remaining farms were pelted; effectively no farmed mink existed in the country by the end of 2020 (Bruschke, 2021). A legal ban on mink farming was brought forward on 8 January 2021 (Bruschke, 2021).

Denmark**Initial detection**

The first positive farm was confirmed in June 2020 (Larsen, 2020a), at which point Denmark was reportedly the biggest mink producer in the world with an estimated herd of 17 million (WHO, 2020; WHO et al., 2021).

Surveillance and spread

Two further farms in the same area became positive, and it was decided to cull all animals in the infected farms and dispose of carcasses via rendering by the beginning of July. Among the three initially affected mink farms, two were epidemiologically linked to a local COVID-19 positive nursing home (Larsen, 2020b). Virus sequencing indicated that people in the area with no contact to either farm or the nursing home were part of the same chain of infection (Larsen, 2020b). Consequently, a mandatory surveillance programme began by testing 10% of all farms in July (125 of 1140 farms (ECDC, 2020; Larsen, 2020c)). By early October, 94 premises in the northern and central Jutland region were confirmed infected (Larsen, 2020c). Control measures up to that point, including biosecurity and consecutive testing, had been insufficient; thus, all infected farms and those within a 7.8 km radius were culled affecting over 200 units (Larsen, 2020c). The virus had infected 207 farms up to 4 November 2020 (Larsen, 2020d).

Risk and containment

New unique mutations in SARS-CoV-2 sequences recovered from farmed mink and humans residing near to farms were discovered, and for a particular mink variant known as Cluster 5, antibody neutralization of the virus was reduced (ECDC, 2020;

SSI, 2020; WHO, 2020). Such findings triggered a governmental mandate to cull the entire herd, including breeding stock. Because of the risk to public health, a de facto shutdown of the Danish mink industry is in place for 2021 although no general ban on future mink farming has been imposed (Larsen, 2020d).

United States of America

Initial detection

After respiratory signs and sudden death among mink were seen in the last week of July 2020 in two commercial farms located in Utah, infection with SARS-CoV-2 was confirmed (Davidson, 2020b, 2020c).

Spread

By October 2020, SARS-CoV-2 was present in 11 mink farms in the state of Utah with further spread to a farm in Michigan and another in Wisconsin (OIE, 2021b). By that time, at least 12 thousand farmed mink had died as a result of coronavirus infection (ECDC, 2020), of a national herd of 3.1 million (WHO et al., 2021). The following month, animals in a commercial unit in the state of Oregon presenting with inappetence, coughing and mild respiratory signs were confirmed SARS-CoV-2 positive, after recoups of COVID-19-positive in-farm personal (Davidson, 2020a). Investigations carried out in a Michigan farm suggest mink-to-human transmission might have occurred (CDC, 2021). In contrast to the Netherlands and Denmark, a comprehensive surveillance system is yet to be implemented in the United States. A total of 16 farms have been confirmed infected up to the end of November 2020 (APHIS & USDA, 2021), and despite no subsequent reports to the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE, 2021b), the outbreak is likely ongoing.

Risk

The response in the United States has been mostly limited to increased biosecurity, quarantine and disinfection of affected units. Culling has not been implemented, and testing is still restricted to symptomatic animals. PPE and testing of farm workers have recently been encouraged (CDC, 2021). One Health teams from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) are reported to be carrying out mink farm investigations (CDC, 2021). Interestingly, wildlife surveillance of areas surrounding infected farms in Utah, Wisconsin and Michigan, between August and October 2020, detected SARS-CoV-2 in a native wild animal for the very first time, among an unspecified number of wildlife species which tested negative (Miles, 2020). The single positive case was an asymptomatic free-ranging American mink sampled in Utah, infected with a virus 'indistinguishable from the virus characterized on the nearby affected commercial mink farm' (Miles, 2020). Moreover, among 102 free-roaming mammals captured outside affected Utah premises in August 2020, 11 presumed escaped mink presented high SARS-CoV-2 antibody titres, three of which also had high RT-PCR cycle threshold detections (Shriner et al., 2021). Two further mink believed to have escaped from a farm in Oregon were reported as positive in December 2020 (Fine Maron, 2021). Such wildlife surveillance findings underline the risk posed by biosecurity breaches and insufficient control measures.

et al., 2021). Although surveillance of VOCs to date has been almost exclusively directed at humans, convergent evolution of potentially harmful mutations can occur in different host species and later spill back to humans.

The recent occurrence of emerging epidemics among farmed mink in several Chinese provinces (Fenollar et al., 2021), caused not only by new viruses—novel mink orthoreovirus outbreak in 2011 (MRV1HB_A) hypothesized to be the result of reassortment between human and swine reoviruses (Lian et al., 2013)—but also by viruses traditionally linked to other animal species—such as outbreaks of porcine pseudorabies virus (Aujeszky's disease agent) in 2014 (Wang et al., 2018); avian paramyxovirus type 1 (Newcastle disease agent) in 2014 (Zhao et al., 2017) and two highly pathogenic H5N1 avian influenza viruses (G15 and XB15) in 2015 (Jiang et al., 2017)—further highlights the susceptibility to infectious agents and

zoonotic potential of American mink. Intensive farming practices, in conjunction with marginal nutrition and poor sanitation, enhance contagion among crowded, genetically homogenous mink (Fenollar et al., 2021).

Crucially, mink are an important species for generation of antigenically diverse respiratory viruses such as influenza (ECDC, 2020) and conceivably SARS-CoV-2. Recent phylogenetic analysis of the first 16 mink farms affected in the Netherlands hinted to a faster evolutionary rate of SARS-CoV-2 in the mink population in comparison with the evolutionary rate seen in humans (Oude Munnink et al., 2021). This might be explained by the comparatively higher metabolic rate of mustelids, multiple generations of infections before detection (Oude Munnink et al., 2021), plus the regular replenishment of naive animals and ease of transmission created by intensive production settings.

4 | FUTURE DIRECTIONS: ENHANCED SURVEILLANCE AND ROBUST CONTROL

The current worldwide population of farmed mink is approximately 60.5 million (WHO et al., 2021; see Figure 1). Since the first COVID-19 cases identified in mink in April 2020, over a year later, the number of mink farms reporting infection with SARS-CoV-2 by country is as follows: 69 in the Netherlands (OIE, 2021b); 290 in Denmark (Boklund et al., 2021; Fenollar et al., 2021); eight in Spain (OIE, 2021b); 17 in the USA (APHIS & USDA, 2021); 13 in Sweden (OIE, 2021b); one in Italy (OIE, 2021b); 23 in Greece (OIE, 2021b); one in France (OIE, 2021b); four in Lithuania (OIE, 2021b); three in Canada (OIE, 2021b); two in Poland (OIE, 2021b); and one in Latvia (OIE, 2021b).

Management of SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks has greatly differed between countries, ranging from a total ban on mink farming in the Netherlands, a temporary shutdown of the industry in Denmark, to quarantine, disinfection and increased biosecurity in the United States of America (see Box 3). In the Netherlands, the nationwide culls implemented in late 2020 and the bringing forward of an industry ban by 3 years (Bruschke, 2021) have decisively eliminated the risk associated with hosting a farmed mink reservoir for SARS-CoV-2. In Denmark, the 2021 industry shutdown was preceded by two epidemic phases that reached a peak in autumn 2020, closely following the COVID-19 human epidemic curve over the same period (Boklund et al., 2021). Over the course of the epidemic in Denmark, different control strategies were implemented (Boklund et al., 2021; see Box 3), yet at least a quarter of infected farms, including a farm reinfection, were identified by regular tests of in-farm personal and/or active surveillance within farms rather than by reliance on clinical signs or a rise in mortality among mink as prompts for testing (Boklund et al., 2021). In the USA, culls have not been implemented and case identification still relies on passive surveillance. Reports (see Box 3) of positive mink sampled in the field highlight the potential for establishment of this invasive species as a wild reservoir for SARS-CoV-2. Prospective comparative analysis of such varied SARS-CoV-2 mink outbreak responses would be most informative in the evaluation of its associated effectiveness in reducing viral spread.

Given the many consequences for public health of SARS-CoV-2 in farmed animals, a cohesive global response is needed consisting of surveillance of both spillover events and variants linked to mink farms, as well as effective control measures to combat unabated spread. A November 2020 statement by the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) urged countries to monitor and report COVID-19 cases in animals (OIE, 2020). Early detection of infection should be prioritized on mink farms through both passive and active monitoring via regular testing of animals and staff, subsequent sequencing of positive samples, and prompt communication of results (Boklund et al., 2021). Moreover, multi-species fur production units deserve special attention, particularly units raising mink, racoon dogs and/or rabbits. Inclusion of SARS-CoV-2 as an emergent multi-species infection in the list of OIE notifiable diseases should be considered to promote case reporting.

In addition to vaccination of human populations and concomitant prioritization of mink farm staff, there are many reasons to propose parallel obligatory vaccination of farmed mink populations. Accordingly, the first COVID-19 animal vaccine has been produced (Tétrault-Farber & Vasilyeva, 2021) plus further mink vaccine candidates are under development. In late 2020, the Russian Federal Centre for Animal Health conducted clinical trials of a vaccine candidate (Vasilyeva, 2020). By March 2021, this immunological product was registered for use in carnivores—dogs, cats, foxes and mink (Tétrault-Farber & Vasilyeva, 2021)—with initial pet vaccinations at veterinary clinics reported in May (BBC News, 2021). The Finnish Fur Breeders' Association in conjunction with the University of Helsinki also announced work towards a vaccine for mink and racoon dogs in January 2021 (FIFUR, 2021). Likewise, in January, the American drug company Zoetis supplied experimental vaccines under development for dogs, cats and mink, for emergency use in nonhuman primates at San Diego Zoo (Zoetis, 2021). Considering that mink farms harvest pelts destined to become luxury items of clothing, once these vaccine candidates reach commercial stage, industry profits could cover the costs associated with obligatory SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. In turn, vaccine profits raised by pharmaceuticals could be used to offset, for example, costs associated with expanding vaccine donation programmes to low- and middle-income countries.

To complement vaccination, other integrated interventions should also be considered to minimize the risk of mink farms acting as biotic hubs for SARS-CoV-2 transmission and evolution. Structural improvements may include revisions of animal density, proximity of enclosures and airflow in commercial mink units. Existing biosecurity challenges should be overcome; for instance, the role of cats, bats, rodents and birds as potential carriers of SARS-CoV-2 between farms and into wildlife warrants investigation. Moreover, implementation of improved welfare standards would address concerns over the conditions imposed on this territorial, solitary species during intensive production (Xia et al., 2020), and at the same time, have the potential to limit viral spread.

In order to enhance surveillance and implement adequate measures to control this highly transmissible and adaptable multi-host virus (MacLean et al., 2021), regulatory frameworks are needed. Imprecise estimates of the number, size and conditions of fur farms highlight the need for oversight, especially regarding the location of farms and surveillance activities (Koopmans, 2021). Surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 and other related viruses, not only of animal trade and markets but also of fur farms hosting COVID-19 susceptible species, would further enhance efforts to trace SARS-CoV-2 origins and perhaps help prevent future pandemics (WHO Team, 2021).

5 | CONCLUSIONS

The spread of SARS-CoV-2 in mustelid populations—particularly farmed mink—presents not just a zoonotic risk to humans, but more concerningly, a potential biotic hub where rampant transmission can facilitate the emergence of variants with enhanced virulence. The

strategies to monitor and control the spread of SARS-CoV-2 among mink have varied widely, and the virus remains in circulation in mink populations throughout the globe. A more comprehensive and coordinated global response is required to tackle infection in mustelids, and consequently, mitigate the risk of future animal and human coronavirus outbreaks.

KEYWORDS

biotic hub, evolution of virulence, farmed mink, one health, reverse zoonoses, SARS-CoV-2

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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B. Reaching the World Health Organization elimination targets for schistosomiasis: the importance of a One Health perspective

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Reaching the World Health Organization elimination targets for schistosomiasis: the importance of a One Health perspective

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The past three years has seen the launch of a new World Health Organization (WHO) neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) roadmap, together with revised control and elimination guidelines. Across all, there is now a clear emphasis on the need to incorporate a One Health approach, recognizing the critical links between human and animal health and the environment. Schistosomiasis, caused by *Schistosoma* spp. trematodes, is a NTD of global medical and veterinary importance, with over 220 million people and untold millions of livestock currently infected. Its burden remains extremely high in certain regions, particularly within sub-Saharan Africa, despite over two decades of mass preventive chemotherapy (mass drug administration), predominantly to school-aged children. In Africa, in contrast to Asia, any zoonotic component of schistosomiasis transmission and its implications for disease control has, until recently, been largely ignored. Here, we review recent epidemiological, clinical, molecular, and modelling work across both Asia and Africa. We outline the evolutionary history and transmission dynamics of *Schistosoma* species, and emphasize the emerging risk raised by both wildlife reservoirs and viable hybridization between human and animal schistosomes. To achieve the 2030 WHO roadmap elimination targets, a truly multi-disciplinary One Health perspective must be implemented.

This article is part of the theme issue 'Challenges and opportunities in the fight against neglected tropical diseases: a decade from the London Declaration on NTDs'.

1. Introduction

Momentum in the fight against neglected tropical diseases (NTDs), 20 epidemiologically complex conditions that predominantly affect impoverished communities [1], has been building alongside a change in targets from morbidity control to elimination. With renewed emphasis on the need to incorporate a One Health approach, 'an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimize the health of people, animals and ecosystems' [2, p. viii], the World Health Organization (WHO) has launched a series of documents over the past 3 years, including a revised 2021–2030 NTDs roadmap [3], a revised *Guideline on control and elimination of human schistosomiasis* [4], a companion One Health approach document for action against NTDs [2], a global strategy on water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) to combat NTDs [5], and a 2022–2026 *One Health joint plan of action* in conjunction with other international agencies [6]. These documents serve to embed One Health at the heart of control efforts for NTDs with significant environmental or zoonotic epidemiological characteristics and stress the importance of One Health in sustainably improving the intertwined health of humans, animals and their ecosystems [2].

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Schistosomiasis is among the most important NTDs and is estimated to infect a quarter of a billion people worldwide [7,8]. This debilitating parasitic disease is present in 78 tropical and subtropical countries, with major foci across Asia, Africa and South America [3], and a potentially emerging focus in southern Europe [9]. However, its burden is placed overwhelmingly on sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), where 90% of human schistosome infections occur [7,10,11], causing approximately 24 000 deaths and at least 2.5 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) [3]. The parasite's environmental infective stages—snail-infective miracidia and mammal-infective cercariae—are restricted to freshwater habitats of the snail intermediate host, thus schistosomiasis is considered a water-borne disease [5], with ongoing debates for and against its classification as a vector-borne disease [12,13]. Importantly, the clinical consequences of infection by schistosomes are experienced not only by humans, but also by non-human mammalian definitive hosts [14], many of which can act as reservoirs of subsequent human infection for certain schistosome species [15–17].

As of January 2020, of 78 endemic countries 51 are targeted for mass preventive chemotherapy (i.e. mass drug administration, MDA, using praziquantel) by WHO owing to moderate to high schistosome transmission [3]. The 2030 WHO schistosomiasis elimination goals call for its elimination as a public health problem (EHP) from all endemic countries—42 in Africa, ten in the Americas, three in Southeast Asia, six in the western Pacific, 16 in the eastern Mediterranean and one in Europe [18]—with EHP defined as less than 1% heavy-intensity infections (≥ 50 eggs per 10 ml urine or ≥ 400 eggs per gram of stool are indicative of a heavy-intensity infection [18]). After 20 years of large-scale MDA, morbidity profiles have shifted; thus a revised EHP definition based on overall infection prevalence instead of heavy-intensity infections has recently been advocated [19]. In addition to EHP, interruption of transmission (IoT) in 25 of the 78 endemic countries has also been set as a WHO schistosomiasis elimination goal, with IoT defined as absence of infection in humans [3]. WHO's EHP goal has been met in China since 2015 [20] but further national control efforts aim for transmission control as well as transmission interruption. Transmission control is defined by Chinese authorities as less than 1% infection prevalence in humans and livestock, plus two consecutive days of negative malacological surveys and no acute schistosomiasis cases [20]—although schistosomiasis is most commonly a chronic disease, an acute presentation has been described in humans [10] and livestock [21]. Transmission interruption is defined by Chinese authorities as absence of infection in humans, livestock and snails for five consecutive years [20].

The WHO roadmap [3] identifies a number of actions required to reach the schistosomiasis elimination targets, which include: more comprehensive MDA strategies (e.g. expanding to include more demographic groups, ensuring access to therapeutics, developing alternatives to praziquantel); snail control (e.g. developing appropriate guidelines for targeted snail control and alternative control methods); improved diagnostics—for humans and animals—for micro-mapping; and the creation of cross-sectoral mechanisms to coordinate key sectors like WASH, environmental management and animal health. The roadmap also expounds on the risk posed by zoonotic reservoirs in Asia and beyond, advocating wider use of veterinary public health interventions [3]. Specific points for consideration include improved

sanitation and management of animal waste, keeping animals away from transmission sites and treating animals with praziquantel. The companion One Health approach WHO document [2, p. xi] 'provides guidance on the One Health actions needed by major stakeholders and how to support a paradigm shift towards One Health in national NTD programmes', and is complemented by the *One Health joint plan of action* [6] framework to support and expand One Health capacities at global, regional, and national level. Hence, the One Health approach is now firmly embedded within WHO guidance on eliminating schistosomiasis.

Operationalizing One Health measures for zoonotic NTDs is nevertheless challenging (see [22]). For instance, despite long-standing knowledge of the effectiveness of anti-rabies dog vaccination in preventing human deaths [23], capacity building for mass dog vaccination is still a critical action required to reach the 2030 rabies elimination targets [3]. Moreover, the recent detection of *Dracunculus medinensis* infections in animals [24] has triggered a focus on emerging animal reservoirs to reach dracunculiasis eradication targets [3]. Indeed, there are now more infections recorded in non-human mammals (mostly domestic dogs, some domestic cats and a few baboons [25]) than in humans [24]. Interestingly, a non-classical transmission pathway in dogs likely contributing to disease persistence has been identified in Chad [25].

In this perspective, we first consider recent advancements in understanding the evolutionary history and transmission dynamics of *Schistosoma* spp., before outlining the emerging risk posed by wildlife and livestock reservoirs of infection and hybridization between human-infective and livestock-infective schistosomes. We then highlight the importance of adopting a One Health approach to eliminate schistosomiasis and discuss potential interventions targeting livestock in SSA that could facilitate progress towards elimination. Finally, we discuss the challenges and next steps associated with implementation of a One Health strategy.

(a) Natural history of *Schistosoma* spp.

The natural history of schistosomes has been marked by their expanding geographical range, host-switching and diversification. Modern molecular biology and genomics indicate an Asian origin of schistosomes, disfavoured the traditional African-origin hypothesis [14]. The prevailing 'out of Asia' theory detailed by Lawton *et al.* [14] posits that schistosomes evolved as parasites of rodents from an avian schistosomatid ancestor. The *Schistosoma japonicum* clade, which still retains distinct genomic similarities with avian parasites, is thought to be the antecedent of the genus [14]. Further speciation likely followed an additional host shift to ungulates that concurred with the diversification of their molluscan intermediate hosts [14]. Over 40 vertebrate species can serve as hosts for *S. japonicum* [10,15,26,27], a generalist strategy that may have helped preserve ancestral genomic features [14]. All three *S. japonicum* clade species responsible for human disease in Asia—*S. japonicum*, *Schistosoma mekongi* and *Schistosoma malayensis*—are zoonotic (i.e. transmitted between animals and humans) [26].

Schistosomes likely invaded Africa on at least two separate occasions [14]. The first occurrence gave rise to the *Schistosoma hippopotami* clade, including two species described from hippos. A second ancestral invasion during the radiation of mammals into Africa during the mid-Miocene caused a

population bottleneck that formed a proto-*Schistosoma mansoni* clade. This ultimately gave rise to two distinct clades of African schistosomes, the *S. mansoni* clade and the *Schistosoma haematobium* clade [14]. The more ancestral *S. mansoni* clade comprises two species that parasitize rodents, *Schistosoma rodhaini* and *S. mansoni* [28]. The latter species is the predominant cause of human intestinal schistosomiasis in SSA and also infects non-human primates [10,29–34] (for a review on non-human primate *S. mansoni* reservoirs in Africa see [35]), although it is often classed as an exclusively human parasite [36]. The Atlantic slave trade is thought responsible for the geographical expansion of *S. mansoni* to the Caribbean and South America [37,38]. The more recent *S. haematobium* clade comprises nine species, including the human-infective species *S. haematobium*, *Schistosoma intercalatum* and *Schistosoma guineensis*, and the species of veterinary health importance causing ruminant intestinal schistosomiasis, *Schistosoma bovis*, *Schistosoma curassoni* and *Schistosoma mattheei*, with the remaining species, *Schistosoma margrebowiei*, *Schistosoma leiperi* and *Schistosoma kisumuensis*, mostly found in wildlife [39–42]. The postulated reinvasion of Asia from Africa by the *Schistosoma indicum* clade, formed of three species of veterinary significance, did not involve a host switch but the continued parasitization of ungulates and rodents [14].

Despite the prevailing perception of schistosomiasis as a predominantly human disease [10,36], the *Schistosoma* genus has shown a remarkable ability to diverge and adapt to new hosts and habitats that has persisted beyond its evolutionary origins. This is evident not only among members of the Asian *S. japonicum* clade, but also among several species of both African clades, as exemplified by the establishment and persistence of *S. mansoni* in the Caribbean [38,43,44], and the recent expansion of *S. haematobium* × *S. bovis* hybrids into Europe ([45] but see [9]). This adaptability presents increasingly recognized challenges to the control and elimination of schistosomiasis and epitomizes the necessity for a holistic One Health approach.

(b) Hybridization between *Schistosoma* species

Concerns about *Schistosoma* hybridization were initially raised by phenotypic observations of unusual egg and worm morphologies deemed to present intermediate characteristics of different species [21,39,46,47], as well as changes in cercarial emergence and shedding patterns [48]. Subsequently, enzymatic studies [39,49–51], and crucially, molecular techniques, have uncovered strong evidence of the interspecific hybridization of schistosomes [28,39,52–55]. Interbreeding between different species can result in the creation of hybrid offspring (hybridization) or, if backcrossing of an interspecific hybrid with a parent species occurs, in the introduction of single chromosomal regions or genes from one species to the other (introgressive hybridization, also known as introgression) [33,56,57]. Such processes can drive genetic variation, with the potential to alter the morbidity, host range, and drug susceptibility of parasites [33,53,57].

Phylogenetically close schistosome species with overlapping endemicity are more amenable to hybridization. Nonetheless, whilst cases of natural hybridization between *S. japonicum* clade species have not been found [39], instances of likely non-viable hybridization between distantly related *S. mansoni* with *S. haematobium* have been recorded in humans

in Mali [58], Cameroon [59], Senegal [60], Côte d'Ivoire [61] and Kenya [62]. Although, *S. mansoni* clade hybrids have been found in snails in Tanzania [63] and Kenya [28], most evidence of schistosome hybridization involves species within the *S. haematobium* clade, with such interspecific hybrids having been recorded across SSA (table 1; for a review on *Schistosoma* hybridizations see [39]).

The interspecific mixing of *S. haematobium* with *S. bovis* has been highlighted in several West African foci [55,75] (table 1). Within different areas of the Senegal River basin, a schistosomiasis hotspot, a heterogeneous distribution of *S. haematobium* × *S. bovis* hybrids has been reported [72], and a positive association between the frequency of such hybrids and the prevalence of *S. mansoni* has been identified (i.e. higher risk of hybrid infection in villages with high *S. mansoni* prevalence) [72]. A possible explanation for this association is the increased susceptibility of humans to livestock-infective schistosomes following pure or mixed *S. mansoni* infection [72]. Active immune response suppression caused by *S. mansoni* is hypothesized to facilitate infection with *S. bovis* or F1 hybrids, consequently driving hybrid transmission [72]. The observed geographical heterogeneity in *S. haematobium* × *S. bovis* hybrid distribution may be explained by: water contact behaviour and immunology of the host; compatibility of hybrids with the locally predominant snail species; more intensive livestock rearing around the shores of Lac de Guiers (where most hybrids have been found); and ongoing selection of *S. bovis* introgressed genes due to their possible adaptive benefits [72].

Interestingly, since 2013, a hybrid *S. haematobium* × *S. bovis* isolate likely originating from West Africa seems to have adapted successfully to the local snail and human population in Corsica, France [76]. This hybrid strain has caused several outbreaks of human schistosomiasis in Corsica without an apparent need for animal reservoirs [76,77]. Overwintering of the Corsica hybrid schistosome strain within the local snail host has been recently demonstrated, providing a potential explanation of local persistence in this newly established focus [78]. Previous single-species infection studies in baboons produced *S. mattheei* eggs but no *S. bovis* eggs [79] nor *S. curassoni* eggs [80], suggesting the latter two livestock-specific schistosomes may require heterospecific mixing to produce viable offspring in humans [47]. However, recent evidence of 'pure' *S. bovis* viable human infection in Nigeria [71] has proven that this species can in fact develop fully as a single species in people. Furthermore, contrary to prevailing thought on the epidemiology of hybridizations between livestock- and human-associated *S. haematobium* clade schistosomes, recent studies carried out in West Africa have demonstrated that human infection by *S. bovis* hybrids is common (table 1).

Genome-wide restriction-site-associated DNA sequencing (RADseq) has shown an increased fitness and viability (so-called hybrid vigour) of *S. haematobium* clade hybrids, which may at least partially explain the change in endemic landscape over a period of 25 years from predominantly intestinal (caused by *S. guineensis*) to urogenital human cases in sympatric regions of Central Africa [55]. Furthermore, recent genomic studies have found *S. haematobium* clade hybridizations to be both ancient [81] and ongoing [82]. Both hybrid vigour and the rise in interspecific schistosome encounters, facilitated by the increased movement of people and animals, will likely increase the frequency

Table 1. Hybrids between species of the *Schistosoma haematobium* clade recently reported across sub-Saharan Africa.

reported <i>S. haematobium</i> clade interspecific hybrid combination ^a	host infected by the schistosome hybrid	type of sample evaluated for molecular evidence	country	reference ^b
<i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. haematobium</i>	human	miracidia	Benin	[48]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	rodent	miracidia, plus snail infection	Benin	[64]
<i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. haematobium</i>	ruminant (cattle)	miracidia, plus snail infection	Benin	[48]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i> ; and <i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. haematobium</i>	human	miracidia	Cameroon	[65]
<i>S. guineensis</i> × <i>S. haematobium</i> ; and <i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	human/snail	sequencing of F1 male worms (field samples used in rodent laboratory infection)	Cameroon	[55]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	human	miracidia	Côte d'Ivoire	[66]
<i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. haematobium</i>	snail	cercariae	Côte d'Ivoire	[67]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. mattheei</i> ; and <i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	human	atypical eggs	Malawi	[68]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	human	atypical eggs from travellers	Mali	[69]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	human/snail	sequencing of F1 male worms (field samples used in rodent laboratory infection)	Mali	[55]
<i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. curassoni</i> ; and <i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. curassoni</i>	human	miracidia	Niger	[47]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i> ; and <i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. curassoni</i>	snail	cercariae	Niger	[70]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	human	miracidia	Nigeria	[71]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	human/snail	sequencing of F1 male worms (field samples used in rodent laboratory infection)	Nigeria	[55]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	human	miracidia	Senegal	[72]
<i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. haematobium</i>	human	miracidia	Senegal	[16]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	snail	cercariae	Senegal	[16]
<i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i>	rodent	female worm	Senegal	[73]
<i>S. bovis</i> × <i>S. curassoni</i>	ruminant (cattle, sheep, goat)	miracidia	Senegal	[16]
<i>S. mattheei</i> × <i>S. haematobium</i>	human	sera from travellers (acute cases), followed by sequencing	South Africa	[74]

^aHybrid combination as reported in reference.

^bReported since Leger & Webster [39].

of hybridizations as interventions are intensified to meet elimination goals [57].

(c) Importance of a One Health approach

Several schistosome species are currently widely recognized as zoonotic, particularly livestock-infective species of the *S. japonicum* clade in Asia. In Africa, livestock-infective species of the *S. haematobium* clade (i.e. *S. bovis*, *S. curassoni* and *S. mattheei*) which tend to hybridize with *S. haematobium* can also be classified as zoonotic, though the significance of domestic ruminants as reservoirs for human transmission is yet to be clarified [75,83]. Land use change, climate change, and

expanding trade, migration and mobility will likely increase parasite hybridization as well as zoonotic spillover [82]. The introduction of schistosomes into new habitats can be mediated by the livestock trade (e.g. the recent discovery of *S. bovis* in Zanzibar [84]), economic migration and displacement and indeed tourism (e.g. in 2017 a cluster of acute cases was reported in Belgian travellers returning from South Africa and associated with *S. mattheei* and *S. haematobium* hybridization [74]). The increased migration of animals and/or humans in conjunction with man-made ecological change (e.g. dam construction, irrigation systems, agriculture and deforestation) will continue altering schistosomes' geographical range, further complicating control efforts [2].

In China, where sustained control efforts (including livestock interventions) have successfully eliminated *S. japonicum* from many endemic foci, the risk of resurgence from both domestic and wildlife animals remains an ongoing challenge (e.g. in 2014, the infection prevalence documented in rodents, goats and dogs was above 9% in Hunan province [85]). Elsewhere, the finding in 2019 of a green monkey infected with *S. mansoni* in St Kitts—where schistosomiasis was thought to have been eliminated in the 1970s—raises several questions, including reintroduction of the parasite to the island, or the existence of a sylvatic cycle maintained by non-human primates [43].

The role of wild rodents as reservoirs of zoonotic schistosomes is being progressively uncovered, with rodents found to be infected with *S. mansoni* in the Caribbean [44,86], Brazil [87] and Africa [73,88,89]. Moreover, in Africa, where the majority of intestinal (caused by *S. mansoni*) and urogenital (caused by *S. haematobium*) human schistosomiasis cases occur, wild rodents have been confirmed to be naturally infected with *S. bovis* and *S. haematobium* clade hybrids [64,73]. Importantly, infected livestock are also relevant sources of zoonotic spillover, particularly, cattle infected with *S. bovis* [16,17].

Approximately 12 million people have been estimated to be at risk of zoonotic schistosomiasis in Asia [90]. Such estimates are yet to be produced for Africa. Resolving the nature of multi-host transmission at a local level remains challenging [91], though recent modelling work [15,17,57] highlights the emerging risk of zoonotic hybrids and other zoonotic schistosomes in Africa [83] and questions whether the traditional top-down, human-centric approach to control and elimination is suitable [92]. Increased understanding of the population structure of schistosomes and their response to selective pressures induced by MDA requires interdisciplinary work, including a combination of molecular, epidemiological and modelling analyses [93]. Given the noteworthy high prevalence of *S. bovis* genes in parasites recently recovered from Nigerian children [71], there is a pressing need to more completely understand the population structure and transmission dynamics of schistosomes infecting African livestock [94] and their spatio-temporal distribution, particularly where zoonotic hybrid prevalence is highest [72]. Similarly, the role of rodents, non-human primates and other relevant animal species warrants further research.

Improved understanding of the eco-epidemiology of schistosomiasis at the human–animal interface and the economic and sociological factors affecting the feasibility and effectiveness of control interventions has been recently proposed as policy pillars for the sustainable elimination of zoonotic schistosomiasis [90]. Zoonotic *S. japonicum* clade and *S. haematobium* clade schistosomes, as well as species that cause animal schistosomiasis, ought to be considered when setting animal health and veterinary public health goals to accompany existing public health elimination goals [3]. Furthermore, the genital pathology of other *S. haematobium* clade species besides *S. haematobium* in urogenital schistosomiasis cases in women and men must be elucidated, including the risk of genital forms of disease from zoonotic hybrids.

(d) Targeting livestock schistosomiasis in sub-Saharan Africa

Interventions to tackle the emerging risk of zoonotic hybrids in Africa include preventing susceptible livestock from coming into contact with contaminated water bodies (e.g. by providing

drinking water in troughs, contamination of communal water with livestock faeces could be minimized [95]), treatment of infected livestock and limiting interaction with wildlife [83]. Reliance on other proposed interventions such as replacement of livestock (e.g. for agricultural management of wetlands) [83] may not be advisable, given schistosomes' tendency for host-switching and range of potential animal reservoirs. For instance, in the case of *S. japonicum*, buffaloes, cattle and horses are considered main reservoirs in parts of Indonesia [96], whereas transmission between dogs and humans and between rodents and humans has been reported, respectively, in areas of the Philippines [97] and China [98].

A key unresolved question for the establishment of a comprehensive One Health strategy is whether extending praziquantel treatment to relevant animal reservoirs in SSA would be epidemiologically and economically beneficial [34]. For example, in 2022, a study assessing the financial impact of livestock schistosomiasis on subsistence farmers of northern Senegal indicated that the impact of withholding interventions substantially surpassed the cost of testing and treatment [99]. Such findings indicate that there is a significant economic burden placed on traditional farmers by this disease, and thus favour, from an economic standpoint, the extension of praziquantel treatment to livestock in SSA.

The use of praziquantel for livestock schistosomiasis is already thought to be widespread in parts of SSA [34,99], but misuse is reported widely, with farmers often employing sub-therapeutic doses, inappropriate products instead of suitable veterinary formulations, and incomplete treatment regimens. Thus, while there exists demand for livestock schistosomiasis control, there is a need for a structured approach [100]. Initial exploration of a herd-level test-and-treat (TnT) approach for cattle using a mathematical transmission model suggests that up to 75% of bovine case-years in highly endemic settings and up to 85% of bovine case-years in lower transmission contexts could be averted [100]. The potential impact of TnT interventions could thus be substantial. There remain several outstanding challenges before TnT interventions could be implemented, including the availability of sensitive and specific point-of-care diagnostics [3,75] (see [101] for a systematic review and meta-analysis of diagnostics for non-human schistosomiasis) and suitable veterinary formulations [100]. Moreover, a TnT approach can only partially mitigate the risk of promoting drug resistance, an ominous spectre given the exclusive reliance on praziquantel for the treatment of human and animal schistosomiasis (table 2). Nonetheless, the clear contribution of cattle to spillover infections in humans and subsequent enhanced risks of hybridization, in addition to the operational feasibility of such an intervention in livestock (compared with wild animals), plus the economic benefits for impoverished communities, justify development of a comprehensive control strategy focused on domestic ruminants [100].

The efficacy of praziquantel against livestock schistosomiasis—cattle and small ruminants (sheep and goats)—is a long-standing pending research need that must be answered if a One Health treatment approach is to be safely implemented, with additional knowledge gaps including ruminant species-specific praziquantel pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics, drug bioavailability and ideal administration route. Commercial veterinary formulations for the treatment of livestock schistosomiasis with praziquantel are not currently widely available in SSA [34]. Hence, enhanced and alternative

Table 2. Concepts and considerations regarding mitigating the risk of emerging resistance to praziquantel.

anthelmintic resistance	Anthelmintic resistance is a heritable change that allows the survival of parasites when exposed to previously efficacious doses of chemotherapy [102]. Emergence of resistance occurs as the selective advantage of drug-resistant strains progressively surpasses that of the wild-type and is established if the resistant phenotype remains able to be transmitted between hosts [102]. Over-reliance on a single anthelmintic drug (praziquantel) and current lack of pharmaceutical alternatives for the treatment of schistosomiasis [103] increases the vulnerability of control and elimination programmes to emerging resistance. There remains no conclusive evidence for the emergence of praziquantel resistance in natural schistosome populations, although instances of reduced efficacy (e.g. for <i>S. mansoni</i> human infection in Uganda [104]) and unsatisfactory clinical improvement (e.g. for <i>S. haematobium</i> clade human infection caused by interspecific hybrids in Senegal [105]) have been reported.
veterinary use of anthelmintics	The use of anthelmintics in the veterinary field is thought to increase the risk of emerging drug resistance [34], owing in part to the unstructured way in which drugs are administered in some settings. A structured test-and-treat approach [100] has potential to partly counteract such risks, although the risk of emerging resistance can never be completely avoided [102]. Notwithstanding, even after decades of extensive praziquantel use in livestock in China, no evidence of drug resistance under field conditions has been reported to date [102].
evolutionary pressure of interventions and presence of zoonotic hybrids	A bidirectional effect between the evolutionary pressure of control interventions and the presence of zoonotic hybrids is probable [57], with potential impacts including reduced praziquantel efficacy and changing morbidity profiles [57], as recently reported in people infected with <i>S. haematobium</i> × <i>S. bovis</i> hybrids in Senegal [105], in addition to a potentially heightened role of animals in transmission as prevalence in humans decreases [15,57].
laboratory schistosomes response to selective pressures	Laboratory studies (see [102]) have produced changes in schistosome fecundity, virulence, drug susceptibility, infectivity, and population genetics [106–114] within a few generations and using a range of selective pressures. How such experimental laboratory studies translate to natural populations remains unclear.
refugia of drug-susceptible genes	Untreated zoonotic reservoirs may act as refugia—a pool of drug-susceptible genes that can dilute resistant genes—which slow the emergence of drug resistance [33,34]. Refugia arise within untreated individuals in the at-risk populations and other animal species relevant to the parasite's life cycle, and perhaps even immature schistosomes that are not susceptible to praziquantel [102]. The size and relevance of refugia will vary depending on the transmission dynamics of the schistosome species. For example, since <i>S. japonicum</i> has several vertebrate hosts that can act as refugia, it is proposed that there exists a low likelihood of emerging resistance [102].
emerging drug resistance	Mass drug administration can exert a sufficiently strong population-level selective pressure for the evolution of resistant strains [102], with repeated chemotherapy predicted to exert selective pressures that favour parasite resistance alleles [115]. The emergence of resistance, especially when it is a recessive trait, tends to follow a sigmoid-type temporal dynamic and therefore is often identified only during or after the exponential-type growth phase that follows an initial slow rise [102]. This underlines the importance of early detection to give time for mitigating interventions to be implemented. Relaxation of constraining density-dependent processes (e.g. on parasite fecundity) after chemotherapy can enhance the spread of drug resistance, depending on the particular density-dependent process at play [115].

supply lines of praziquantel for veterinary usage will also require development to meet the increased demand.

Current estimates of the prevalence and geographical extent of livestock schistosomiasis are incomplete [16] and require a comprehensive epidemiological mapping approach to redress [34]. Crucial information at a local level on domestic ruminants' exposure to contaminated water sources

will further prospects for the design and implementation of strategies that complement treatment by mitigating re-infection. Continuous surveillance and monitoring to detect early signs of emerging resistance in both humans and animals are also paramount to safeguard praziquantel. Such activities would include monitoring prevalence, clinical outcomes and drug efficacy (e.g. egg reduction rates),

assessment of temporospatial genetic diversity, population structure and gene flow, and measurement of allele frequency changes mediated by treatment [102] (table 2).

Currently, there are no commercially available schistosomiasis vaccines for either humans or animals [26,83], although this is an active area of research and development (for recent reviews see [116] and [117]), which could potentially radically shift approaches towards control and elimination [118]. The development of anti-schistosome animal vaccines began in the 1970s with *S. matthei*-irradiated larvae found to be as immunogenic in sheep as natural challenge [119], and with *S. bovis*-irradiated larvae found to be protective against natural challenge in cattle (higher growth rate, reduced worm burden and reduced egg output in vaccinated animals compared with controls) [117,120]. These initial attempts were followed in the 1980s by a cryopreserved radiation-attenuated schistosomula vaccine against *S. bovis* in sheep [121], as well as irradiated *S. japonicum* vaccines in mice, pigs, sheep, cattle and buffaloes of China [122,123]. More recent efforts have focused on the use of recombinant DNA vaccine technology for livestock (mostly testing three antigens: glutathione S-transferases, paramyosin and triose-phosphate isomerase) given its antibody- and cellular immunity-inducing properties, its cost, and logistical advantages of field deployment without relying on a cold-chain [117]. Despite the encouraging results of early live-attenuated *S. bovis* and *S. matthei* livestock vaccine candidates, the lack of recently published studies [117] highlights a delay in progress and an unmet One Health research need.

(e) One Health, environmental management and WASH

Implementation of water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) measures (i.e. safe water supply, personal cleanliness and hand-washing, access to facilities and services for the safe disposal of urine and faeces [5]), snail control and environmental management interventions, can reduce schistosome transmission and benefit the health of people, animals and ecosystems. However, the success of differing interventions will vary according to the local context. For instance, while chemical snail control with niclosamide molluscicide formulations resulted in a substantial reduction of snail populations in China, its use in Laos did not have a significant impact [26]. Moreover, molluscicide environmental contamination might preclude its use in other countries and hence more sustainable alternatives like environmental modification (e.g. concreting canals and/or vegetation removal in the snail habitat, land use change to avoid flood irrigation) and/or biological control (e.g. introduction of snail predators) could be explored in these contexts. In fact, the elimination of *S. japonicum* in Japan predated praziquantel and relied on snail population reduction

through environmental modification associated with rapid economic development, in combination with health education and animal reservoir control [26].

Key hygiene and sanitation deficiencies within Africa persist, including lack of sewage infrastructure (affecting two thirds of the continent's population) and no access to clean water (endured by almost half of the population in Africa) [83]. Robust long-term measures to tackle such challenges would greatly enhance the prospects of widespread and sustained elimination of schistosomiasis and other water-borne diseases. While a One Health approach has a role to play in improving this situation, it will ultimately require continued economic development, political commitment, and stability. It remains to be seen whether elimination of schistosomiasis can be achieved without such wholesale progress.

2. Conclusion

The importance of One Health to the control and elimination of NTDs has gained increased recognition through its integration into the WHO 2030 NTD roadmap [3] and companion documents [2,4,5]. The evolutionary history of schistosomes as multi-host parasites which continue to readily hybridize and adapt exemplifies the particular importance of One Health to the effectiveness and success of interventions targeting elimination. One Health approaches—which encompass the treatment and/or vaccination of livestock, environmental management, and snail control—will be integral to reducing the risk of zoonotic spillover and mitigating the risk of resurgence in human populations and improving the economic prospects and livelihoods of communities that depend on healthy livestock. Many challenges remain to the sustainable implementation of such approaches, but this should not detract from the importance of embracing One Health to combat schistosomiasis and other NTDs.

Data accessibility. This article has no additional data.

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All authors gave final approval for publication and agreed to be held accountable for the work performed herein.

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C. Modelling livestock test-and-treat: A novel One Health strategy to control schistosomiasis and mitigate drug resistance

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Modelling livestock test-and-treat: A novel One Health strategy to control schistosomiasis and mitigate drug resistance

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Schistosomiasis, a neglected tropical disease, is a widespread chronic helminthiasis reported in 78 countries, predominantly those within sub-Saharan Africa, as well as Latin America, Asia, and most recently, even Europe. Species of the causative blood fluke infect not only humans but also animals, and hybrids between previously assumed human-specific and animal-specific schistosomes are being increasingly reported. Existing control programs across Africa focus on humans and rely heavily on mass drug administration of praziquantel, the sole drug available against schistosomiasis. Praziquantel is safe and highly efficacious but could become ineffective if resistance emerges. To reach the revised World Health Organization goal of elimination of schistosomiasis as a public health problem, and interruption of transmission within selected regions, by 2030, new consideration of the role of animal reservoirs in human transmission in general, and whether to also treat livestock with praziquantel in particular, has been raised. However, whilst there are no dedicated control programs targeting animals outside of Asia, there are emerging reports of the use and misuse of praziquantel in livestock across Africa. Therefore, to effectively treat livestock in Africa and to help mitigate against the potential evolution of praziquantel resistance, structured control strategies are required. Here, using a transmission modelling approach, we evaluate the potential effectiveness of a theoretical test-and-treat (TnT) strategy to control bovine schistosomiasis using a currently available point-of-care diagnostic test (developed for human use) to detect circulating cathodic antigen (POC-CCA). We show that implementing TnT at herd-level from 2022 to 2030

could be highly effective in suppressing infection in cattle and even, in lower prevalence settings, reaching nominal 'elimination' targets. We highlight the importance of enhancing the specificity of POC-CCA for use in livestock to avoid unnecessary treatments and discuss the outstanding challenges associated with implementing TrT as part of a holistic One Health approach to tackling human and animal schistosomiasis.

KEYWORDS

modelling, schistosomiasis, livestock, test-and-treat, One Health

Introduction

A substantial proportion of the world's disease burden is caused by infectious agents that lead to high mortality, morbidity, and reduced productivity among millions of people and their animals. Schistosomiasis is a major freshwater-snail-borne neglected tropical disease (NTD) caused by blood flukes of the genus *Schistosoma*. This parasitic disease remains a major public health problem in the majority of 78 tropical and subtropical countries, infecting >240 million people (1–3), 90% living in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (2, 4).

Current global efforts to control human schistosomiasis rely predominantly on mass drug administration (MDA), whereby populations (mainly school-aged children) are mass treated with the donated anthelmintic, praziquantel (PZQ). Praziquantel is safe, highly efficacious, and can be administered easily. Consequently, MDA programs have had, in general, major impacts on reducing infection prevalence, intensity and morbidity (2, 3, 5–7). The success of such activities has led the World Health Organization (WHO) to set revised targets for the 'elimination as a public health problem' (EHP) (<1% heavy intensity infections) of schistosomiasis in all affected countries, together with interruption of transmission within selected regions, by 2030 (8). The potential role of schistosomiasis in animals does, however, raise significant challenges for achieving these goals, and stresses the critical need for a One Health approach globally.

Traditionally, only the Asian schistosome species *S. japonicum* and *S. mekongi* were widely acknowledged as zoonotic (9). Domestic animals, notably bovines, have been suggested as responsible for up to 97% of schistosomiasis japonica disease transmission in Marshland regions of China (10). Consequently, China has performed integrated mass PZQ treatment of both humans and bovines, as well as improvements to water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH), replacement of bovines with tractors, and has attempted to develop a bovine vaccine. These sustained efforts have yielded great progress: from being a country with the highest schistosomiasis burden in the

1950s to, since 2015, reaching their EHP goal (11). Indeed, the overall prevalence of *S. japonicum* in China is now <1% in both humans and livestock populations (11, 12), and the majority of endemic provinces have either reached the Chinese authorities criteria of transmission control [i.e., under 1% infection prevalence in humans and livestock, in addition to negative local malacological surveys in two consecutive days plus absence of acute schistosomiasis cases (11)] or transmission interruption [i.e.: no infections in humans or livestock for five consecutive years, in addition to absence of infected intermediate snails for at least five years (11)].

In contrast, the role of animal schistosomiasis in SSA, in terms of either zoonotic risk or economic impact has, until very recently, been largely ignored, and there are no formal anti-schistosome control nor donation programs involving animals. Livestock schistosomiasis caused by *S. bovis*, *S. curassoni* and/or *S. matthei* in cattle, sheep and goats is, however, prevalent across SSA (9, 13). Furthermore, while human urogenital schistosomiasis was previously thought to be solely caused by the human-specific parasite *S. haematobium*, an ever-growing number of molecular studies have identified viable hybrids between this species and co-endemic livestock-specific parasites (9, 14–21), shed in the urine of human patients of several SSA countries including Senegal (14, 16, 21), Niger (20), Benin (17), Malawi (15), Côte d'Ivoire (18) and Nigeria (19). Notably, *S. bovis* hybrids appear to be common among infected children in locations of Senegal (72% *S. haematobium* - *S. bovis* hybrid prevalence) (16) and Nigeria (89% *S. bovis* - *S. haematobium* hybrid prevalence) (19), with 'pure' *S. bovis* human infections recently confirmed in Côte d'Ivoire (18) and Nigeria (19). A case of hybridized livestock *S. bovis* with *S. curassoni* viably infecting a child in Niger has also been identified (20). Interestingly, a hybridized *S. haematobium* - *S. bovis* zoonotic strain likely introduced from either Senegal (22, 23) or Benin (17, 23) appears to be now established within Corsica, Europe (23, 24).

These findings demonstrate that there is an important zoonotic component of schistosomiasis transmission in SSA,

and one which has been predicted to be of increasing importance as elimination programs targeting humans intensify (25). Additionally, there are highly important, if also often overlooked, animal welfare, productivity, and socioeconomic impacts of animal schistosomiasis, which further jeopardize livelihoods, food security and nutrition amongst neglected communities (26, 27). Schistosome infection in cattle, though often classed as sub-clinical, has been associated with diarrhea, anemias, weight loss, growth retardation, susceptibility to infection, and/or intestinal and hepatic lesions (13, 28, 29). Similar, or often more severe, morbidity (and mortality), combined with reduced productivity profiles have also recently been reported in infected sheep and goats (26, 27). Indeed, the financial impact projected over one year of withholding livestock schistosomiasis interventions was recently predicted to be substantial, where its costs surpassed those of testing and treating suspected cases in Northern Senegal (27).

The importance of veterinary public health interventions in achieving the WHO elimination 2030 targets has now been acknowledged in both the newly launched WHO NTD Roadmap 2021-2030 (8) and the Schistosomiasis Guideline for control and elimination of human schistosomiasis (30, 31). Amongst challenges identified to reach this goal are gaps in the scientific understanding of zoonotic transmission and implementation of effective interventions to address zoonotic reservoirs, as well as critical actions regarding diagnostics development, including standardized point-of-care (POC) tests (8). It is unlikely that an equivalent MDA strategy as used in humans would be deemed acceptable for livestock because of the potential risk of promoting the emergence of PZQ resistance. This is critical, given there is now resistance to all known veterinary anthelmintics globally (32), and any exacerbation of the risk of emerging resistance is particularly pertinent for schistosomiasis as PZQ is the only efficacious drug for both humans and livestock.

Nevertheless, recent work indicates already widespread use and misuse of PZQ in livestock—including, but not exclusive to, PZQ tablets donated *via* the WHO MDA programs for school-aged children, with little knowledge of application or dosage requirements (26). Indeed, more than a third of respondents in a recent survey within Senegal stated that they had given anti-schistosomiasis treatment to their livestock within the preceding four years (27). Such documented indiscriminate PZQ use against schistosomes of domestic ruminants highlights a previously unforeseen yet existing demand for animal disease control. A critical need to develop a structured approach for the treatment of livestock schistosomiasis in SSA is thus evident.

A test-and-treat (TnT, and/or the related *T3: Test, Treat, Track*) design for controlling livestock schistosomiasis would anchor the key recent WHO policy recommendations on diagnostic testing, treatment and surveillance in general

(8, 30). Such a strategy would enable local veterinarians, veterinary technicians and/or community leaders within endemic countries to easily and inexpensively assess whether a herd is infected with schistosomiasis and only then distribute appropriately dosed PZQ. Such a policy could minimize the costs and suffering to the livestock and their owners, and at the same time mitigate the risk of promoting the emergence of PZQ resistance as compared to either PZQ misuse or an MDA approach of treating all herds irrespective of their infection status. Here, we evaluate the impact of a theoretical herd-level TnT intervention targeting bovine schistosomiasis running from 2022 through 2030 using a mathematical transmission model. We use our recent epidemiological data on the prevalence of bovine schistosomiasis collected in farming locations of Northern Senegal to inform model parameterization and we discuss our findings in terms of their theoretical and applied implications for integrated One Health schistosomiasis disease control and elimination policy and practice.

Materials and methods

Ethical statement

Ethical approval for the fieldwork was provided by: (i) Imperial College London (London, UK) application 03.36; (ii) the CRERB at the Royal Veterinary College (London, UK) application URN20151327; and (iii) the Comité National d'Ethique pour la Recherche en Santé (Dakar, Senegal) application SEN15/68. Written informed consent was obtained from all livestock owners. Livestock owners were offered standard anthelmintics for infected animals.

Parasitological data

Prevalence estimates presented here focus on data from cattle (live *Bos taurus*, *Bos indicus* and cross breeds) coprological surveys conducted in 2017 in the Senegal River Basin area of northern Senegal, West Africa, as part of the Zoonoses and Emerging Livestock System (ZELS) program (16, 25). In this human schistosomiasis endemic area, Richard Toll and Lac de Guiers (estimated urogenital schistosomiasis prevalence in children and adults was 87% and 79% in 2016, and 88% and 41% in 2017-18, respectively (16)), henceforth referred to as RT, schistosome transmission is perennial due to the year-round persistence of freshwater habitats for intermediate snail hosts (i.e., the Senegal River and the Lac de Guiers lake) (16).

Faecal samples from 200 sympatric live-sampled bovines in eight RT site locations (Didjiery; Mbane; Medina Cheikhou; Ndombo; Sanente; Temeye; Thiago and Yetti Yone) were

collected following randomized protocols and processed using two schistosomiasis tests: Kato-Katz (KK) for presence of *Schistosoma* spp. eggs (examination of two slides per sample), and an adapted Miracidial Hatching Technique (MHT) to determine egg viability (and also used as an alternative diagnostic for the presence of eggs). Protocols for both techniques are described elsewhere (16).

Prevalence estimates derived from the results of both coprological exams informed the prevalence range explored in the modelled TnT strategy (Figure 1) using an imperfect semiquantitative POC diagnostic measuring urine levels of the adult worm gut-associated circulating cathodic antigen (CCA), hereby referred to as POC-CCA (33). This POC diagnostic is ordinarily employed for *S. mansoni* human-endemicity mapping given its superior sensitivity in comparison to the reference standard KK (34). Preliminary sensitivity and specificity estimates of POC-CCA using Bayesian latent class approaches based on bovine urine samples collected during the ZELS program (35)—where the overwhelming majority of infected cattle shed *S. bovis* (16)—were used for modelling TnT (Table 1). These POC-CCA performance estimates were based on the interpretation of a positive result as indicative of an infected animal, and of a negative result as indicative of an uninfected animal (positive cut-off value: \geq trace, i.e., trace, +, ++ or +++ (35)).

Prevalence estimation

The KK and MHT data were modelled as two independent Bernoulli-distributed variables conditional on the location-

specific prevalence, π_i , and the sensitivity, se , and specificity, sp , of the respective diagnostics. Therefore, the probability that an individual tests positive for each diagnostic is

$$P(+) = se \times \pi_i + (1 - sp)(1 - \pi_i) \quad (1)$$

The sensitivity of each test was assigned an informative beta prior parameterized using published performance values (16) such that the median and central 95% percentile was 0.31 (0.16 – 0.49) for KK and 0.79 (0.60– 0.91) for MHT. The specificity of both tests was assumed to be 1 (i.e., 100%). The prevalence in each location was estimated using a Bayesian Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approach using the JAGS program (JAGS version 4.3.0) called with the rjags package version 4-12 (38) for R version 4.0.2 (39).

Herd-level transmission model

We developed a simple deterministic mathematical transmission model based on that originally published by Anderson and May (36, 40) to track the mean number of schistosomes per host (worm burden), $W(t)$, during a TnT intervention. The model is defined by a single ordinary differential equation,

$$\frac{dW(t)}{dt} = \frac{R_0(\mu_0 + \mu_1)\mu_2 W(t)\Phi(W(t),k)}{R_{H \rightarrow S}(\mu_0 + \mu_1)(N_1/N_2)W(t)\Phi(W(t),k) + \mu_2} - (\mu_0 + \mu_1)W(t) \quad (2)$$

where μ_0 and μ_1 denote the cattle and schistosome mortality rates respectively and the environmental and intermediate host

TABLE 1 Fixed and varied parameters used within the herd-level transmission model.

Parameter	Definition	Value	Reference
<i>Fixed parameters</i>			
μ_0	Mortality rate of definitive host (1/average life expectancy in years)	1/5	Approximate average age of ZELS study cattle – 5 years (mean=4.49; sd=3.63; n=343)
μ_1	Mortality rate of adult schistosomes within definitive host (1/average life expectancy years)	1/5	(36)
μ_2	Mortality rate of intermediate snail (1/average life expectancy in years)	1/0.5	(36)
se_{POC}	POC-CCA diagnostic sensitivity	0.62	Preliminary estimate (35)
sp_{POC}	POC-CCA diagnostic specificity	0.70	Preliminary estimate (35)
ϵ	Efficacy of praziquantel. Proportion of adult schistosomes killed by treatment	0.9	(37)
<i>Varied parameters</i>			
R_0	Schistosome basic reproductive number	1.5 – 3	This work
$R_{H \rightarrow S}$	Component of R_0 describing transmission from definitive (cattle) host to intermediate (snail) host	1 – 100	This work
N_1/N_2	Definitive (cattle) to intermediate (snail) host population size	0.01 – 0.5	This work
k_0	Overdispersion of schistosomes among definitive (cattle) hosts at (pre-intervention) baseline	0.2 – 1	This work
n	Number of cattle tested by POC-CCA per test-and-treat round	1, 2 or 4	This work

stages of the schistosome lifecycle are compressed into the basic reproduction number $R_0=R_{H \rightarrow S}R_{S \rightarrow H}$. The component $R_{H \rightarrow S}$ captures transmission from cattle to snails and $R_{S \rightarrow H}$ transmission from snails to cattle. The snail mortality rate is denoted μ_2 and N_1/N_2 is the definitive (cattle) to intermediate (snail) host population size. The finite nature (and rapid turnover) of the snail population size provides a natural negative density dependence to constrain the size of the parasite population and the mating probability, $\Phi(W(t), k(t))$ (40) is a positive density-dependent process that leads to the existence of a transmission breakpoint (41). Parameter $k(t)$ is the overdispersion parameter of the negative binomial distribution, which is assumed to capture adequately the distribution of schistosomes among hosts. The time dependency of $k(t)$ results from the changing overdispersion following initiation of treatment (42),

$$k(t) = \begin{cases} k_0, & t < t_T \\ \frac{k_0 W(t)}{(1+k_0)W_0 - k_0 W(t)} = k_1, & t = t_T \\ \frac{W(t)^2(W_0 - W_1)^2}{(W_0^2/k_0)(W(t) - W_1)^2 + (W_1^2/k_1)(W(t) - W_0)^2}, & t > t_T \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where k_0 , k_1 , W_0 and W_1 are the overdispersion parameters and mean worm burden at baseline (pre-intervention, subscript 0) and immediately after treatment (subscript 1), respectively, and t_T denotes a treatment time. The prevalence of infection, $\pi(t)$, is derived from the negative binomial distribution of worms among hosts (40)

$$\pi(t) = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{W(t)}{k(t)}\right)^{-k(t)} \quad (4)$$

Baseline conditions, parametric uncertainty, and interventions

We ran the model to endemic equilibrium using 100,000 parameter sets drawn from a Latin hypercube, sampling R_0 , $R_{H \rightarrow S}$, N_1/N_2 and k_0 from uniform prior distributions (see Table 1). We then selected randomly 250 parameter sets within $\pm 1\%$ of 5% increments in baseline prevalence from 40% to 95%. Using these parameter sets we modelled the impact of a TnT intervention strategy (see Figure 1) using PZQ starting in 2022 and continuing annually with the last TnT round implemented in 2030. At each TnT round, the probability of a herd receiving treatment is given by the probability of at least one positive POC-CCA test result, $P(+\geq 1)$, from n sampled animals

$$P(+\geq 1) = 1 - (1 - se_{POC} \times \pi(t) - (1 - sp_{POC}) \times (1 - \pi(t)))^n \quad (5)$$

where se_{POC} and sp_{POC} denote the sensitivity and specificity of the POC-CCA respectively. Note that we assume a parallel testing regimen whereby n animals are tested simultaneously and if at least one positive test is returned, treatment is triggered. Combining $P(+\geq 1)$ with the efficacy of PZQ, ϵ , we thus modelled the (average) effect of treatment at each TnT round as

$$W(t + dt) = W(t) - W(t)P(+ \geq 1) \epsilon \text{ for } t = tT$$

Test-and-treat effectiveness indicators

We evaluated the effectiveness of the TnT intervention by two metrics. First, we calculated the case-years averted to the end of 2030 as a percentage of the baseline prevalence in 2022 (endemic equilibrium before the first round of TnT),

Percent case-years averted

$$= \frac{1}{9 \times \pi(2022)} \int_{t=2022}^{t=2030} (\pi(2022) - \pi(t)) dt \quad (7)$$

Second, we calculated the percentage of simulations within each prevalence category that nominally reached elimination, here defined as having a prevalence of less than 1% at the end of 2030. Note that this is different from the WHO elimination as a public health problem threshold of 1% *heavy* infections which could not be applied readily to livestock because of the difficulty in quantifying infection intensity.

Diagnostic performance dynamics

In addition to calculating the probability that at least one POC-CCA would return a positive result (and thus trigger treatment with PZQ, Equation 5), we also calculated the positive predictive value (PPV, assuming a parallel testing strategy) as an indicator of the performance of TnT in being able to detect correctly infected bovines during the intervention,

Positive predictive value

$$= \frac{se_{POC} \times \pi(t)}{se_{POC} \times \pi(t) + (1 - se_{POC})(1 - \pi(t))} \quad (8)$$

TABLE 2 Estimates of 'apparent' and 'true' prevalence of bovine schistosomiasis in eight locations in Richard Toll, Senegal sampled in 2017.

Location	N_{KK}^a	Apparent prevalence by KK	N_{MHT}^b	Apparent prevalence by MHT	Mean posterior 'true' prevalence (95% CrI ^c)
Didjiery	35	66%	20	85%	95% (85% – 100%)
Mbane	11	36%	7	100%	90% (64% – 100%)
Medina Cheikhou	25	68%	22	82%	93% (80% – 100%)
Ndombo	11	27%	6	50%	60% (29% – 92%)
Sanente	12	0%	5	60%	43% (13% – 82%)
Temeye	6	0%	3	67%	50% (13% – 91%)
Thiago	29	14%	12	67%	60% (35% – 84%)
Yetti Yone	71	15%	30	97%	89% (70% – 100%)

^aNumber of cattle sampled by Kato-Katz (KK).

^bnumber of cattle sampled by miracidial hatching technique (MHT).

^cCredible interval.

Results

Prevalence of bovine schistosomiasis

The apparent prevalence (by either KK or MHT) and the estimated 'true' prevalence of *Schistosoma* spp. infection among cattle in the eight sampled locations in RT are shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. The high sensitivity of MHT compared to KK (~79% vs. ~31%) ensures greater concordance between the 'true' prevalence and that observed by MHT compared to KK (Figure 2). Bayesian posterior 'true' prevalence estimates ranged from 43% (95% credible interval, CrI: 13%, 82%) to 95% (95% CrI: 85%, 100%), with six of the eight locations having a 'true' prevalence greater than 50%. These estimates informed the prevalence range (40% to 95%) considered in the modelling of TnT.

Infection dynamics

The modelled prevalence dynamics during a TnT intervention between 2022 and 2030 using either $n=1$, $n=2$ or $n=4$ POC-CCA tests per herd are illustrated in Figure 3 for a (pre-intervention) baseline prevalence of 50%, 70% and 90%. Each TnT round is assumed to be implemented at the start of each year, with the reduction in prevalence being a function of the efficacy of PZQ (90%, Table 1) and the probability of at least one positive POC-CCA test (i.e., conditional on at least one positive test, all animals are treated). Consequently, the more animals tested, the greater the impact of each TnT round. Depending on the level of endemicity (baseline prevalence) and the number of tests administered per TnT round, infection dynamics can either stabilize at a suppressed 'pseudo equilibrium' or can continue to decline towards transmission breakpoints.

Effectiveness of test-and-treat

The reduction in bovine schistosomiasis case-years as a percentage of the baseline prevalence achieved by the end of 2030 are shown in Figure 4. The relative impact of interventions decreases slightly with increasing baseline prevalence. For example, when four animals are tested per TnT round, the mean case-years averted range from a maximum of approximately 85% at a starting prevalence of 40% to approximately 75% at 95% baseline prevalence. When two animals are tested per round, the corresponding reductions range from approximately 75% at 40% baseline prevalence to

approximately 60% at 95% baseline prevalence. Irrespective of baseline prevalence, the maximum achievable percentage reduction in case-years over the 9-year time horizon (2022 through 2030) is approximately 85%.

The percentage of simulations reaching a prevalence of less than 1% by the end of 2030, defined nominally here as 'elimination' is shown in Figure 5. Elimination is an unlikely outcome when using $n=1$ or $n=2$ tests per TnT round, but for $n=4$ there is up to approximately 75% chance of achieving the 1% elimination target by the end of 2030 in low prevalence settings and, even in the highest prevalence settings, the chance is greater than 10%.

Diagnostic performance dynamics

Modelled changes in the PPV during the TnT intervention are shown in Figure 6. The dynamics illustrate how the PPV (or the probability of detecting at least one truly infected animal; ‘true positive’)—while being relatively high at pre-intervention baseline—declines during TnT with the declining prevalence of

schistosomiasis (Figure 3). By 2030, for $n=4$ tests per TnT round, the PPV is less than 25% for 90% baseline prevalence and less than 5% for 50% and 70% baseline prevalence. The use of fewer tests retains a higher PPV because of the diminished likelihood of detecting a false positive—specificity declines in powers of n —and the reduced impact on schistosomiasis prevalence (Figures 3, 4).

Discussion

The recently launched WHO NTD 2021–2030 Roadmap and WHO guideline for the control and elimination of human schistosomiasis include within their strategy a consideration of potential control of infection in animal reservoirs (8, 30, 31). Here, we have explored the potential effectiveness of a TnT strategy (Figure 1) targeting bovine schistosomiasis motivated by epidemiological data collected in northern Senegal where the prevalence in bovines can be greater than 90% (Table 2). We show that a hypothetical herd-level TnT intervention running from 2022 through 2030 could have a substantial impact on bovine schistosomiasis, averting up to 85% of case-years (Figure 4) and, in lower prevalence settings, effecting a substantial chance of local elimination/interruption of transmission (Figure 5). Hence, if TnT was used at scale and targeted at multiple livestock species (i.e., whichever key hosts are playing a role in transmission within the area, such as goats, sheep and beyond, as well as cattle as simulated here), it could not only facilitate the WHO elimination goals for human schistosomiasis—by limiting spillover infection from animal reservoirs to humans and concurrent opportunities for interspecific hybridization—but also enhance productivity and livelihoods, further helping to lift people out of poverty.

Notwithstanding the clear potential benefits of treating livestock and reducing the burden of schistosomiasis, an equally important objective behind the TnT strategy is to avoid unnecessary treatment of uninfected herds. Achieving this objective also critically depends on the specificity of the diagnostic test used. We modelled TnT here using the POC-CCA diagnostic which was originally developed and validated for the detection of *S. mansoni* in humans (43), but that has also been recently shown to have moderate sensitivity (~62%) and specificity (~70%) for detecting intestinal livestock schistosomes caused by *S. bovis* and *S. curassoni* (35). The use of a POC test—

as opposed to more specific traditional faecal parasitology—is important to facilitate the ease of implementing TnT strategies at scale. Moreover, our data show clearly that parasitology based on KK of livestock stool has very poor sensitivity (see Table 2 and Figure 2A). However, the estimated specificity of currently available POC-CCA may be too low to satisfy confidence requirements to avoid initiation and continuation of TnT in uninfected herds, thus ongoing work to enhance specificity for livestock usage should be prioritized, even at the cost of sensitivity. With improved specificity, adaptive strategies could also be developed to help meet the dual TnT objectives. For example, the use of a single test to identify and initiate TnT would minimize the risk of an initial false positive and subsequent testing could be implemented only after several completed treatment rounds to lower the number of potentially missed treatments. Alternatively, initial testing could aim to quantify herd-level prevalence (adjusting for sensitivity and specificity) and mathematical modelling used to project the likely number of treatment rounds required to reach pre-defined objectives.

Modelling the transmission dynamics of human schistosomiasis has been used extensively in recent years to evaluate the impact of MDA and to inform decision making on strategies to reach the WHO's elimination goals (44–46). Modelling has, however, been seldom applied to livestock schistosomiasis, although some key modelling analyses have quantified contributions of zoonotic reservoirs and human-animal schistosome hybrids to infection dynamics in humans (10, 25). Nonetheless, there remains great uncertainty in our understanding of the population biology and transmission dynamics of livestock schistosomiasis, which we have tried to reflect in the modelling presented here. Some uncertainties are common to both human and livestock infection. For example, the role of acquired immunity, while long suspected to contribute to the epidemiological patterns observed in

human schistosomiasis (47, 48), has not been elucidated completely in either humans or animals and its effects may alter the effectiveness of MDA (49). Moreover, a recent eco-evolutionary hypothesis linking worm-directed concomitant immunity and epidemiological patterns in humans presents further (potential) consequences for schistosome control (50). Other processes that regulate schistosome populations—such as density-dependent fecundity—are also debated and incompletely understood in both humans and animals (51). The impact on the transmission breakpoint (i.e., the minimum infection level that can sustain parasite transmission) of repeated MDA rounds has, however, been explored in a recent mathematical analysis of helminth burdens within a human population (42). Treatment non-compliance was highlighted as a key challenge that increases parasite overdispersion (smaller k) and further complicates elimination (by increasing parasite population resilience) (42). We have incorporated this important phenomenon into our model *via* a dynamic overdispersion parameter that varies through repeated TnT rounds. In addition, modelling schistosome dynamics in livestock is complicated by the often-fragmented nature of livestock herds in small rural communities, the impacts of seasonality on transmission risk and livestock migration (particularly amongst transhumance populations), as well as the limited understanding of environmental exposure (i.e., waterbody interaction) among dispersed populations.

Given these uncertainties, the modelling presented here should therefore be viewed as illustrative of the potential impact of TnT. Animals within herds are assumed to experience similar infection risk as they will be exposed to potentially contaminated water sources as a group. In the proposed simulated strategy, a representative small number of animals are tested to determine whether the herd is likely to be infected, and the whole herd is treated when an infected member of the group is detected. For simplicity and as proof-of-principle, we have only modelled schistosome burden in one animal host (bovines) within a perennial transmission location, given that in the Northern Senegal study area upon which model parameters are based, bovines are thought to act as the primary zoonotic reservoir of *S. bovis* (25). Notwithstanding, it is apparent, that both large and small ruminants can be heavily infected with blood flukes across Africa, and with *Schistosoma* species that can infect humans through viable hybridization with *S. haematobium*. In addition to this, wildlife, notably rodents and non-human primates can also play a significant role in zoonotic transmission of both intestinal and urogenital schistosomes to humans (52, 53). Thus, we have deliberately simplified many structural (e.g., inter-connected nature of herds) and biological (e.g., role of acquired and/or concomitant immunity; role of multiple animal reservoirs in schistosome transmission) complexities that would alter the transmission

dynamics. Nonetheless, the clear contribution of cattle in spillover to humans in SSA in conjunction to the feasibility and numerous benefits of implementing control measures in these domestic ruminants (public and veterinary health benefits plus economic benefits) justify efforts to design a coherent and comprehensive strategy that includes them.

Nevertheless, there are numerous practical and logistical challenges that must be overcome to make TnT viable. Appropriate veterinary dosages and commercially available products tailored to livestock alongside stakeholder education would contribute to avoiding the current *ad hoc* use (and misuse) at livestock owners discretion (26) and minimize the risk of PZQ resistance. Critically, within Africa, PZQ is currently donated for human use only and while there may be some market to purchase PZQ by larger farmers because of the productivity benefits—particularly for small ruminants (27)—it is highly unlikely that a livestock-centric schistosomiasis program would be sustainable without some form of third-party donation.

Yet while there remain major challenges to the implementation of TnT, the evidence is now incontrovertible that livestock act as reservoirs for schistosome hybridization (9, 15–17, 20) and that livestock schistosomiasis causes significant economic and productivity losses (26, 27), compounding further the lives and livelihoods of impoverished populations. The need to address this challenge has been articulated by the WHO (8, 30). The findings we present here confirm that a TnT approach has the potential to be an effective strategy in controlling livestock schistosomiasis within a broader One Health approach eliminating NTDs.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are publicly available. Code for dynamic transmission model and associated data available at <https://github.com/martwalker/schistoTnT> and for the statistical model at <https://github.com/martwalker/trueprev>. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding authors.

Ethics statement

The animal study was reviewed and approved by: (i) Imperial College London (London, UK) application 03.36; (ii) the CRERB at the Royal Veterinary College (London, UK) application URN20151327; and (iii) the Comité National d'Éthique pour la Recherche en Santé (Dakar, Senegal) application SEN15/68. Written informed consent was obtained from the owners for the participation of their animals in this study.

Author contributions

JW and MW conceptualized the work. MW, SL, MN, and AD developed the mathematical methodology. MW and AD carried out the formal analysis. EL, AB, ND, and JW, collected and analyzed the samples and the data that this work is based on, with fieldwork and permissions facilitated by MS. AD, MW, and JW wrote the original draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed to the article and approved the submitted version.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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D. Chapter 2 Appendices

Table D1. Age estimates for bovines surveyed during the ZELS project in Richard Toll and Barkedji, Senegal.

ZELS Dataset	Age range (years)	No. observations	Mean	Standard deviation
Live bovines	0 - 16	280	4.14	3.60
Abattoir bovines	0-15	63	6.06	3.32
Combined bovines	0-16	343	4.49	3.63

Senegalese live bovines from Richard Toll and Barkedji were younger than abattoir bovines, with a combined (i.e., live and abattoir bovines) mean of 4.49 years. Consequently, the test-and-treat model was fitted with a bovine life expectancy of 5 years.

Histogram of ZELS bovine age estimates (live and abattoir)

Figure D2. Frequency histogram of age estimates in years among cattle surveyed while alive (live) or post-mortem (abattoir) in both ZELS project study sites. When combining both sets of ZELS data (i.e., live and abattoir) (see Table D1), 39% (134/343) of cattle surveyed were 2 years old or less whereas 14.6% (50/343) were 9 years old or above, with a mean age estimate of 4 and 1/2 years (see Table D1). Considering underestimation due to truncation of age ranges—for instance, a 12-years-plus-old animal was coded as 12 years, the test-and-treat model was fitted with a bovine life expectancy of 5 years.

E. Chapter 3 Appendices

Western Africa (2020) Status of Schistosomiasis Elimination

Boundaries, names and designations used here do not imply expression of WHO opinion concerning the legal status of any country, territory or area, or of its authorities, or concerning delimitation of frontiers or boundaries. Dotted / dashed lines represent approximate border lines for which there may not yet be full agreement.

Schistosomiasis > Endemicity

Data Source: Data provided by health ministries to ESPEN through WHO reporting processes. All reasonable precautions have been taken to verify this information. Copyright 2021 WHO. All rights reserved. Generated 11 November 2021

Figure E1. Western Africa human schistosomiasis endemicity. At present, many highly endemic areas (in red) are still found in Senegal. Senegal national borders highlighted in burgundy inside dashed-line rectangle. Source: WHO. Retrieved from: <http://espen.afro.who.int/diseases/schistosomiasis>.

Figure E2. Map of northern Senegal localities surveyed from May 2016 to January 2018, as part of the ZELS project, with the aim of studying schistosomiasis prevalence in humans, snails, and livestock. Source: Leger et al, 2020. Retrieved from:

[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanplh/article/PIIS2542-5196\(20\)30129-7/](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanplh/article/PIIS2542-5196(20)30129-7/)

Table E3. Dental age estimation in domestic ruminants ^a.

Pairs of adult teeth (incisors)	Cow Age estimate (years)	Sheep Age estimate (years)	Goat Age estimate (years)
0	<2	<1	<1
1	2	1-1.5	1-1.5
2	2.5	1.5-2	1.5-2
3	3.5	2-2.5	2-2.5
4 ^b	3.5-4	2.5-4	2.5-3
B ^c	>5	>5	>5

^a Adapted from MSD manual (Merck & Co Inc. 2024)

^b 4th incisor refers to the canine tooth of domestic ruminants.

^c B refers to “broken mouth” which denotes deterioration after eruption of all adult teeth.

Barplot of age estimates of treated bovines

Figure E4. Distribution of recorded dental age estimates among pre-and post-praziquantel study bovines.

Barplot of age estimates of treated goats

Figure E5. Distribution of recorded dental age estimates among pre-and post-praziquantel study goats.

Barplot of age estimates of treated sheep

Figure E6. Distribution of recorded dental age estimates among pre-and post-praziquantel study sheep.

F. Chapter 4 Appendices

Table F1. *Schistosoma* species *cox1* and ITS characterisation of a subset of pre- and post-praziquantel study parasites collected from Senegalese cattle.

Animal ID	cox1/ITS status of pre-PZQ samples			cox1/ITS status of post-PZQ evaluated samples			Host classification relative to treatment
	# <i>Sb</i>	# not conclusive	# evaluated	# <i>Sb</i>	# not conclusive	# evaluated	
DB17	5	3	8	0	1	1	Non-responder
DB42	3	1	4	0	16	16	Non-responder
MB1	2	0	2	1	7	8	Non-responder
MB7	8	0	8	0	1	1	Non-responder
MB9	0	3	3	0	8	8	Non-responder
MB10	0	7	7	0	8	8	Non-responder
MB25	3	5	8	0	8	8	Non-responder
NB2	7	1	8	0	1	1	Non-responder
NB6	1	7	8	0	5	5	Non-responder
NB7	0	8	8	0	1	1	Non-responder
NB8	1	7	8	0	1	1	Non-responder
TGB2	0	2	2				Responder
TGB3	1	0	1				Responder
TGB4	5	3	8				Responder
TGB5	3	5	8				Responder
TGB6	0	2	2				Responder
TGB7	0	7	7				Responder
DB4	7	1	8				Responder
DB5	3	2	5				Responder
DB7	7	1	8				Responder
DB9	1	1	2				Responder
DB10	7	1	8				Responder
DB11	7	1	8				Responder
DB12	6	2	8				Responder
DB16	7	1	8				Responder
DB20	3	2	5				Responder
DB21	2	0	2				Responder
DB22	6	0	6				Responder
DB25	1	0	1				Responder
DB30	7	1	8				Responder
DB31	6	2	8				Responder

DB33	8	0	8		Responder
DB36	4	0	4		Responder
DB37	3	2	5		Responder
DB38	7	1	8		Responder
DB39	5	1	6		Responder
DB40	8	0	8		Responder
DB41	3	5	8		Responder
MB2	0	1	1		Responder
MB3	8	0	8		Responder
MB4	6	1	7		Responder
MB5	1	0	1		Responder
MB8	4	0	4		Responder
MB12	0	2	2		Responder
MB15	1	0	1		Responder
MB16	0	1	1		Responder
MB17	1	2	3		Responder
MB21	5	2	7		Responder
MB26	6	2	8		Responder
MCB1	1	2	3		Responder
MCB2	1	3	4		Responder
MCB4	0	1	1		Responder
MCB5	4	4	8		Responder
MCB6	0	2	2		Responder
MCB7	1	0	1		Responder
MCB8	2	5	7		Responder

Abbreviations: pre-PZQ, pre-praziquantel; post-PZQ, post-praziquantel; Sb, *Schistosoma bovis*.

Table F2. Qubit DNA yield from eluted miracidia and Nanodrop DNA yield from eluted worms.

Host ID	Type of sample	dsDNA (ng/ μ l)
DB17	Pre-PZQ miracidia	Sample out of range, too low*
NB6	Pre-PZQ miracidia	0.143
NB6	Pre-PZQ miracidia	0.171
NB7	Pre-PZQ miracidia	0.103
DB42	Post-PZQ miracidia	Sample out of range, too low**
MB9	Post-PZQ miracidia	0.060
5B2	ZELS female worm ¹	10.213
5B2	ZELS male worm ¹	11.396
5B2	ZELS female worm ²	7.271
5B2	ZELS male worm ²	12.984
4B10	ZELS female worm ¹	9.062
4B10	ZELS male worm ¹	12.138
4B10	ZELS female worm ²	9.239
4B10	ZELS male worm ²	11.017

Abbreviations: dsDNA, double stranded DNA. ¹First female-male couple collected from animal host. ²Second female-male couple collected from animal host. *Too low despite successful genotyping. **Not amplified.

F3. Optimised two-panel multiplex PCR protocol for 12 selected *S. bovis* microsatellite markers, for amplification of *S. bovis* miracidia.

Almost all multiplex primers are taken from Webster et al, 2015 erratum, except for Sha_104176_i13 designed by Boon et al, 2019, henceforth referred to as Sha.

Lyophilized primers with a concentration of 80,000 pM are stored as 100 µM stock solutions by adding 800 µl of molecular water to each tube (one forward (F) and one reverse (R) primer tube per primer pair). Stock solutions (100 pmol/µl) to be aliquoted and stored at -20°C, protected from light to prevent loss of fluorescence.

Primer panel mix using a 100 µM stock solution aliquot for each primer pair as below:

Panel 1 primer mix		Panel 2 primer mix	
Sh9	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer	Sh13	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer
Sh3	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer	Sh4	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer
Sh1	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer	Sh11	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer
Sh14	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer	Sh15	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer
Sh6	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer	Sh2	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer
Sha	10 µl F primer + 10 µl R primer	Sh12	5 µl F primer + 5 µl R primer

Then, add molecular water to each primer mix for a total volume of 250 µl.

Multiplex PCR reagents:

Component	Volume for one reaction	Final concentration
2x Type-it Multiplex PCR Master Mix	6.25 µl	1 x
Primer mix	1.25 µl	0.2 µM for almost all, with exception of Sha 0.4 µM
Q-Solution, 5x	1.25 µl	0.5 x
RNase-free water	0.75 µl	
Template DNA (miracidia)	3 µl	
TOTAL:	12.5 µl	

Cycling conditions:

	Temp	Time
Denaturing	95°C	15 min
[35 cycles]		
Denaturing	94°C	30 secs
Annealing	56°C	90 secs
Extension	72°C	60 secs
Extension	60°C	30 min
Store	4°C	∞

Gel Electrophoresis to visualize PCR product:

Make a 2% agarose solution with 1X TAE. Once the solution is cool enough, add 1 µl of SYBR Safe for each 10 ml of TAE (e.g., 15 µl for a 150 ml gel). Once the gel has set, load 4ul of PCR product plus 2ul of loading dye into the gel wells. Flank with 100 bp hyper ladder. Run the gel for ~50 minutes at 120 V.

Table F4. Number of private alleles (Ap), observed heterozygosity (Ho), and summary of Chi-squared (X^2) tests for Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium per loci of pre-PZQ schistosome isolates by location.

Loci	Djidièry (n=58)				Mbane (n=66)				Ndombo (n=51)			
	Ap	Ho	df	X^2	Ap	Ho	df	X^2	Ap	Ho	df	X^2
Sh9	2	0.845	91	117.731 ^a	2	0.800	91	194.378 ^c	1	0.760	66	95.814 ^b
Sh3	1	0.891	190	252.107 ^b	1	0.869	210	234.498	2	0.850	153	163.664
Sh1	0	0.983	91	114.268	0	0.924	91	112.304	0	0.882	78	80.974
Sh14	0	0.877	15	13.925	3	0.708	36	17.667	0	0.706	10	7.990
Sh6	0	0.491	10	49.786 ^c	1	0.429	21	59.038 ^c	0	0.541	10	13.549
Sha	4	0.420	153	285.450 ^c	1	0.350	78	259.101 ^c	4	0.342	66	158.407 ^c
Sh13	2	0.948	153	144.864	0	0.924	153	150.636	0	0.960	171	200.259
Sh4	0	0.870	105	106.010	0	0.898	78	86.651	2	0.830	120	181.115 ^c
Sh11	0	0.605	28	24.040	0	0.518	21	22.997	0	0.675	21	18.175
Sh15	0	0.268	3	0.873	1	0.133	3	9.465 ^a	0	0.273	3	1.097
Sh2	0	0.912	171	168.640	0	0.859	171	193.034	1	0.900	136	200.874 ^c
Sh12	0	0.638	3	1.707	1	0.631	6	4.503	1	0.588	6	1.879

Abbreviations: n, number of analysed isolates; df, degrees of freedom of Chi-squared test.

^{a, b, c} Significance, respectively $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$.

Table F5. Number of private alleles (Ap), observed heterozygosity (Ho), and summary of Chi-squared (X²) tests for Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium per loci of schistosome isolates by treatment status.

Loci	Pre-PZQ (n=32)				Post-PZQ (n=25)			
	Ap	Ho	df	X ²	Ap	Ho	df	X ²
Sh9	1	0.700	45	66.887 ^a	1	0.667	36	37.959
Sh3	4	0.625	153	202.154 ^b	1	0.706	105	140.722 ^a
Sh1	2	0.733	66	83.195	2	0.833	66	56.650
Sh14	2	0.438	21	54.401 ^c	1	0.696	15	6.224
Sh6	2	0.333	10	31.497 ^c	1	0.250	6	12.480
Sha	2	0.217	15	52.788 ^c	4	0.250	28	82.287 ^c
Sh13	2	0.724	78	75.408	4	0.833	105	91.898
Sh4	3	0.621	66	77.553	0	0.500	36	54.896 ^a
Sh11	1	0.353	10	9.386	2	0.533	15	9.833
Sh15	0	0.056 ^b	1	10.610 ^b	1	0.267	3	0.355
Sh2	5	0.586 ^c	153	226.767 ^c	0	0.773	78	81.944
Sh12	0	0.567	6	1.351	0	0.591	6	3.868

Abbreviations: n, number of analysed isolates; df, degrees of freedom of Chi-squared test.

^{a, b, c} Significance, respectively p<0.05, p<0.01, p<0.001.

Figure F6. Delta K plot clearly showing best K estimate for the pre-PZQ analysis was K=4.

Figure F7. Delta K plot clearly showing best K estimate for the pre vs post PZQ analysis was K=2.